

Deliverable D8.1

Successful implementation of CS ELSI and procedures for data protection, record and sample retrieval, and for record and sample withdrawal from the Biobank

D8.1

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Table of Contents

List of Figures	ii
List of Tables	ii
Table of abbreviations	iii
1 Introduction.....	4
1.1 Foreground.....	4
1.2 General Objectives	4
1.3 Approach.....	4
2 Implementation Report.....	5
2.1 Governance.....	5
2.1.1 Approval by the CNBC.....	7
2.1.2 Evaluation of Research Proposals	7
2.2 Data and Samples	8
2.2.1 Data Management and Standardization.....	8
2.2.2 GDPR Implementation.....	8
2.2.3 Material Transfer Agreement / Data Transfer Agreement.....	9
2.3 Participation	10
2.3.1 Informed Consent	10
2.3.2 Incidental Findings.....	10
2.3.3 Genetic Counseling	13
2.3.4 Withdrawal Procedure and Destruction of Data/Samples	13
2.3.5 Vulnerability and Minors' Participation	14
2.4 Engagement.....	15
3 Sustainability of the ELSI Perspective beyond the Work Package.....	15
3.1 Involvement in the Documentation Base	15
3.2 Typology of Risks and Genomic Identifiability	15
3.3 Sustainable Risk Governance: Mapping Risks.....	18
3.3.1 Adapting Situational Analysis for Mapping Risks	18
4 Conclusions.....	19
5 References	20
6 Appendix	22

List of Figures

Figure 1. Organizational structure of biobank.cy Center of Excellence	6
Figure 2. Incidental Findings: Scenarios	12
Figure 3. Typology of risks	17

List of Tables

Table 1. List of attached documents	22
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Table of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
ACMG	American College of Medical Genetics
biobank.cy	The short name of the “ <i>Center of Excellence in Biobanking and Biomedical Research</i> ”, created in Cyprus as a result of the CY-Biobank funded project
BBMRI	Biobanking and BioMolecular resources Research Infrastructure
CMT	Charcot-Marie-Tooth Disease
CNBC	Cyprus National Bioethics Committee
CoE	Center of Excellence
CY-Biobank	The short name of the funded project, “Biobanking and the Cyprus Human Genome Project”
DPO	Data Protection Officer
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DTA	Data Transfer Agreement
ELSI	Ethical, Legal and Societal Implications
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESHG	European Society of Human Genetics
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ISAC	International Scientific Advisory Committee
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
ICF	Informed Consent Form
IF	Incidental Findings
IT	Information Technologies
MIABIS	Minimum Information About Biobank data Sharing
MMRC	Molecular Medicine Research Center
MTA	Material Transfer Agreement
MUG	Medical University Graz
NIH	National Institutes of Health
OMIM	Online Mendelian Inheritance in Man
QM	Quality Management
QMS	Quality Management System
REC	Research Ethics Committee
UCY	University of Cyprus
WHO	World Health Organization
WMA	World Medical Association
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Foreground

This report describes the implementation of ethical, legal, and societal implications (ELSI) recommendations, procedures for data protection, record and sample retrieval and for record and sample withdrawal from the biobank.

In this regard, BBMRI-ERIC's ELSI Services & Research¹ experts² guided and advised the CY-Biobank project consortium on harmonizing and monitoring its procedures, specifically on consent process, incidental findings, risk assessment, composition of independent ethics committees, Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA), inclusion of minors/vulnerable groups in research, general ethical principles, and the GDPR implementation.

Medical University Graz (MUG) and Biobank Graz provided input that relates to topics such as sensitive aspects arising from large number of participants and further guidance, e.g., on Clinical Trial Directive and Commission Directive 2005/28/EC.

CY-Biobank personnel ensured working coherently towards the goals of the work package in preparing and updating the Biobank documentation, applying recommended procedures and regulations and striving towards increased transparency and openness.

1.2 General Objectives

The main objectives of WP8 are to:

- apply the BBMRI-ERIC ELSI Services & Research unit's (formerly CS ELSI) recommended procedures and regulations,
- maintain transparency and openness to the scientific community and the lay public,
- set up procedures and prepare documents for donor enrolment and sample collection and retrieval and patient withdrawal.

Please note that there is a great overlap of activities and expectations related to WP8 and WP11, the last work package which was added by the European Commission on ethical requirements, after approval of the project.

1.3 Approach

COVID-19 pandemic resulted in a necessity to move WP8 activities to online platforms. Due to the lack of on-site collaboration possibilities and the difficulties of online engagements, WP8 activities have been re-organized in an approach adaptive to the necessities of the local context, the COVID-19 pandemic and technical possibilities. In order to reach the above-mentioned objectives, the ELSI activities included the following: active engagement, passive guidance and complementary commentaries.

The guidance and advice often took the form of *active engagement*, meetings, organization of topical workshops, responses to questions, but also *passive guidance* in the form of suggested documents, guidelines and templates. Furthermore, a major element of this process was supporting the development of the

¹ In 2014, BBMRI-ERIC established the Common Service ELSI (CS ELSI), which comprised ELSI experts from across its member states and headquarters to provide guidance on ethical, legal and societal issues. Following an extensive evaluation process and a simplification in its governance structure, the CS ELSI was renamed as ELSI Services & Research.

² Unless otherwise noted, the experts who have contributed to the work package and its tasks directly include Kaya Akyüz, PhD candidate (BBMRI-ERIC), Sara Casati, PhD (BBMRI-ERIC), legal advisor Gauthier Chassang (INSERM), Signe Mezinska, PhD (BBMRI.lv), Olga Tzortzatou, PhD (subcontracted expert) and Michaela Th. Mayrhofer, PhD (BBMRI-ERIC).

infrastructure that included drafting of the documents or the improvement of existing documents. The guidance in such cases, e.g., in the case of the informed consent form or the incidental findings policy, was complemented by produced *commentaries* that directly tackled existing or potential ethical, legal and societal issues.

In all these activities, the overarching aspect that has been identified as crucial for the success of the project was a good risk governance structure. The reasoning behind is two-fold. First, ethical, legal and societal implications are often entangled in risks, from *public* perception of risks associated with participation in the Biobank to the risk of genomic identifiability for the *participant* or even risk of litigation for the Biobank. Second, risks are not restricted to the early period during which the Biobank within the Center of Excellence (CoE) is establishing itself as an infrastructure. Instead, risks are only partially foreseeable even for a well-established Biobank functioning for many years. Third, rather than doing an analysis of the local risks for biobank.cy Center of Excellence from an external perspective, it is imperative to foster practices that would include multiple actors within and beyond the institution in the assessment, communication and mitigation of risks.

Considering that WP8 would have been the first work package to end according to the grant agreement (before amendment), even before WP2-Physical Premises & Equipment Infrastructure and WP4-Bioinformatics & eHealth, our approach necessitated careful consideration of a continuous ELSI presence within the project, beyond the work package's scope and duration, most notably WP3-Quality Management, where ethico-legal management aspects remain a critical cornerstone of quality standards for implementation and operation of the CoE. Toward this purpose, a research paper on typology of risks has been drafted and a public workshop on genomic identifiability has been organized, contributing both to biobank.cy and the biobanking community in general. The manuscript, which will be submitted within 2021Q1 will serve as cornerstone for the next workshop of WP8 to take place in March/April 2021, where quality management (QM), information technologies (IT) and ELSI perspectives will be brought together to support a sustainable risk governance for the Biobank and the CoE as a whole.

2 Implementation Report

2.1 Governance

biobank.cy Center of Excellence is designed as a multi-layered infrastructure built on five pillars: Innovation Hub, Education Hub, Molecular Medicine Research Center, the Biobank and the Diagnostic Lab. Along with other consortium members and work packages, WP8 has been making suggestions towards a good governance that is summarized in the following organizational structure (see Figure 1).

Before this project, the Biobank (as *Biobank with Specialization in Kidney and other Genetic Diseases* under Molecular Medicine Research Center) had a constitution³ describing its background and how it operates. As this constitution predated the implementation of EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and it did not correspond to the current and planned organizational infrastructure of the CoE, numerous changes were followed upon guidance by the WP8 team, along with further input from other work packages. Bylaws of a German Biobank have been shared with biobank.cy as an example. biobank.cy improved the existing by-laws by considering the necessities that emerged with the CoE structure as well as the ELSI guidance (see Appendix A1 for the new by-laws).

The guidance provided centered around principles of transparency and accountability and stressed the following:

- Prioritization of participant's well-being and rights over the interests of users of samples and data,
- Implementation of mechanisms of supervision ensuring the functioning of the Biobank in compliance with the relevant laws and regulations as well as ethical standards,
- Scientific integrity and implementation of oversight mechanisms,

³ The original (previous) constitution of the biobank:

http://www.ucy.ac.cy/mmrc/documents/Biobank_Constitution_Eng_240716.pdf

- Public engagement and dissemination in line with transparency standards (accessibility of research results, when possible),
- Optimal and respectful use and sharing of samples and data as limited and valuable resources.

Figure 1. Organizational structure of biobank.cy Center of Excellence

WP8's contribution to the governance has often been part of broader discussions including the implementation of the in WP3 addressed quality management standards (e.g., ISO 9001) or building of the technical infrastructure that relates to other work package activities. From the ELSI perspective, our guidance relied on the relevant European and international guidelines and informational material that may benefit the good governance structure. These include *Operational Guidelines for Ethics Committees that Review Biomedical Research* (World Health Organization, 2000), *Research ethics committees: Basic concepts for capacity-building* (World Health Organization, 2009), *WMA Declaration of Taipei on Ethical Considerations regarding Health Databases and Biobanks* (World Medical Association, 2016).

We have highlighted that there is no uniformity across the governance structures among European biobanks (Kaye et al., 2016), but also referred to efforts towards harmonization⁴ including those by BBMRI-ERIC. Furthermore, we pointed to training resources, such as the *Training and Resources in Research Ethics Evaluation* (TRREE)⁵ program, that would provide further knowledge to the relevant biobank.cy staff. We have also pointed out specific aspects that have arisen during the exchanges including but not limited to potential conflicts of interest, representation of patients/participants, necessity to determine internal rules in writing (clear statement of the mission, criteria for being appointed to committees, the frequency of meetings, reporting practices). Besides the Project Management Committee, which pertains specifically to the management of the CY-Biobank project funded by the European Commission, the following bodies have been established to

⁴ See Ethical Governance Framework and Ethics Check for ADOPT BBMRI-ERIC:

https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/wp-content/uploads/D5.7_Rev1.pdf;

Horizon 2020: Guidance on Ethics Self-Assessment (European Commission):

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/ethics/h2020_hi_ethics-self-assess_en.pdf

⁵ Training and Resources in Research Ethics Evaluation:

<https://elearning.trree.org/mod/page/view.php?id=18>

manage and govern the biobank.cy CoE, and the current compositions as well as detailed descriptions are available in Appendix A1:

- Academic Council and the Director General (responsible for management of the CoE including budgetary and administrative decisions),
- Stakeholder's Forum (engagement between Biobank representatives, collaborators, patient organizations, medical societies, and industry representatives according to Stakeholders' Action Plan),
- Internal Ethics Advisory Board (responsible mainly for advice on internal/external requests for data or samples, following ethics approval by relevant bodies for the project, e.g., by Cyprus National Bioethics Committee),
- External Ethics Advisory Boards (responsible for monitoring the ELSI issues, and initially, annual reporting as part of WP11 deliverables),
- International Scientific Advisory Committee (ISAC; responsible for strategic advice to the Director of the CoE and the Academic Council) (to be finalized yet),
- CoE Council (advisory role for long-term planning and strategy as part of University of Cyprus internal regulation).

Updated by-laws (see Appendix A1) are currently under review by WP8. Similarly, documents such as Impartiality Agreement / Disclosure of Conflict of Interest (see Appendix A2) and Access Policy (part of By-laws, see Appendix A1) are currently in use. From the ELSI perspective, certain functions, such as the Data Protection Officer (DPO) and genetic counsellor, were also relevant during the discussions of the governance structure, but these are taken up in later sections.

2.1.1 Approval by the CNBC

In Cyprus, there is no Biobank law and no law concerning the operation of research biobanks. Previously, upon funding by the European Regional Development Fund and the Republic of Cyprus, through the Cyprus Research Promotion Foundation (currently, Research and Innovation Foundation, the main body funding research in Cyprus) under the Strategic Research Infrastructures call, Prof. Constantinos Deltas had led the establishment of the first Biobank in Cyprus, which was approved by the Cyprus National Bioethics Committee (CNBC) for biobanking for genetic diseases for 25 years, starting 01.11.2011.

Within the current project, CY-Biobank, as of 22.07.2020, CNBC approved the application for the new program titled "Biobanking and the Cyprus Human Genome Project" with the following conditions: exclusion of minor participants' samples' from biobanking, the use of the informed consent form EEBK03 for biobanking including external projects and continuous reporting according to Operational Codes of the CNBC. These documents, including the template of the informed consent form are available⁶ on the CNBC website. A copy of the letter of approval by the CNBC (dated 30.09.2020) can be found in the Appendix A3.

2.1.2 Evaluation of Research Proposals

As partially described in the above section on Governance, the biobank.cy CoE built necessary bodies that would function as part of evaluation mechanisms. As part of the new by-laws, an access policy for the Biobank data and samples has been prepared (see Appendix A1). Access policy specifies for which purposes and by whom an access request can be made and if accepted what should be considered, such as protection of confidentiality of participants' data and transparency regarding research results, the status of material and data collected and archived for third parties as pay-for-fee service (solely for partial operational cost recovery) and how to deal with actionable incidental findings.

A prerequisite to applying for accessing samples and data, is necessary prior documented funding, public interest and societal impact, and prior approval by an appropriate ethics committee in the country of the researcher (e.g. CNBC in Cyprus). Following registration and submission of the application, Biobank Access Committee reviews the proposals that satisfy the prerequisites. The committee is comprised of members of

⁶ Operational Codes – Forms on CNBC Websites:

http://www.bioethics.gov.cy/moh/cnbc/cnbc.nsf/dmlform_en/dmlform_en?OpenDocument

the Academic Council and Internal Ethics Board, described above, and evaluates applications according to its compliance with ethical guidelines as well as suitability/availability of the requested material/data and the potential conflicts due to probable current use of the same samples/data by ongoing research projects.

If application is approved, the parties sign the access agreement and depending on the status of the researcher's institution (academic/not-for-profit or private commercial/for-profit), the fee is paid (partial cost recovery or higher/full cost recovery, respectively). Further details, such as intellectual property rights, are clarified in the signed Material Transfer Agreement / Data Transfer Agreement as described below.

2.2 Data and Samples

2.2.1 Data Management and Standardization

The BBMRI-ERIC Quality Management team has extensive experience in the quality management systems and implementation of relevant standards. The CY-Biobank project focused thus far on the establishment of a quality management system (QMS) according to the international standard ISO 9001:2015 "Requirements for quality management systems" (ISO, 2015). The organizational structure has been described above (2.1: Governance) and the ISO 9001 implementation contributes to the organizational basis for the CoE, including all core units. At the same time, the biobanking processes in the Biobank core unit are being set up in accordance with the international standard for biobanking, ISO 20387:2018 "Biobanking – General requirements for biobanking" (ISO, 2018). Furthermore, the QM team in close collaboration with the biobank.cy CoE IT team is safeguarding all relevant aspects of data security and data safety. biobank.cy IT team and the UCY IT team are both working in parallel on embedding the biobank.cy CoE operations according to the international standard ISO/IEC 27001:2013, which focuses on the information security techniques and management systems and had already been initiated by the UCY (ISO & IEC, 2013). The IT team implemented a comprehensive Document Management System (DMS) on Microsoft SharePoint, which serves both the CoE and the Biobank. Since the Diagnostic Lab has not yet been setup, ISO 15189 "Medical laboratories — Requirements for quality and competence" has not been yet been implemented (ISO, 2012). For the detailed reporting of relevant activities, please refer to the deliverables of WP3 (D3.1, D3.2 and D3.3).

WP8 has provided input, whenever necessary, during workshops/meetings organized by WP3 and QM representatives were invited to the workshops organized within WP8. Certain aspects of data management that relate to personal information and data security are covered by the GDPR implementation steps as described in the next section.

2.2.2 GDPR Implementation

WP8 provided biobank.cy guidance on implementation of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) both through exchanges and pointing out relevant resources⁷ available through BBMRI-ERIC Knowledge Base (Mayrhofer & Schlünder, 2018).

The University of Cyprus has its own DPO. Besides, biobank.cy has an agreement with a local legal firm that provides the DPO functionality as well as supporting the CoE on "the preparation and implementation of reports and assessments, such as risk analysis for information security, mapping and analysis of data processing activities, data protection impact assessment (DPIA), information security plan as well as other accountability mechanisms such as internal policies and procedures and external notices" (see Appendix A5) and the IT Security Officer serves as the internal responsible staff.

⁷ Webinar on "The GDPR and Health Research" (Apr 2018):

<https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLlu6KJ19npXz5lqcDVquPNfhgCHOtamPi>

Webinar on "The GDPR – Anonymisation and Pseudonymisation" (June 2018):

https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLlu6KJ19npXxo379cvW9UN_TDwn-H52Eq

The EU General Data Protection Regulation - Answers to Frequently Asked Questions - Version 2.0:

<https://zenodo.org/record/3473120#.YCQ1vM9KjKg>

How Sensitive Is Genetic Data? (Sariyar, Suhr, & Schlünder, 2017)

The appointed DPO has implemented the data protection impact assessment, which will be improved through regular monitoring and review (see Appendix A5). Furthermore, a Confidentiality Agreement (see Appendix A6) has been drafted that informs staff with tasks involving personal data. Towards an improved information security, a Security Policy (Appendix A7) has been drafted by the IT Security Officer. This covers aspects regarding processing of personal data of the participants and the employees, processes in cases of technical and physical problems or security incidents as well as long-term assessment and evaluation of the effectiveness of measures.

2.2.3 Material Transfer Agreement / Data Transfer Agreement

Material Transfer Agreement (MTA) and Data Transfer Agreement (DTA) are central to the use of samples and data at a Biobank by external parties. Although they are legal documents, their content is also relevant from ethical and societal perspectives. WP8 reviewed the MTA provided by biobank.cy. It has been acknowledged that the MTA has been successfully prepared and with a written commentary, potential issues that may arise due to the current state of the document have been highlighted. At the time of the review the DTA was not yet finalized; however, the points of critique have been raised in ways that may also be useful while drafting the DTA.

Some of the points raised included:

- distinctions between commercial and non-commercial recipients that may not hold in certain settings,
- definition of the “third party” and parts relating to “destruction of samples” that may restrict the possibility for replication of experiments, e.g., as part of academic journals’ publication policies,
- possibility of genomic data being generated from material,
- definitions of recipient scientist that might not cover the possibility of multiple institutional affiliations,
- requirements for publications that might be in conflict with publication policies of academic journals, resulting in findings being published in journals with less stringent criteria and possibly with lower quality/reach,
- the timing considerations for review of the publications that result from use of the samples and ambiguities regarding the process in case of disagreement between the Biobank and the recipient scientist,
- ambiguities regarding the return or destruction of samples and shipping fees and potential insurance costs,
- minor and technical issues.

We have also mentioned documents that are potentially relevant for improving the MTA and drafting the DTA, which are listed under the BBMRI-ERIC ELSI Knowledge Base⁸ although raising the important point that some of these documents predate the GDPR. Similarly, we have highlighted the BBMRI-ERIC ELSI webinar on Material and Data Transfer Agreements⁹.

Following the commentary, the biobank.cy team modified the MTA to produce a single MTA/DTA document (see Appendix A8), which will be reviewed in 2021Q1.

⁸ RD-Connect MTA/DTA (Sep 2014):

<https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/wp-content/uploads/2016/07/ejhgCHARTER.pdf>

CORBEL/Life Science RI Innovation Helpdesk – Templates:

<https://lifescience-ri.eu/collaborative-activities/innovation-helpdesk/templates.html>

Sample Data and Material Transfer Agreement (Jan 2016):

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3928451>

Informed Consent Guide and Sample Template for Biobank and Registry-Based Research (Sept 2018):

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3928446>

Data Transfer Guide for African States/EU Member States (Sept 2018):

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3928410>

Sample Data Transfer Agreement – Outgoing for Data Transfer within the EU (Sept 2018):

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3928389>

Sample Material Transfer Agreement (Sept 2018):

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3928385>

⁹ BBMRI-ERIC ELSI Webinar “Material and Data Transfer Agreements” by Olga Tzortzatou:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Tu2mYZA8xfs&list=PLlu6KJ19npXyOx3Hjcb-wt5Y6yBTNBO1E>

2.3 Participation

2.3.1 Informed Consent

Although informed consent is often considered through the legal document, an Informed Consent Form (ICF), it is rather a process that involves not only specific moment of providing consent, but also the entire process of engagement before, during and after the act of consenting. Therefore, informed consent has to be considered on the one hand through the ICF, but also through analysis of how incidental findings are dealt with and genetic counseling is conducted, how withdrawal process is designed, special considerations for vulnerable groups / minors and lastly engagement approach of the Biobank. We group all these seemingly separate topics under participation and while the discussion starts with ICF as a document, it relates to processes that go beyond the moment of providing consent and involve actors other than the Biobank staff who are responsible for informed consent. For the ICFs approved by the CNBC please see the Appendix (A9-A10).

In order to provide the basis of this holistic approach, we have organized an internal online workshop with the title “Focusing on Informed Consent” with an experienced biobanker from the German Biobank Node as the guest speaker (26-27.05.2020). Based on scenarios involving samples and data from the Biobank, which were designed according to their documentation, we opened up discussion into the governance structure of the Biobank. Having an experienced biobanker as guest speaker allowed us to highlight best practices by linking the form and function of the Biobank, from IT systems to ELSI considerations. Finally, we touched upon the topic of risks and presented a typology/taxonomy of risks in biobanking that we used to brainstorm the best ways to communicate and mitigate risks. The workshop discussions were summarized and provided as a report to participants and other biobank.cy personnel.

We have also provided commentaries in writing and through online exchanges, shared the ICF template¹⁰ recommended by the Permanent Working Party of the German Medical Ethics Committees. Along the holistic approach, our analysis focused on suggestions for the improvement of the existing ICF, touching upon numerous topics: for instance, the use of the term “ownership” regarding which BBMRI-ERIC has previously suggested¹¹ for the WMA Declaration on Ethical Consideration Regarding Health Databases and Biobanks the following terms as alternatives “guardianship, custodianship or stewardship” as well as legal differences in certain national contexts (Capron et al., 2009; Hallmans & Vaught, 2011). However, besides the relevant sections below, our discussions mainly gravitated around the topic of risks, from assessment to communication and mitigation, which resulted in the preparation of a manuscript described in Section 3.2.

2.3.2 Incidental Findings

Incidental findings (IFs) and whether/how they are to be returned have been an important topic during the WP8 exchanges. The passive guidance included advertising of the BBMRI-ERIC webinar¹² on “Ethical Handling of Incidental Findings in Research” by Eline Bunnik from BBMRI.NL, the provided “Guide to the Detection, Management and Communication of Incidental Findings for Biobanks” available¹³ as open access document

¹⁰ Template for Informed Consent concerning the use of biological samples and related data in biobanks recommended by the Permanent Working Party of the German Medical Ethics Committees approved by the General Assembly on 21/06/2019:

<https://www.akek.de/docs/ICF%20Biobanks%20FINALapproval%202020-10-20%20Clean.pdf>

¹¹ BBMRI-ERIC Contribution to the Public Consultation on the WMA Declaration on Ethical Considerations Regarding Health Databases and Biobanks – Article 22 (06.12.2015):

https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/wp-content/uploads/2016/08/BBMRI-ERIC_Contribution-to-WMA-declaration-on-HDB-and-BB_CD-VF.pdf

¹² Recording of the BBMRI-ERIC ELSI Webinar „Ethical Handling of Incidental Findings in Research” 04.06.2020 by Eline Bunnik from:

<https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/news-events/webinar-elsi-incidentalfindings/>

¹³ “Guide to the Detection, Management and Communication of Incidental Findings for Biobanks” under BBMRI-ERIC ELSI Knowledge Base:

under BBMRI-ERIC ELSI Knowledge Base. As a comparison to the European perspective, we have highlighted the relevance of The Report by the US Presidential Commission on “Ethical Management of Incidental and Secondary Findings in the Clinical, Research and Direct-to-Consumer Contexts” and provided the open access document (Gutmann et al., 2013) as well as an example IFs policy summary.

During earlier direct engagements, WP8 team and invited speakers have noted how the majority of the incidental findings are from imaging, not genetics; however, for instance, in case of genetic findings, we have noted that there is no consensus at the European level. For instance, while the German Biobank Node follows the American College of Medical Genetics (ACMG) Guidelines (Kalia et al., 2017)¹⁴, in France, the approach described in the guidelines of European Society of Human Genetics (ESHG)¹⁵ is recommended (Matthijs et al., 2016). We have highlighted the importance of having a framework for incidental findings: e.g., criteria for incidental findings and their reporting, procedures regarding genetic counseling, sharing of information with the family doctor, validation of findings/clinical validity (e.g. IVD standards) and situations to avoid, such as providing the finding directly to the participant without support as well as gray areas/conflicts, e.g. participant’s *right not to know* vs. incidental finding regarding a life-threatening health condition.

During a specific internal workshop on 16.12.2020 that focused on incidental findings, we expanded on the passive guidance and previous engagements. The scope included definitions (primary, incidental, anticipatable and not anticipatable findings) and discussion of the variety of incidental findings (Gutmann et al., 2013). We raised the relevant ethical issues: respect for autonomy, nonmaleficence, beneficence and justice. Finally, we have touched upon IFs as part of a process from anticipation to follow-up¹⁶. Following the ethical aspects, the legal aspects from the European perspective were highlighted, followed by the ESHG and Eurogentest recommendations and positions. Here, we have also distinguished between approaches in health and research contexts. The IFs issue has been discussed as part of the informed consent process. Finally, specific issues regarding liabilities have been mentioned. Following the European perspective, the presentation summarized the 2015 Opinion of the National Bioethics Committee in Cyprus on the issue of IFs¹⁷.

During the workshop, an external speaker Neeme Tonisson from Estonian Biobank and University of Tartu was invited due to the Estonian Biobank being known for extensive research into IFs, their discovery, communication and management. Neeme Tonisson, with experience in both the ELSI and the genetic / medical aspects, presented his talk titled *Ethical and Social Aspects in Biobank Governance in Estonia*. Along the lines of the presentation, research on IFs from Estonian biobank that has been published provides detailed account of processes, from anticipation to the follow-up and the structure of the Biobank (Leitsalu et al., 2016; Leitsalu et al., 2015).

As the practical component of the workshop, we have designed two scenarios of potential IFs that allow for discussion of various ethical, legal and societal issues. Both of these scenarios were based on imaginary identification of pathogenic genetic variants for Charcot-Marie-Tooth (CMT) disease, a non-fatal, inherited, peripheral neuropathy with a gradual progression with typical features, such as weakness in foot and lower leg muscles, muscle atrophy in hands, progressive sensory loss (Nicolaou et al., 2010; Timmerman, Strickland, & Züchner, 2014). The disease is very heterogenous both in terms of the underlying genetic mechanisms, but also the onset, progression and the severity of the symptoms (Timmerman et al., 2014). The most common subtype is CMT1A and the most common mutation causing CMT is a microduplication on chromosome 17 (Kumps et al., 2020). Despite the relatively high number of genes known to be harboring causal mutations, CMT follows a Mendelian model with complete penetrance. There are many genes that cause CMT, but in

https://www.bbmri.nl/sites/bbmri/files/Erasmus_MC_Handreiking_Interactieve_pdf_Engels_29_04_2020_V3.pdf

¹⁴ See also ClinVar Database:

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/clinvar/docs/acmg/>

¹⁵ See also ESHG policy statements:

<https://www.eshg.org/index.php?id=477>

¹⁶ See footnote #13 for the description of the process.

¹⁷ Opinion available under the CNBC website in Greek: “Γνώμη αναφορικά με τα τυχαία ή μη αναμενόμενα ευρήματα που προκύπτουν από γενετικές αναλύσεις με τεχνολογίες αλληλούχισης επόμενης γενεάς (Next Generation Sequencing)”:

http://www.bioethics.gov.cy/moh/cnbc/cnbc.nsf/dmlopinions_arch_gr/dmlopinions_arch_gr?OpenDocument

each CMT patient, there is often one single gene that has the causal mutation. CMT has a global prevalence of 1 in 2500 and in Cyprus 1 in 6250 (Nicolaou et al., 2010).

We have chosen CMT for a number of reasons. First of all, it is not among the conditions that ACMG incidental findings guidelines (Green et al., 2013; Kalia et al., 2017) are suggesting, allowing further room for discussion. Second, CMT is an incurable disease; however, a CMT finding may be actionable in certain aspects. The Clinical Genome Actionability Knowledge Repository¹⁸ lists CMT^{19, 20} among the conditions, which are scored according to a rubric that highlights severity of the condition, likelihood, effectiveness and nature of the intervention²¹. These interventions (actionability) also include drugs and therapies that may have adverse effects on individuals with the genetic variation. For CMT patients, certain chemotherapeutic agents may have devastating consequences on the nerves, making the knowledge of the genetic finding potentially actionable. For instance, the guidelines²² state “over 30 medications have been identified as toxic or potentially toxic to persons with CMT”, naming certain anesthesia and chemotherapeutic drugs. On the one hand, providing the incidental finding to the participant could be devastating as this is an incurable progressive disease, but the information may also save the participant from further and faster deterioration if applicable. Finally, there is at least one research article that reports an incidental finding of CMT for the mother during non-invasive prenatal testing (Kumps et al., 2020) suggesting that increasing applications of personalized medicine will result in identification of many further cases, especially of CMT1A, due to the microduplication.

Case Report (Minor participant)

Recruited for research project that includes **whole genome sequencing** (+ possibly aCGH)

Incidental finding (**genomic**): **Copy Number Variation** (CNV: Duplication of a 1.4 Mb region--17p12)

Known consequence: **CMT1A (demyelinating peripheral neuropathy)**

Possibly **sporadic**, no known case in the family

Participant has **no symptoms**

Expected progression:

- usually early onset,
- progressive sensory loss,
- weakness in foot and lower leg muscles,
- muscle atrophy in hands,
- not fatal.

Case Report (Adult participant)

Recruited for Cyprus Genome Project as part of a trio; **whole genome sequencing** conducted

Incidental finding (**genomic**): **Point Mutation** (*PMP22* C65→T, Ser22Phe, Autosomal Dominant)

Known consequence: **CMT1A (demyelinating peripheral neuropathy)**, possibly **HNPP**

Sporadic, mutation not identified in the rest of the trio

Participant has **no symptoms**

Expected progression:

- variable onset and severity,
- progressive distal muscle weakness and atrophy,
- pes cavus deformity of the feet,
- mild muscle atrophy in hands,
- not fatal.

See: Kleopa et al 2004

CMT: Actionability

Predictive Testing: "For asymptomatic minors at risk for adult-onset conditions for which early treatment would have no beneficial effect on disease morbidity and mortality, predictive genetic testing is considered inappropriate, primarily because it negates the autonomy of the child with no compelling benefit." (*Gene Reviews*)

Oncology: "Over 30 medications have been identified as toxic or potentially toxic to persons with CMT[...] Vincristine and paclitaxel (chemotherapeutic agents) pose a definite high risk of nerve damage and should be avoided by all patients with CMT, including those who are asymptomatic." (*Actionability Knowledge Repository*)

Anesthesia: "Avoiding succinylcholine is recommended." (*ORPHANET*)

Further Resources

- Actionability Knowledge Repository Report on CMT
- OMIM entry for CMT1A
- ORPHANET entry for CMT
- ICD: Gene Reviews report for CMT
- List of Neurotoxic Medications by CMT Association

Figure 2. Incidental Findings: Scenarios

(from the Templates of Incidental Findings Scenarios-Minor/Adult Participants prepared within WP8, see Appendix A12-13)

Following the workshop and the drafting of the IFs policy (see Appendix A11) by biobank.cy colleagues, WP8 has provided an internal report and commentary highlighting ELSI issues that could be relevant in the improvement of the IFs policy. The templates for IFs scenarios (see Figure 2 for extracts) that we have

¹⁸ Clinical Genome Actionability:

<https://actionability.clinicalgenome.org/ac/>

¹⁹ Charcot - Marie - Tooth Disease, Type 1:

<https://actionability.clinicalgenome.org/ac/Adult/ui/stg2SummaryRpt?doc=AC129;>

²⁰ DNM2-Related Intermediate Charcot-Marie-Tooth Neuropathy:

<https://actionability.clinicalgenome.org/ac/Adult/ui/stg2SummaryRpt?doc=AC148>

²¹ Presentation „Systematic assessment of clinical actionability associated with genomic variation” by Elizabeth Webber:

https://www.clinicalgenome.org/site/assets/files/2268/webber_actionability_overview.pdf

²² See footnote #19: Charcot - Marie - Tooth Disease, Type 1.

produced are available in the Appendix (A12-13), which also highlight further resources such as OMIM²³, ORPHANET²⁴, Gene Reviews²⁵ and a relevant patient organization²⁶ that may also be useful for genetic counselling, discussed in the next section.

2.3.3 Genetic Counseling

Engagements with participants may include genetic counseling as part of return of IFs, but also during the informed consent process, where genetic counselor may need to simplify complex matters regarding genetics and risks and benefits of participation from a genetics perspective. In this regard, biobank.cy developed a role description for the genetic counsellor position, summarizing main tasks, duties and responsibilities as well as qualifications and soft-skills necessary for this role (see Appendix A14).

Andrea Christofides, PhD in molecular biology from MMRC under the guidance of Prof. C. Deltas, has been undergoing training in genetic counselling while also receiving formal training by attending a master's program in genomic and genetic counseling with the University of Cardiff.

2.3.4 Withdrawal Procedure and Destruction of Data/Samples

There are varying approaches in the biobanking community regarding withdrawal of consent. In early exchanges, we have considered the topic through two contexts: **ongoing research** that uses the samples/data and the already **ended research** that have used the samples/data. In both cases the participant informing process should be triggered and individuals are often provided with choices (as stated in the informed consent form). Participant should be informed about the limitations of use. In case the removal of data/samples directly affects ongoing research, this entails an assessment that should focus on the specificity of the situation unless it is noted in the informed consent form.

As we have pointed out, different types of Biobanks have different policies regarding withdrawal. For instance, UK Biobank²⁷ suggests withdrawal at three levels: no further contact, no further access, no further use. In exchanges, we have also suggested that in the ICF, there should be a third option of “no further contact” besides deletion/destruction and keeping/anonymization. Moreover, we think it should be noted that “anonymization” or “no further contact” will make it impossible to contact the individuals upon incidental findings. For more information, we point out the following suggestion BBMRI-ERIC has made in the past²⁸:

“Individuals must have the right to apply to the chief processor, at any time and without harmful consequences, to withdraw their consent for or opt out of their identifiable information to remain included in a Health Database and their biological material to remain in a Biobank. Withdrawal of consent should automatically entail deletion of all identifiable data and destruction of biosamples. Where destruction is impossible and justified by legitimate interests of the responsible persons, the full and irreversible anonymisation of the biological resources must be implemented by the destruction of data and keys enabling decoding/reidentification of samples and data in order to maintain them for scientific purposes in the same Database/Biobank. Any results already obtained from such biological

²³ Online Mendelian Inheritance in Man (OMIM):

<https://www.omim.org/>

²⁴ ORPHANET:

<https://www.orpha.net/>

²⁵ Gene Reviews:

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK1116/>

²⁶ Charcot-Marie-Tooth Association (CMTA):

<https://www.cmtausa.org/>

²⁷ UK Biobank withdrawal policy:

<https://www.ukbiobank.ac.uk/withdrawal/>

²⁸ BBMRI-ERIC Contribution to the Public Consultation on the WMA Declaration on Ethical Considerations Regarding Health Databases and Biobanks – Article 17 (06.12.2015):

https://www.bbmri-eric.eu/wp-content/uploads/2016/08/BBMRI-ERIC_Contribution-to-WMA-declaration-on-HDB-and-BB_CD-VF.pdf

D8.1 Successful implementation of CS ELSI and procedures for data protection, record and sample retrieval, and for record and sample withdrawal from the Biobank

resources can remain in the system and can be the basis for publications. Provided that they comply with law and regulation, any limitation to the right to withdraw must be outlined in the consent process.”

According to the intended withdrawal policy of the biobank.cy, in case, the participant decides to withdraw, participant is informed about the process and is allowed to choose among three gradual options:

- Withdrawal - no further communication;
- Withdrawal - no further access to medical history, but continuing use of samples and data already collected;
- Withdrawal - no further re-use (destruction or irreversible anonymization of the file including abolishing the link with the data).

Following the informing process as described in the Withdrawal Form (see Appendix A15), the participant will be asked to sign the form by the deciding on one of the options without having to justify his/her decision. It should be noted that the withdrawal policy has been prepared after the approval of the ICF by the CNBC and the current ICF states the participants can withdraw their consent any time and that their decision will not affect their treatment in any way and as withdrawal procedure, the following is noted in the current ICF: “In order not to interfere with the credibility of the research results that may be ongoing, and to minimize the loss of scientific benefit, if you decide to withdraw, you will be asked by the project manager if you agree for the Biobank to keep all of your data and biological samples that have been collected up to that point, in full anonymity and disconnected from your identifiable folder. If you do not agree, the Biobank will delete your personal data and results and destroy the biological samples.” As the biobank documentation is still being further developed and improved, the harmonization across documentation is expected to include the suggested updates.

Withdrawal of consent by a participant falls under the operative procedures of the Biobank. However, if a decision is ever taken for the destruction of an entire collection of data/samples or the dissolution of the entire Biobank, the intervention of the CNBC and the Data Protection Commissioner shall be sought, to supervise the destruction process.

2.3.5 Vulnerability and Minors' Participation

The participation of volunteers who sign the broad consent form for general use of data and samples of the Biobank in future research studies, is restricted to adults. Per the decision of the CNBC, no minors are entitled to participate through the signing by their parents or legal guardians. However, minors can participate in other separate research projects which have specific project objectives and defined duration.

Vulnerable populations and the participation of minors have been another topic on which guidance has been provided in the form of a presentation by BBMRI-ERIC ELSI Services & Research member Sara Casati, PhD, titled *Vulnerable Populations in Biobanking: The Minors' Engagement as the Training Ground* on 16.12.2020 and a drafted guidance document with the same title to be shared with biobank.cy and made publicly available in the BBMRI-ERIC Knowledge Base (2021Q1). The aim has been to sensitize the biobank.cy staff into the topic of vulnerable populations and minors' participation in research. The presentation and the guidance document focus on vulnerability as a concept, safeguards, temporary vulnerability in case of minors as well as concepts that relate to the other sections of this document, such as incidental findings and informational risk, while highlighting international cornerstones, such as the Belmont Report²⁹, the Barcelona Declaration³⁰, the Helsinki Declaration³¹ among others.

²⁹ The Belmont Report by The National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research (1979):

https://www.hhs.gov/ohrp/sites/default/files/the-belmont-report-508c_FINAL.pdf

³⁰ The Barcelona Declaration (1998):

<https://www.istitutobioetica.it/documenti-di-riferimento/documenti-di-riferimento/187-documenti/556-the-barcelona-declaration-on-policy-proposals-to-the-european-commission-on-basic-ethical-principles-in-bioethics-and-biolaw>

³¹ Helsinki Declaration by WMA (2013):

<https://www.wma.net/wp-content/uploads/2016/11/DoH-Oct2013-JAMA.pdf>

Sara Casati is also involved in discussions of changes in the Minimum Information About Biobank data Sharing (MIABIS)³² standard (Eklund et al., 2020; Merino-Martinez et al., 2016) regarding the samples and data from pediatric biobanks (e.g. how they are categorized and searched for) as part of her role at BBMRI-ERIC and biobank.cy will be asked whether a representative would be interested in taking part in the planned discussions.

2.4 Engagement

Engagement Policy of biobank.cy is under review from the ELSI perspective and a commentary will be provided to biobank.cy within 2021Q1.

3 Sustainability of the ELSI Perspective beyond the Work Package

The approach used for WP8 contributed to the implementation of the recommended ELSI procedures and regulations and setting up of procedures and preparation of relevant documents as described above. Along with the above summarized accomplishments, WP8 also pursued transparency and openness to the scientific community and the lay public by producing a manuscript on the topic of risks to be published in a relevant open-access journal and an accompanying workshop. These will also form the basis of sustaining the ELSI perspective beyond the work package along with the involvement of biobank.cy in the Documentation Base, as will be described in the next section.

3.1 Involvement in the Documentation Base

BBMRI-ERIC contributes to the collection of best practice examples, for instance through previous project involvements or supporting translation of available resources, such as recently the *Informed Consent Form*³³ of the Association of the Medical Ethics Committees in Germany. However, in certain cases, we faced difficulty acquiring and sharing with biobank.cy best practice examples, for example of incidental findings policies. BBMRI-ERIC ELSI Services & Research is currently working on building a system that will allow biobanks to share their documentation to stimulate and enable both knowledge transfer from advanced partners and peer-to-peer knowledge exchange. In order to provide early access to biobank.cy to such Biobank documentation from other biobanks, biobank.cy has been invited to contribute to the design of the system representing the ideal “intended user”. Once the system is running, the system will be useful for all biobanks to share and learn from the documentation of others. Ultimately, this will increase transparency of the governance structure of particular biobanks and contribute to harmonized governance practices and ethical standards across European biobanks.

The Documentation Base conceptualization includes, to date, Monica Cano Abadia, Kaya Akyüz, Petr Holub and Michaela Th. Mayrhofer (all BBMRI-ERIC) as well as biobankers; namely Christian Gully (Biobank Graz, Austria), Sirpa Soini (Aurii Biobank, Finland) and Stella Antoniou (Biobank of biobank.cy CoE, Cyprus).

3.2 Typology of Risks and Genomic Identifiability

The manuscript prepared is a typology of risks involved in biobanking (Akyüz et al., 2021). In this paper, risks that have been identified through the analysis of the literature as well as relevant ethical and legal documents, such as guidelines, have been brought together. The identified risks have been grouped in categories as seen in Figure 3 and through the categorization, it has been shown how certain risks are entangled and multiple.

The typology of risks is important for the CY-Biobank project because of three main reasons. First, identification of risks is the initial step in a well-functioning risk governance model. In this regard, the typology may serve as

³² MIABIS: Minimum Information About Biobank data Sharing
<https://github.com/BBMRI-ERIC/miabis>

³³ See footnote #10.

a starting point that can lead to an expansion of the repertoire of potential risks in the local context of biobank.cy. Once a risk is identified, the communication and mitigation steps may be undertaken. If risks are not acknowledged early on, their materialization may have significant consequences for the Biobank, the employees, the participants, the society and/or the research community.

Second, the typology allows to show how useful it is to incorporate different actors' and their perspectives into the risk governance. Although WP8 stands for ELSI, the risks identified span a wide range, from loss of public trust (societal) to violation of participants' values (ethical), compensation following litigation (legal), hacking (IT), impacting healthy organs (medical), stigmatization (social/psychological), accidents (health of the employees), contamination/infection (public health), scientific misconduct (research community), failure of backup systems (technical), closure of the hosting institution (institutional) or loss of funding (financial). In this regard, different actors (e.g., quality manager, nurse, genetic counselor, IT staff, participants, patient organizations, industry representatives) may contribute to identification of novel risks that not only affect their area of expertise, but other actors and areas as well.

Third, a typology allows to categorically think about risks, where the same action may have very different consequences or risk potential in different contexts, acknowledging that these categories may continuously expand. This means that a single typology cannot encompass the whole repertoire of risks as they may differ according to sociotechnical context. It also means, the identification of risks is a continuous process that should go beyond the early phase of a project and become part of a routine exercise.

The manuscript is prepared by Kaya Akyüz (BBMRI-ERIC), Melanie Goisau (BBMRI-ERIC), Gauthier Chassang (INSERM), Łukasz Kozera (BBMRI-ERIC), Signe Mezinska (BBMRI.lv), Olga Tzortzatou (subcontracted expert) and Michaela Th. Mayrhofer (BBMRI-ERIC), co-funded by CY-Biobank project and BBMRI-ERIC.

Figure 3. Typology of risks

(from manuscript in preparation: Akyüz et al., 2021)

While the manuscript aims to identify a broad repertoire of risks through a typology, we have also focused on a specific risk, genomic identifiability, and a public workshop was organized on 25.11.2020 by BBMRI-ERIC (Looking back, going forward – Rethinking genomic data at #HeLa100). The recording is available online³⁴. In this workshop, the risk of genomic identifiability has been discussed through a very special case for both life sciences research and the ELSI literature: Henrietta Lacks and the publishing of the genome sequence of the HeLa cell line (Landry et al., 2013). Following the publication of the mentioned article, a controversy erupted as the openly accessible genomic data carried potential risks for Henrietta Lacks' descendants due to identifiability (Callaway, 2013b), only to be resolved with a unique solution tailored for this specific case by the National Institutes of Health (NIH), Lacks family and the researchers (Callaway, 2013a, 2013c).

The HeLa genome sequencing controversy shows how the current understanding of risks according to standards and guidelines are often not up to date in light of the societal, scientific and technological developments and the expansion of data infrastructures. This highlights the necessity to incorporate a proactive risk governance that would allow for identification of risks that are novel and that may emerge in the near future.

³⁴ Workshop “Looking back, going forward – Rethinking genomic data at #HeLa100”: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5QWNTfsqca0>

3.3 Sustainable Risk Governance: Mapping Risks

With this deliverable, we approach the stage where the majority of the components of the Biobank infrastructure, from procedures to documentation, are at least established while some are being improved as a result of ELSI guidance. Following the submission of the above discussed manuscript to the relevant academic journal to be published open-access, we plan to realize our next major activity, a workshop that was originally planned as an interdisciplinary activity across science, ELSI, IT and QM.

The first and the original goal of this workshop is to collect a diverse body of experiences from participating experts and create a living document of varied practices in organizing consenting in different countries and institutional contexts. The aim is not to put together a novel universal consent form and a consenting pipeline as a simple solution to a complex issue, nor choose a model out of the existing options. It is rather to go beyond focusing on the moment of consent and lay out step by step what considerations should be included in each separate case, informing newly founded biobanks as well as established ones of pitfalls and opportunities, while thinking outside the box for generating innovative ideas for an inclusive and feasible consenting process and the related consent management, by asking *how dynamic* and *how broad* consent can be.

The second goal is to contribute to sustainable risk governance at biobank.cy. For this purpose, based on the manuscript planned to be submitted within 2021Q1, we will propose a mapping method for identification, communication and mitigation of risks. During the workshop participants from different backgrounds will come together in small group settings to identify further elements to be included in an already created risk typology, allowing for testing of a pro-active risk governance model for biobank.cy. Design and planning of the workshop have been ongoing and the workshop is planned to take place in March/April 2021.

The risk mapping benefited from the insights of the following experts: Kaya Akyüz, Melanie Goisaufl and Michaela Th. Mayrhofer (all BBMRI-ERIC).

3.3.1 Adapting Situational Analysis for Mapping Risks

The workshop will focus on the topic of risks from a practical perspective: risk mapping. In this practical component, we will be relying on qualitative social sciences methodology that may be considered broadly under grounded theory (Charmaz, 2006), more specifically situational analysis (Clarke, 2005; Clarke, Friese, & Washburn, 2015, 2018). Although situational analysis is used for qualitative research in social sciences, it is highly adaptable to different contexts, especially in identifying implicit or unobvious relations between elements within a situation through mapping exercises. The methodology relies on constructing three different types of maps – situational, social worlds/arenas and positional maps – as well as exercises such as relational mapping and writing memos (Clarke et al., 2015).

In the risk mapping exercise, we will focus on situational map as the type and relational mapping as the exercise. The situational maps are used to “lay out all the major human, nonhuman, discursive, historical, symbolic, cultural, political, and other elements in the research situation of concern” (Clarke et al., 2015, p. 13). First, all relevant elements (e.g. participants, blood samples, genome data, ICF, genetic counsellor, hackers, liquid nitrogen, external researchers, -80°C freezers, University, DPO, patient representatives, journalists, institutional website and others) are randomly mapped out through a collaborative activity by CY-Biobank project members. This forms the situational map. Second, each participant takes one element in the situational map and draws random lines to each other element, reflecting on what kind of risks may be possible in this relationship. For instance, a line from *hackers* to *-80°C freezers* may allow identification of the risk of a potential hacking of the freezing system’s control. Although not identified in a Biobank, such a possibility emerged recently as attempts by hackers were uncovered, where COVID-19 vaccine cold-chain was targeted (Zaboeva & Frydrych, 2020). Third, the participant writes short memos on any risks identified through the relational mapping, explaining in short what the risk entails. Lastly, participants discuss risks identified, collecting a repertoire of risks that directly relate to situation of biobank.cy and the communication/mitigation possibilities.

The end product of risk mapping should resemble an expanded and more specialized version of the typology that we have produced in Figure 3. The risk mapping can only be part of the risk governance framework since

identification of potential risks necessitates further effort into mitigation and communication. Furthermore, the risk mapping exercise would only function if this activity is repeated periodically. In the final workshop on risk mapping, WP8 will introduce both the activity itself and put it into practice initiating such a model.

This work especially benefited from the following experts Kaya Akyüz and Michaela Th. Mayrhofer.

4 Conclusions

The implementation is largely on track. We recommend continuation of improvement of the documents and procedures. This necessitates continuation of the exchanges within WP8 and across work packages until the end of the project as requested by amendment. The upcoming publication as described above and the planned workshop including the risk mapping practice will be the main focus in upcoming months along with completion of the remaining commentaries.

5 References

Please refer to footnotes for online resources. All online resources have been last accessed on 08.02.2021.

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6 Appendix

Table 1. List of attached documents

Document Number	Description	Note
A1	By-laws	
A2	Impartiality Agreement / Disclosure of Conflicts of Interest	available only in Greek
A3	Approval by CNBC	available only in Greek
A4	DPO confirmation	
A5	DPIA synthesis	available only in Greek
A6	Confidentiality Agreement	available only in Greek
A7	Security Policy	available only in Greek
A8	The updated MTA/DTA template	
A9	Informed Consent Form – Adults	
A10	Informed Consent Form – Minors	
A11	Incidental Findings Policy	
A12	Template: Incidental Findings Scenario – Minor	
A13	Template: Incidental Findings Scenario – Adult	
A14	Genetic Counselor – Role Description	
A15	Withdrawal Form	available only in Greek

The biobank.cy Center of Excellence in Biobanking and Biomedical Research

Table of Contents

INTRODUCTION	3
DIRECTOR'S MESSAGE	3
VISION	4
MISSION	4
BIOBANKING.....	4
QUALITY POLICY.....	5
ACCESS TO MATERIA AND/OR DATA	5
ORGANISATION STRUCTURE.....	6
GOVERNANCE	7
ACADEMIC COUNCIL - DIRECTOR GENERAL.....	7
CENTER OF EXCELLENCE COUNCIL.....	7
INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC ADVISORY COMMITTEE (ISAC).....	8
INTERNAL ETHICS ADVISORY BOARD (IEAB).....	8
EXTERNAL ETHICS ADVISORY BOARD (EEAB)	9
STAKEHOLDERS' FORUM	10
PROJECT MANAGEMENT COMMITTEE (PMC)	10
LEGAL FRAMEWORK.....	11
LOCAL AND INTERNATIONAL QUIDELINES	11
ANNEX 1: ACCESS POLICY	12
ANNEX 2: GOVERNANCE MEMBERS	15
ACADEMIC COUNCIL	15
CENTER OF EXCELLENCE COUNCIL.....	15
INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC ADVISORY COMMITTEE (ISAC).....	15
INTERNAL ETHICS ADVISORY BOARD (IEAB).....	15
EXTERNAL ETHICS ADVISORY BOARD (EEAB)	15
STAKEHOLDERS' FORUM.....	15
ANNEX 3: WITHDRAWAL FORM.....	16

INTRODUCTION

Director's message

Dear Reader,

Established in 2011, the Molecular Medicine Research Center (MMRC) was the first research center of the University of Cyprus (UCY) that aspired and aimed at developing front-line research on human genetic diseases and offer better prospects for diagnosis, prevention and therapy, in the framework of precision medicine. MMRC was one of nine Strategic Projects established in Cyprus thanks to successful external competitive funding from the European Regional Development Fund and the Republic of Cyprus through the Research Promotion Foundation. The project was entitled: *Creation of a Kidney Specific Biobank and Infrastructure for Genomics Research [NEW INFRASTRUCTURE/ STRATEGIC/0308/24]*.

A more recent development (April 2019) is the approval through the European Commission H2020-WIDESPREAD-01-2018-2019: Teaming Phase 2 program, for funding a scientific proposal of the University of Cyprus, entitled: *Biobanking and the Cyprus Human Genome Project (CY-Biobank)*

The aim of the European Commission is the funding of groups in countries that are weak performers in research and innovation, to upgrade existing or create new *Centers of Excellence in Research and Innovation*. This new establishment, known as *Center of Excellence in Biobanking and Biomedical Research* (for short CY-Biobank or biobank.cy), was officially launched on October 1, 2019.

The central aim of the project is the upgrading of the MMRC into a larger and more complete medical research infrastructure, in the heart of which is the enhancement and enrichment of the Cyprus Biobank. This CoE, one of six being established in Cyprus, aspires to create the necessary tools and leverage the opportunities for next generation medical research in Cyprus, in order to be better prepared to meet the new challenges in translational research and precision medicine.

With the use of the Biobank infrastructure, the CY-Biobank project aims to start and complete the study of the Cypriot human genome which is going to serve as a referral instrument for many other projects concerning the rare monogenic disorders or the more frequent complex conditions of multifactorial aetiology. A common final objective is better treatments and better drugs for all patients, showing utmost respect to high scientific and ethical standards in the conduct of research.

The CY-Biobank project will enable the concentration of a critical mass of experts at the CoE who will be thrilled to establishing collaborations and offering technology infrastructure and know-how to young investigators and medical doctors who are interested in pursuing innovative research projects. The biobank.cy CoE aspires to serve as an incubator of creative ideas for research based on valid and sound scientific hypotheses. At the CoE you will find postdoctoral fellows and graduate students working side by side with UCY faculty, medical doctors and other experienced researchers, pursuing projects of translational medicine, always aimed at serving the patient.

We will be happy to talk to and invite to our premises any individual or parties interested in meeting with us and discussing on issues of common research interests. We are particularly keen to establish productive collaborations with representatives of the medical and pharmaceutical community of Cyprus.

We invest in the Biobank, we invest in a healthier Cyprus!

Prof. Constantinos Deltas

Project Coordinator

Director, CY-Biobank, Center of Excellence in Biobanking and Biomedical Research

Vision

We aspire to further expand a contemporary Biobank at an island-wide level and establish a research environment aimed at precision medicine, motivated by our genuine care for human well-being. Key components are continuous education, research and innovation, aimed to serve the patients. The ultimate sacred purpose of the biobank.cy Center of Excellence is to make the link between the dramatic picture of the affected individual-the patient as a human macro-entity-and the patient as a molecular biological micro-entity. The next feat is the prevention or correction of the molecular malady through translational research and precision medicine.

Mission

We, the people at the biobank.cy, Center of Excellence (CoE), aspire to create an upgraded research environment with the necessary tools to develop innovative front-line research in the field of genetic diseases and molecular medicine. With the combination of research instruments that include molecular genetics and biostatistics, bioinformatics, molecular and cell biology, we aim to make biobank.cy a major gate to new knowledge for improving human health. At the CoE we care about contributing to better diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment of diseases, through promoting research, innovation and education, in a patient-centric approach.

At biobank.cy CoE we embrace our National dimension.

We invest in the Biobank, we invest in a healthier Cyprus!

Biobanking

The Biobank stores liquid biosamples (e.g. plasma, serum, urine, and blood), gDNA, tissue samples, and associated data while maintaining highest quality standards and safety conditions.

All data and biological materials archived at the Biobank are donated on a strictly voluntary basis by healthy volunteers, patients, and study participants following informed consenting. To protect a donor's privacy all identifying information is replaced by unique number-/letter codes (»doubly pseudonymized«). Donated biological material is labelled, registered, portioned in small tubes (aliquots), and stored in low temperature repositories.

Quality Policy

The biobank.cy Centre of Excellence established the following Quality Policy and is committed to:

- Comply with ISO9001:2015 and continually improve the effectiveness of the Quality Management System
- Comply with all regulatory requirements and ethical guidelines in full transparency
- Ensure that the activities of the biobank.cy are structured and impartial
- Apply the principles of best practices for its biobank as well as research and diagnostic activities
- Ensure all staff know about the Quality Management System and apply processes in line with standard methods

Access to Material and/or Data

National and international scientists and research groups as well as collaborating industry partners may request data and biological materials hosted by the CoE for biomedical research projects. All applications require prior approval by an ethics committee or a relevant Institutional Review Board. The Biobank Access Committee is responsible for the receipt and processing of all biomaterial and/or data requests. Details can be found in the CoE's Access Policy in [Annex 1](#).

ORGANISATION STRUCTURE

The biobank.cy Center of Excellence operates under the umbrella of the University of Cyprus with the status of a separate School, reporting directing to the Senate. It is managed by the Academic council, which is chaired by the Director General, and are advised by a Center of Excellence Council, Internal and External Ethics Advisory Boards, and an International Scientific Advisory Committee. Furthermore, a Stakeholder's Forum has been formed with members from the public, industry, research community, patients' organisations, and other interested parties, for raising awareness of the biobank.cy, communicating with the members to define their needs, and ensuring that the desired impact of its activities is achieved.

The Centre of Excellence consists of five pillars as listed and seen in the organogram below:

- 1) Molecular Medicine Research Centre, the research arm of the CoE
- 2) Biobank, a medical research infrastructure, of national character
- 3) Molecular Diagnostic Laboratory, to offer high quality diagnostic services
- 4) Education Hub, to promote knowledge in the fields of biobanking and biomedicine
- 5) Innovation Hub, to venture into new discoveries for a wider common good

The CY-Biobank Center of Excellence Organization

Each of the five CoE pillars have (or will have) a head with scientific and managerial duties and they are supported by the CoE's core processes that are managed by the administration. The pillars' heads and the administration report to the Director General and the Academic council. The CoE receives also support from the UCY Administration Services as shown above.

GOVERNANCE

Academic Council - Director General

Ultimate responsibility for delivering the resource, ensuring careful budgetary and corporate governance, falls to the Academic Council. The Academic Council manages the Center of Excellence (CoE) as specified by the Regulations of the University of Cyprus (General regulations for Centers of Excellence and Research Units, 1999 to XXXX¹) and is responsible for decisions on all matters related to administration, personnel hiring, purchases, research activities, biobanking etc. In this respect, the CoE will have in house administration services but will also be using services provided by the University of Cyprus.

The Chairman of the Academic Council is the Director of the CoE who is responsible for the day-to-day activities of the center. The CoE Director is elected and appointed by the Senate for a period of five years (with possibility of renewal) according to the rules drawn up by the Senate and approved by the UCY Council.

The Academic Council has 3-15 members who can be UCY academic faculty members or group leaders at the CoE that supervise ongoing research programs. Members must be approved by their respective Departments or School and are appointed by the Senate, following a suggestion by the Academic Council or the CoE Director. Subject to Senate's approval, the members can be part of the Academic Council for as long as they are members of the CoE.

Decisions are taken by simple majority and in case of a tie, the Chairman will have a casting vote.

The Academic Council meets every four months (or more frequently if it is necessary) and an agenda is prepared by the CoE Director prior to the meeting. Meeting minutes shall be kept by a secretary provided by the CoE. The meeting minutes shall be finalized within 10 working days following each meeting.

The Academic Council submits CoE's annual budget to the Senate together with suggestions regarding employment of new research staff, special scientists, and other personnel. In addition, the CoE prepares and submits to the Senate an annual report describing past year's activities including details of income and expenses. For the duration of the CY-Biobank Project, similar reports must be submitted to the UCY Research and Budget Offices as well as to the Cyprus Directorate General for European Programmes, Coordination and Development.

The activities of the CoE are evaluated 6 months prior to the 5-year term of the Director, based on criteria stipulated by the Senate and a decision is made regarding continuing of operations.

Members of the UCY that work at the CoE research programs can be invited at the Academic Council meetings as observers.

See [Annex 2](#) for membership.

Center of Excellence Council

The CoE council has an advisory role and supports the CoE within the University of Cyprus and outside of it. It reviews the long-term policy, strategic priorities, and the annual report of the center. It is required to be formed according to the Regulations of the University of Cyprus (General regulations for Centers of Excellence and Research Units, 1999 to XXXX¹).

The CoE Council has 5-9 members that are coming from both the academic community and outside of it. CoE Council members cannot be members of the Academic Council. Members are appointed by

¹ The UCY has submitted the relevant application for the biobank.cy CoE and a Parliament approval is pending

the Senate following a suggestion by the Director or the Academic Council. Membership to the CoE Council is for 4 years with the possibility of renewal for another 4 years. The president of the CoE council is selected by the CoE council members following a vote. The Director General of the CoE participates as an observer without a voting right.

The composition of this Board, which is approved by the Senate, could be as follows:

- Representative of the Rector's Council, University of Cyprus
- President of the Cyprus Medical Association or his/her representative
- Director of Medical Services and Services for Public Health, Ministry of Health, or his/her representative
- President or representative of Cyprus Federation of Patients' Organizations
- Other Personalities of the Cyprus general society

The CoE Council meets once every four months (or more frequently if it is necessary). A report for the activities and progress of the CoE will be prepared and submitted to CoE Council prior to the meeting by the CoE Director. Meeting minutes shall be kept and finalized within 10 working days following each meeting.

See [Annex 2](#) for membership.

International Scientific Advisory Committee (ISAC)

The International Scientific Advisory Committee (ISAC) will be established by the Center of Excellence to provide advice to the CoE Director, and the Academic Council on the strategic decisions, international trends and Biobanking directions, new markets, and assist in general on networking with important partners around the globe.

ISAC will meet annually with the Academic Council (and the Project Management Committee (PMC) for the duration of the CY-Biobank project) to review progress and achievements against the agreed objectives and also future plans. It will evaluate the outputs of the resource and their contribution to the scientific community both nationally and internationally. Its remit will also include advising and commenting on issues related to using the Biobank for collaborative research (such as access to participant data or samples). Meeting minutes shall be kept and finalized within 10 working days following each meeting.

Committee will have 5 renowned members, from fields such as: molecular medicine; population genetics; nephrology; Biobanking; bioethics or else.

See [Annex 2](#) for membership (under formation).

Internal Ethics Advisory Board (IEAB)

The Internal Ethics Advisory Board offers advice on internal or external material/data requests submitted to the Biobank. The IEAB activity will not substitute the role of the Cyprus National Bioethics Committee, or any other appropriate ethics body/Institutional Review Board, the approval of which is a prerequisite for any request of data/material submitted to the Biobank.

The Board ensures that the research and aims of projects requesting to use Biobank data and/or material conform to internationally and locally accepted ethical guidelines, taking into consideration the avoidance of duplication of ongoing research projects. This is deemed necessary as all archived data and material are collected and stored with substantial human effort and cost, and therefore their use should be maximised without jeopardizing the success of other ongoing projects.

IEAB may also assist in setting policies and may offer opinions on ongoing ethical issues in research, including the implementation of a policy regarding the fee-for-service and informed consent.

The Board will have maximum 5 members. The composition of this Board, is proposed to be as follows:

- Individual(s) with scientific and medical expertise, ideally with experience serving previously in Ethics Committees
- Non-scientific member(s), related to social, legal or cultural considerations
- Patient Representative(s)

Members of the committee are appointed by the CoE Director/Academic council for a period of two years with the possibility of renewal for another term.

IEAB meets once every four months or in between if urgently needed to review any requests falling within its mandate. CoE will be sharing material/data requests submitted to the Biobank and any other relevant material in advance of IEAB meeting for their review.

IEAB will be advising the CoE in writing within 10 working days whether any concerns have been identified with the submitted requests. In case of any concerns, the IEAB will be providing justifications and have the option to request additional information or amendments.

The CoE will facilitate the IEAB work and meetings by providing any secretarial and logistics assistance whenever needed.

See [Annex 2](#) for membership.

External Ethics Advisory Board (EEAB)

The External Ethics Advisory Board exercises an independent external advisory role on the activities of the Biobank in order to protect both the Biobank participants and CoE researchers. It considers potential risks and benefits for the community in which the Biobank research will be carried out and its ultimate goal is to support the Academic Council for promoting high ethical standards in CoE health research.

The board will have 4 members. Members will be independent and not involved in any CoE projects. The composition of this Board, is as follows:

- Individual(s) with scientific and medical expertise, ideally with experience serving previously in Ethics Committees
- Non-scientific member(s), related to social, legal or cultural considerations
- Patient Representative(s)

Members of the committee are appointed by the CoE Director/Academic council for a period of two years with the possibility of renewal for another term. EEAB meets once a year unless needed otherwise to monitor the Biobank ELSI issues and how they are handled.

In advance of EEAB meeting, the CoE will provide them with data/material access requests submitted during the year, along with the Internal Ethics Advisory Board evaluations and reports, for their review. EEAB will be advising the CoE in writing within 10 working days on the ethics procedures followed and provide advice or other input, as deemed necessary. Recommendations for amendments may also be reported.

For the duration of the CY-Biobank project, the report prepared by the advisory board following each of their meetings will also be submitted to the European Union as specified in WP11-D11.2 and D11.3 in line with the project reporting periods.

The CoE will facilitate the EEAB work and meetings by providing secretarial and logistics assistance as needed.

See [Annex 2](#) for membership.

Stakeholders' Forum

Stakeholders' Forum has been created by the Academic Council and consists of representatives of the CY-Biobank, collaborators, patients' organizations, medical societies, and pharma industries. Stakeholders' Forum is disseminating the CoE activities and shares opinions and ideas on new initiatives. In addition, it can assist on identifying future actions and projects to satisfy unmet needs.

For each group of stakeholders, targeted training activities, workshops and informative events will be organized on a regular basis based on the Stakeholders' Action Plan to enhance the public/scientific awareness and impact.

See [Annex 2](#) for membership.

Project Management Committee (PMC)

For the duration of the European funded project, CY-Biobank (grand agreement number No. 857122), a Project Management Committee (PMC) is responsible for the overall CY-Biobank project management and it is the ultimate decision-making body. It is comprised of a representative from each partner with an equal decision-making vote. In case of a tie, the Project Coordinator will have the casting vote. Representation in the PMC is as follows:

University of Cyprus, Prof. Constantinos Deltas, Project Coordinator & biobank.cy Director General
Medical University of Graz, (MUG, BBMRI.at), Prof. Kurt Zatloukal (QMS lead)
BBMRI-ERIC, Prof. Jens Habermann, Director General
RTD TALOS, Dr Alexandros Michaelides, Chief Executive Officer

LEGAL FRAMEWORK

The biobank.cy Center of Excellence is operating with a status of a separate School, under the umbrella of the University of Cyprus, which is a public non-profit organisation subject to the Cypriot law. It enjoys scientific and partial administrative autonomy while complying with the rules and regulations of the UCY. Consequently, the biobank.cy is also subject to UCY legislation:

- [The University of Cyprus Law 1989 to 2019](#)
- [The University of Cyprus \(Election, Evaluation and Upgrading of the Academic Staff\) Statutes of 1996 to 2015](#)
- [The Rules of Evaluation for the Upgrading, Continuation or Termination of Employment of the Academic Staff](#)

The CoE is compliant with Cyprus law 125(I)/2018) for implementation of the European Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679. As a Data Protection Officer (DPO), it has been appointed the legal firm KOUSIOS KORFIOTIS PAPACHARALAMBOUS (<https://kkplaw.com/>).

The donor has full power of disposal over his/her biomaterials and related data. This generally includes the option to restrict use to specific research project, diagnostic test, and the exclusion from the broad unlimited time use. A donor deciding to withdraw from the Biobank, will be asked to sign a request without having to justify his/her decision. The Withdrawal Form ([Annex 3](#)) informs the donors about the process and allows them to choose among several and gradual options going from “no more contact” to the “destruction” of the materials. He/she will be given the option for irreversible anonymization of his/her record, including abolishing the link with the data, thus keeping the data and biological material for use in cases that no follow-up is required.

LOCAL AND INTERNATIONAL GUIDELINES

The biobank.cy Center of Excellence is listing below local and international guidelines that have been considered for the set-up of the governance and access policy:

- [WMA Declaration of Helsinki – Ethical Principles for Medical Research Involving Human Subjects](#), 1964
- [WHO Operational Guidelines for Ethics Committees](#), 2000
- [Research ethics committees: basic concepts for capacity-building](#), 2009
- [Opinion of the Cyprus National Bioethics Committee \(CNBC\) regarding the creation and use of Biobanks and archived human biological samples for research](#), 2009
- [Opinion of the Cyprus National Bioethics Committee \(CNBC\) regarding the incidental and unexpected findings from genetic analysis with technologies of Next Generation Sequencing](#), 2015
- [Opinion of the Cyprus National Bioethics Committee \(CNBC\) regarding the bioethical framework for participation of citizens in campaigns promoting health](#), 2015
- [Good Clinical Practice \(ICH-GCP\), R2](#), 2017

ANNEX 1: Access Policy

Access policy to Biobank data and material

- At the Biobank of the University of Cyprus there are archived personal and medical data and biological material, in the form of DNA, plasma, serum, urine. Other biospecimens are also stored or may be stored as well, according to the needs of specific projects. The data and material can be used for any useful research studies with anticipated positive impact to humans.
- Prospective applicants for access to the Biobank must demonstrate that they are knowledgeable researchers who have access to a well-developed laboratory and have had previous experience in research or have collaborators with documented experience in research. This is a requirement to secure that the precious material will be used in the best possible and promising way without risking its improper use. Applicants cannot be students at any stage of their career, rather applications should be submitted by their immediate supervisors.
- The Biobank operates in absolute confidentiality of the data concerning the volunteers. At the same time, the Biobank operates in transparency with regards to its activities and use of the data. This means that every research project and the use of the data/material is publicized through the website of the Biobank. The name of the organizations and project coordinators who use material of the Biobank will be known to the public along with the title of their research proposal.
- The Biobank collects and archives material and data for general use while at the same time it serves as a custodian to the material of other researchers who so wish and do not have the capacity to have their own Biobanking premises and facilities. Material for which the Biobank serves as a custodian is under the control of the owner who also pays a fee for this custodianship service. This material and data cannot be used by other researchers without the prior approval and agreement of the owner, which may entail a collaboration between the owner and the applicant to use the material. It is up to the owner to accept or refuse any application for collaboration.
- All samples and data for general use are going to be provided to the researchers in absolute confidentiality, in an anonymous and coded format, with no mechanism to identify the volunteers. In case of useful or incidental findings of actionable character, the researchers will communicate with the Academic Council of the Biobank and discuss the most appropriate mechanism of contacting the concerned volunteer, if this was his/her wish and option on the consent form (see consent form of the Biobank or the specific project concerned). The team should include a health care professional and a genetic counselor.

Guidelines for obtaining access to the Biobank

Who has access?

All applicants to use data and material can be of the public or the private domain, both in Cyprus and abroad, and the proposed research should be in the public interest. Applicants must demonstrate ability to conduct research and the host organization must be a place where the proposed research can be conducted successfully. The project must have secured the necessary funding and have a prior

approval by the Cyprus National Bioethics Committee (CNBC) or an appropriate ethics committee if from abroad.

For applications coming from abroad, the applicants should demonstrate approval by an appropriate ethics body/Institutional Review Board in their country, before consideration. Additionally, the Biobank will assess whether there is a need for a separate approval by the CNBC.

How are requests for samples and data assessed?

The Biobank has its own internal and external advisory ethics boards, which are duly informed of any application to use material for research, however it is not the duty of these bodies to perform an additional detailed ethics review. Any proposal or any application to use Biobank material must have a prior approval by an appropriate ethics board, which in Cyprus is represented by the Cyprus National Bioethics Committee.

The internal Biobank Access Committee, which includes members of the Academic Council and the Internal Ethics Board, will examine every application for the purpose of insuring that it complies with ethical guidelines, is not planning to duplicate research objectives already in progress and does not impinge the rights of other researchers who are using the same or similar material through this Biobank. It will also evaluate the availability of requested material and its quality and suitability for the intended purpose, as well as the amount requested.

What is the access procedure?

- 1) **Registration:** Register the identity of the researcher and his/her host organization. The host organization must be an approved research center registered with the Cyprus Research and Innovation Foundation. If it is a foreign organization, it must be approved and registered in its own country. The applicant must provide a brief CV and a proof of previous research experience.
- 2) **Application:** Applications may be submitted by single researchers or by legal entities/institutions, including Universities or research centers. It is a single stage process which requires the completion of specific questions aimed to determine whether the proposal can be materialized through the Biobank and is compatible with the Biobank's objectives as well as to appraise the scientific merit of the proposal. The Biobank Data Access Committee will determine whether there is opportunity for networking applicants with other Biobank collaborators regarding current projects and potential common goals.

Specific fields to complete on the application form:

- Name of Principal Investigator and major collaborators/partners
 - Identity of the Host Organization where research will be conducted
 - Summary of proposal, 400-500 words
 - Major specific aims, 400-500 words
 - Description of Methodology with major tools to use, no more than 800 words
 - Impact expected from the proposed research, 400-500 words
 - Material and data requested, 200-300 words
- 3) **Access agreement:** A contract is signed by the two parties, which describes the purpose of the collaboration between the researcher(s) and the Biobank. Researchers from academia and from not-for profit organizations pay a fee which only aims to ensure partial

cost recovery. For private commercial entities and for-profit organizations, the fee could be higher with the possibility to cover full cost. Fees have been determined by the business development team based on the CoE business model (costing and pricing calculations). Potential intellectual property rights belong with the Biobank and researchers based on contribution, as described in the MTA/DTA to be signed by both parties.

- 4) **Research results** must be returned to the Biobank, after the research is published or the research project completed

ANNEX 2: Governance Members

Academic Council

Chairman: Prof. Constantinos Deltas
Members: Prof. Christos Schizas
Dr Konstantinos Parperis
Dr Gregory Papagregoriou
Dr Konstantinos Voskarides

Center of Excellence Council

Members: H.E. Ambassador of Austria, Dr. Maria Eva Ziegler, Observer
Marios Eliades, Lawyer
Elena Tanou, Tourism Entrepreneur
Marios Kouloumas, President of the Cypriot Federation of Patients' Associations
Katerina Agapitou, Journalist
Anastasia Papadopoulou, Lawyer
Professor Constantinos Deltas, CY-Biobank Director, Observer

International Scientific Advisory Committee (ISAC)

Members: Prof. Daniel Gale,
Advisory Board under formation

Internal Ethics Advisory Board (IEAB)

Members: Dr Aristotelis Constantinides, Associate Professor, Department of Law
Dr Tatiana Synodinou, Associate Professor, Department of Law
Dr Gregory Papagregoriou, biobank.cy Senior Group Leader
Mrs Despina Roussou, Cyprus Federation of Patients' Organizations

External Ethics Advisory Board (EEAB)

Members: Prof. Urban Wiesing, The Institute for Medical Ethics and History of Medicine,
University of Tübingen
Prof. Eleni Kalokairinou, Professor of Philosophy, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
Mr Yiannos Geogiades, Advocate & Legal Consultant, Geogiades & Associates
Mrs Stella Eleftheriadou, Cyprus Federation of Patients' Organizations

Stakeholders' Forum

Members: Klea Papaellina
Marios Kouloumas, President of Cyprus Federation of Patients' Organizations
Forum under formation

No payment or honorarium is provided to Members of the CoE Advisory Boards and Committees.
Compensation or reimbursement for expenses incurred may be considered.

ANNEX 3: Withdrawal Form

ΚΕΝΤΡΟ ΑΡΙΣΤΕΙΑΣ - ΒΙΟΤΡΑΠΕΖΑ ΚΑΙ ΒΙΟΙΑΤΡΙΚΗ ΕΡΕΥΝΑ, biobank.cy

ΕΝΤΥΠΟ ΑΝΑΚΛΗΣΗΣ ΣΥΓΚΑΤΑΘΕΣΗΣ

[για συμμετοχή ως εθελοντής δότης βιολογικού υλικού]

Ανάκληση Συγκατάθεσης:

Εγώ ο/η

επιθυμώ να ανακαλέσω τη συγκατάθεσή μου για συμμετοχή ως εθελοντής δότης δεδομένων και βιολογικού υλικού:

Στη Βιοτράπεζα του Κέντρου Αριστείας - Βιοτράπεζα και Βιοϊατρική έρευνα, biobank.cy (**Βιοτράπεζα**)

Η εν λόγω ανάκληση συνεπάγεται ανάκληση συγκατάθεσης επεξεργασίας των προσωπικών μου δεδομένων από τη Βιοτράπεζα δυνάμει του άρθρου 7 παρ. 3 του Ευρωπαϊκού Γενικού Κανονισμού Προστασίας Δεδομένων 2016/679.

Δηλώνω ότι, έχω ενημερωθεί ότι για να μην επηρεασθεί η αξιοπιστία των αποτελεσμάτων έρευνας που ίσως βρίσκεται σε εξέλιξη, και να ελαχιστοποιηθεί η απώλεια του επιστημονικού οφέλους, στη περίπτωση απόφασής μου να αποσυρθώ, έχω ενημερωθεί για τους τρόπους ανάκλησης της συγκατάθεσής μου και έχω επιλέξει τον επιθυμητό τρόπο ανάκλησης όπως φαίνεται πιο κάτω.

Κατανοώ ότι σε περίπτωση επιλογής «Χωρίς περαιτέρω χρήση», η **Βιοτράπεζα** θα καταστρέψει με ασφαλή μέσα τα δεδομένα ή, εναλλακτικά, τα δεδομένα θα ανωνυμοποιηθούν πλήρως και θα αποσυνδεθούν από τα δείγματα που συλλέχθηκαν (irretrievably unlink) αφού ο κωδικός που χρησιμοποιείται για επανασύνδεση των δειγμάτων και των προσωπικών δεδομένων θα διαγραφεί. Μόνο το υπογεγραμμένο έντυπο συγκατάθεσης και ένα αντίγραφο του παρόντος εντύπου ανάκλησης συγκατάθεσης που επιβεβαιώνει την απόσυρσή μου θα φυλάσσονται για σκοπούς αρχειοθέτησης/αποδεικτικού στοιχείου της επιλογής ανάκλησης και για σκοπούς αποτροπής περαιτέρω χρήσης πληροφοριών σχετικά με εμένα σε έρευνα.

Τέλος, κατανοώ ότι τα δεδομένα δεν μπορούν να αφαιρεθούν από ήδη ολοκληρωμένες μελέτες / επιστημονικές αναλύσεις που έγιναν με χρήση των δεδομένων και του βιολογικού υλικού μου, καθώς επίσης κατανοώ ότι υπάρχει πιθανότητα να μην είναι δυνατή η ανίχνευση όλων των κατανεμημένων δειγμάτων.

Επιλογές ανάκλησης συγκατάθεσης (επιλέξτε με ✓)

- **«Χωρίς περαιτέρω επικοινωνία»:** Το Κέντρο δεν θα επικοινωνεί πλέον με κανένα μέσο με τον εθελοντή αλλά δύναται να συνεχίσει να χρησιμοποιεί τα δείγματα και τα δεδομένα που έχουν ήδη συλλεχθεί και δύναται να συνεχίσει να έχει πρόσβαση στο ιατρικό του ιστορικό εάν αυτό είναι απαραίτητο.
- **«Χωρίς περαιτέρω πρόσβαση»:** Η Βιοτράπεζα δεν θα επικοινωνήσει με τον εθελοντή και δε θα έχει δυνατότητα πρόσβασης στο ιατρικό ιστορικό του αλλά μπορεί να συνεχίσει να χρησιμοποιεί δείγματα και δεδομένα που έχουν ήδη συλλεχθεί.
- **«Χωρίς περαιτέρω χρήση»:** Το Κέντρο θα καταστρέψει ή θα ανωνυμοποιήσει όλα τα δείγματα και δεδομένα από τον εθελοντή και δεν θα επικοινωνήσει με τον συμμετέχοντα ξανά. Ως εκ τούτου, τυχόν πληροφορίες και δείγματα που συλλέχθηκαν προηγουμένως δεν θα είναι πλέον διαθέσιμα σε ερευνητές.

Ημερομηνία:

Υπογραφή:

ΔΗΛΩΣΗ ΑΜΕΡΟΛΗΠΤΗΣ ΕΚΤΕΛΕΣΗΣ ΚΑΘΗΚΟΝΤΩΝ ΚΑΙ ΑΠΟΚΑΛΥΨΗΣ
ΤΥΧΟΝ ΣΥΓΚΡΟΥΣΗΣ ΣΥΜΦΕΡΟΝΤΩΝ

Ο/η υπογεγραμμένος/η με αριθμό
πολιτικής ταυτότητας, εργοδοτούμενος/η του Κέντρου Αριστείας για
Βιοτρέπεζα και Βιοϊατρική Έρευνα, CY-Biobank, του Πανεπιστημίου Κύπρου (ΠΚ) στη θέση
..... δηλώνω ότι:

α) Θα εκτελώ τα καθήκοντά μου με αμέριστη αμεροληψία, χωρίς να επηρεάζομαι από
οποιοδήποτε παράγοντα που δεν βασίζεται σε αντικειμενικά γεγονότα και στοιχεία. Σε
περίπτωση που έχω οποιοδήποτε οικονομικό ή άλλο συμφέρον, άμεσο ή έμμεσο, σε σχέση
με το έργο του Κέντρου Αριστείας για Βιοτρέπεζα και Βιοϊατρική Έρευνα (CY-Biobank),
δεσμεύομαι να ενημερώσω άμεσα τη διεύθυνση του Κέντρου.

β) Αντιλαμβάνομαι ότι σύγκρουση συμφερόντων μπορεί να προκύψει από οποιαδήποτε
ιδιάζουσα σχέση ή οποιαδήποτε εξ αίματος ή εξ αγχιστείας συγγένεια μέχρι τετάρτου
βαθμού ή σχέση οξείας έχθρας με οποιοδήποτε πρόσωπο που έχει πρόδηλο οικονομικό ή
άλλο συμφέρον και σχέση με το CY-Biobank. Σε περίπτωση που προκύψει τέτοιου είδους
σύγκρουση συμφέροντος οφείλω να τη φέρω άμεσα εις γνώσιν του εργοδότη μου.

γ) Έχω λάβει γνώση της Εγκυκλίου 4.9 για τη Σύγκρουση Συμφερόντων / Σύγκρουση
Υποχρεώσεων του Πανεπιστημίου Κύπρου ([Παράρτημα Ι](#)) που αφορά στα μέλη Διδακτικού
Εκπαιδευτικού Προσωπικού (ΔΕΠ) και τους ερευνητές, και αποδέχομαι ότι για σκοπούς
εργοδότησής μου στο CY-Biobank, οι σχετικοί όροι θα με δεσμεύουν και εμένα ανεξάρτητα
με την κατηγορία προσωπικού στην οποία ανήκει η θέση που κατέχω.

Υπογραφή Εργοδοτούμενου:

Ημερομηνία:

Παράρτημα Ι

4. ΑΚΑΔΗΜΑΪΚΟ ΠΡΟΣΩΠΙΚΟ

4.9 Εγκύκλιος για την Σύγκρουση Συμφερόντων / Σύγκρουση Υποχρεώσεων

1. Γενικά

- 1.1 Το Διδακτικό και Ερευνητικό Προσωπικό που συμμετέχει στις επιχειρηματικές δραστηριότητες οφείλει στις σχέσεις του με τρίτους να διαφυλάσσει και να εξασφαλίζει τα καλώς νοούμενα συμφέροντα καθώς και την αποστολή του Πανεπιστημίου Κύπρου.

Για αποφυγή σύγκρουσης συμφερόντων ή και υποχρεώσεων πρέπει να ακολουθούνται οι διαδικασίες που αναφέρονται στη Παράγραφο 4.

- 1.2 Δεν είναι δυνατή η ταυτόχρονη πλήρης απασχόληση του Διδακτικού και Ερευνητικού Προσωπικού στο Πανεπιστήμιο Κύπρου και σε φορέα εκμετάλλευσης της γνώσης.

2. Συγκρούσεις Υποχρεώσεων

Συγκρούσεις υποχρεώσεων μπορεί να προκύψουν όταν υπάρχουν συγκρουόμενες απαιτήσεις όσον αφορά στον χρόνο και την ενέργεια ενός μέλους του ακαδημαϊκού προσωπικού ως αποτέλεσμα εξω-πανεπιστημιακών δραστηριοτήτων και συμφερόντων τα οποία θα μπορούσαν να περιορίσουν την ικανότητα του μέλους του ακαδημαϊκού προσωπικού να ανταπεξέλθει στις υποχρεώσεις του/της απέναντι στο πανεπιστήμιο.

Το Πανεπιστήμιο αναμένει ότι οι εξω-πανεπιστημιακές δραστηριότητες και ενδιαφέροντα μελών του ακαδημαϊκού προσωπικού δε θα παρακωλύουν τις κύριες υποχρεώσεις τους, στις οποίες συγκαταλέγονται η διδασκαλία, η έρευνα, η διοικητική δραστηριότητα, η παραγωγή δημιουργικού έργου ή άλλου είδους υποχρεώσεις προς το Πανεπιστήμιο.

Ο καθορισμός συγκεκριμένων καθολικών κριτηρίων για τον ορισμό του σωστού καταμερισμού εργασίας δεν είναι εφικτός, αλλά η πείρα διδάσκει ότι τα μέλη του ακαδημαϊκού προσωπικού με πλήρη απασχόληση αντιμετωπίζουν δυσκολίες στη διεκπεραίωση των κύριων υποχρεώσεών τους όταν αφιερώνουν περισσότερο από το αντίστοιχο μιας εργάσιμης ημέρας σε εξω-πανεπιστημιακές δραστηριότητες, όπως η παροχή συμβουλευτικών υπηρεσιών ή δραστηριότητες που απαιτούν την παροχή ουσιαστικών διοικητικών υπηρεσιών προς εξω-πανεπιστημιακό οργανισμό.

Η συμμετοχή σε τέτοιας φύσεως δραστηριότητες θα πρέπει να αποσκοπεί στην ενίσχυση της ακαδημαϊκής ιδιότητας του μέλους του ακαδημαϊκού προσωπικού και την ενίσχυση της δημόσιας αναγνώρισης και κύρους του Πανεπιστημίου.

Ορισμένες δραστηριότητες στον τομέα της δημόσιας υπηρεσίας συνεισφέρουν στη δημόσια αναγνώριση και ενίσχυση του κύρους του Πανεπιστημίου Κύπρου ως εξέχοντος και δημιουργικού ιδρύματος. Σε περιπτώσεις οι οποίες προνοούν εκτεταμένη υπηρεσία στο δημόσιο τομέα εκ μέρους του μέλους του ακαδημαϊκού προσωπικού (π.χ. διδακτική θέση, συμμετοχή σε επιτροπές Κυβερνητικής πολιτικής, υπηρεσία σε επαγγελματική οργάνωση, διεκδίκηση δημόσιου αξιώματος κλπ.), οι πρόεδροι των τμημάτων και οι κοσμήτορες πρέπει να ενημερώνονται ώστε να γίνονται κατάλληλες διευθετήσεις.

Μέλη του ακαδημαϊκού προσωπικού τα οποία λαμβάνουν πλήρη χορηγία και οικονομική ενίσχυση μέσω συμβολαίου κατά τη διάρκεια της ακαδημαϊκής χρονιάς, συμπεριλαμβανομένου του καλοκαιριού, θεωρείται αποδεκτό αυτή να είναι το αντίστοιχο της μιας ημέρας εβδομαδιαίως για εξω-πανεπιστημιακή δραστηριότητα, εκτός εάν αυτό απαγορεύεται από τους όρους της συμφωνίας με τον χορηγό.

Εάν προκύψουν ερωτήματα σχετικά με το τι επιτρέπεται από τη συγκεκριμένη χορηγία ή συμβόλαιο, διευκρινήσεις μπορούν να ληφθούν μετά από συνεννόηση με τον Διευθυντή Διοίκησης.

Μέλη του ακαδημαϊκού προσωπικού τα οποία δε μπορούν να αντεπεξέλθουν ικανοποιητικά στις υποχρεώσεις τους προς το Πανεπιστήμιο λόγω των εξω-πανεπιστημιακών τους δραστηριοτήτων μπορούν να συζητήσουν το ενδεχόμενο άδειας άνευ απολαβών. Σε ορισμένες επιστήμες όπου ενδείκνυται, όπως π.χ. την αρχιτεκτονική, την ιατρική, και σε περιπτώσεις που υπάρχει τεκμηριωμένη ανάγκη, μέλη του ακαδημαϊκού προσωπικού μπορούν επίσης να συζητήσουν το ενδεχόμενο μερικής απασχόλησης.

3. Συγκρούσεις συμφερόντων

3.1 Γενικά

Συγκρούσεις συμφερόντων μπορεί να προκύψουν όταν τα προσωπικά συμφέροντα μέλους του ακαδημαϊκού προσωπικού παρακωλύουν τις υποχρεώσεις του/της προς το Πανεπιστήμιο. Οι καθοριστικοί παράγοντες προς αποφυγήν ηθικών και νομικών συγκρούσεων συμφερόντων είναι η προσωπική υπευθυνότητα και ακεραιότητα. Το Πανεπιστήμιο Κύπρου αναμένει όπως όλα τα μέλη του ακαδημαϊκού και διοικητικού προσωπικού διεξάγουν τις εξω-πανεπιστημιακές τους δραστηριότητες με τρόπο ο οποίος να δίνει μια θετική εικόνα τόσο του μέλους σαν άτομο και της ιδιότητάς του όσο και του Πανεπιστημίου.

Ο καθορισμός προτύπων πρακτικής και επιτέλεσης εργασίας σε σχέση με πιθανές συγκρούσεις συμφερόντων πρέπει να γίνεται στο οικείο επίπεδο με την καθοδήγηση των Κοσμητόρων, σε συνεννόηση με τους Προέδρους των Τμημάτων και την έγκριση του Αντιπρύτανη. Το κύριο μέσο κοινοποίησης και διαχείρισης εξω-πανεπιστημιακών δραστηριοτήτων περιλαμβάνει το διάλογο μεταξύ του ακαδημαϊκού προσωπικού και του οικείου Κοσμήτορα.

Η επίλυση των προβλημάτων επιτυγχάνεται καλύτερα στο επίπεδο Σχολής όπου υπάρχει μέγιστη γνώση του πεδίου έρευνας, ακαδημαϊκής δραστηριότητας ή άλλου είδους δημιουργικής εργασίας και όπου τα πρότυπα επιτέλεσης εργασίας και αξιολόγησης γίνονται κατανοητά. Με αυτό τον τρόπο μπορούν να απαμβλυνθούν διαφορές στα επίπεδα των οικείων προτύπων.

3.2 Ορισμοί

Ο όρος *εξωτερική οντότητα* αναφέρεται σε κάθε οργανισμό, συνεργασία, κυριότητα ή οποιαδήποτε άλλη οργανωμένη νομική οντότητα εκτός Πανεπιστημίου. Για μέλη του ακαδημαϊκού προσωπικού στον τομέα της αρχιτεκτονικής, αυτό δεν συμπεριλαμβάνει πελάτες στους οποίους παρέχουν επαγγελματικές υπηρεσίες.

Ως *σημαντικό συμφέρον* ορίζεται η λήψη ή η αναμονή αγαθού που έχει οικονομική αξία, συμπεριλαμβανομένου μισθού ή άλλου είδους πληρωμής για προσφερόμενες υπηρεσίες οι οποίες υπερβαίνουν ποσοστό ενός τρίτου του ετήσιου μισθού του, από το μέλος του ακαδημαϊκού προσωπικού ή μέλη της στενής του οικογένειας και συμπεριλαμβάνει μερίσματα που κατέχουν οι ίδιοι ή μέλη της στενής τους οικογένειας τα οποία υπερβαίνουν το ένα τρίτο του ετήσιου μισθού του ή 10% ιδιοκτησίας (ownership interest). (Αυτό αφορά μόνο σε μερίσματα

που υπάγεται απευθείας στον έλεγχό τους και όχι σε αυτά που διαχειρίζεται τρίτο μέρος π.χ. αμοιβαία κεφάλαια).

Ο όρος στενός συγγενής αναφέρεται στον/στην σύζυγο και στα εξαρτώμενα τέκνα.

Ο όρος *χρήση της υποδομής του Πανεπιστημίου Κύπρου* δεν περιλαμβάνει τη μη συχνή και περιστασιακή χρήση ούτε περιλαμβάνει υπηρεσίες για τις οποίες τα μέλη του ακαδημαϊκού προσωπικού αποζημιώνουν το Πανεπιστήμιο.

Είναι αδύνατο να απαριθμηθούν όλες οι περιπτώσεις στις οποίες μπορούν να παρουσιαστούν συγκρούσεις συμφερόντων. Ο ακόλουθος κατάλογος είναι ενδεικτικός τέτοιων περιπτώσεων:

A. Η ύπαρξη σημαντικού συμφέροντος σε εξωτερική οντότητα η οποία χορηγεί τη διδασκαλία ή τις ερευνητικές δραστηριότητες για τις οποίες μέλος του ακαδημαϊκού προσωπικού είναι υπεύθυνο. Υπάρχει πιθανή σύγκρουση συμφέροντος όταν ο κύριος ερευνητής λαμβάνει σημαντικό μέρος του ετήσιου μισθού του ανά έτος ή έχει σημαντικό μέρος σε ιδιωτική εταιρεία. Ενδεικτικά, σημαντικό μέρος του ετήσιου μισθού μπορεί να θεωρηθεί το ένα τρίτο, και μέρος σε ιδιωτική εταιρεία μεγαλύτερο του 10%.

B. Διαχείριση της αγοράς εξοπλισμού, εργαλείων, υλικών, υπηρεσιών ή άλλου είδους αγαθών από εξωτερική οντότητα στην οποία μέλος της στενής οικογενείας έχει σημαντικό ή καθοριστικό συμφέρον, χωρίς κήρυξη προσφορών.

Γ. Καθοδήγηση επιχορηγημένης έρευνας στο Πανεπιστήμιο Κύπρου προς όφελος εξωτερικής οντότητας η οποία δεν έχει υποστηρίξει την έρευνα αυτή.

Δ. Παροχή συμβουλευτικών υπηρεσιών προς κυβερνητική υπηρεσία σε θέμα το οποίο θα μπορούσε να ωφελήσει εξωτερική οντότητα στην οποία οι ίδιοι έχουν σημαντικό συμφέρον.

E. Μετάδοση σε εξωτερική οντότητα προϊόντων, πορισμάτων, υλικών, αρχείων ή πληροφοριών επιχορηγημένης έρευνας στα οποία δεν έχει πρόσβαση το ευρύτερο κοινό. (Αυτό δεν αποκλείει ενδεχόμενη παροχή συμβουλευτικών υπηρεσιών επί τη βάση αποτελεσμάτων επιχορηγημένης έρευνας κατά την οποία δεν υπάρχουν σχέσεις που συγκρούονται).

ΣΤ. Χρήση για προσωπικό όφελος (ή άλλους μη εγκεκριμένους σκοπούς) προνομιακής πληροφόρησης που αποκτήθηκε σε σχέση με επιχορηγημένη έρευνα ή άλλες πανεπιστημιακές δραστηριότητες.

Z. Αποδοχή δωρεών ή ειδικών εκδουλεύσεων από εξωτερική οντότητα με την οποία το Πανεπιστήμιο έχει (ή πρόκειται να έχει) δoσοληψίες π.χ. όπως καθορίζεται στο (B) πιο πάνω.

H. Αποδοχή επιχορήγησης έρευνας που αναλαμβάνεται για την επαλήθευση προκαθορισμένων ερευνητικών πορισμάτων.

Θ. Ταυτόχρονη συμμετοχή σε δραστηριότητες εξωτερικών οντοτήτων και σε ενδοπανεπιστημιακές δραστηριότητες οι οποίες συναγωνίζονται άμεσα για την εξασφάλιση κρατικών και/ή ιδιωτικών πόρων.

I. Λήψη ακαδημαϊκής ή διοικητικής απόφασης που θα μπορούσε να αποβεί σε προσωπικό τους όφελος.

K. Ταυτόχρονη λήψη εξωτερικής και πανεπιστημιακής οικονομικής αποζημίωσης για τις ίδιες υπηρεσίες ή δραστηριότητες.

Λ. Εμπλοκή φοιτητών, με τους οποίους έχουν σχέσεις επιτηρητή ή ακαδημαϊκού συμβούλου στο Πανεπιστήμιο, στις εξωτερικές τους δραστηριότητες χωρίς σαφές εκπαιδευτικό όφελος για τους φοιτητές.

4. Κοινοποίηση

Το Πανεπιστήμιο απαιτεί την ετήσια κοινοποίηση εξω-πανεπιστημιακών δραστηριοτήτων εκ μέρους των μελών του ακαδημαϊκού προσωπικού στην ετήσια έκθεση τους προς τον οικείο Κοσμήτορα.

Το Πανεπιστήμιο επίσης απαιτεί εκ μέρους όλων των μελών του ακαδημαϊκού προσωπικού την ετήσια κοινοποίηση στον οικείο Κοσμήτορα καταστάσεων, πιθανών ή πραγματικών, που μπορεί να οδηγήσουν σε σύγκρουση συμφερόντων

Στην Ετήσια Έκθεση τα μέλη του ακαδημαϊκού προσωπικού πρέπει να κάνουν ανασκόπηση των εξωτερικών τους δραστηριοτήτων. Αν η ανασκόπηση αυτή υποδεικνύει την πιθανότητα πραγματικής σύγκρουσης συμφερόντων ή την εμφάνιση τέτοιας (βλ. A-I πιο πάνω), τότε πρέπει να παρουσιασθεί σύντομη περιγραφή των δραστηριοτήτων αυτών στον οικείο Κοσμήτορα για έλεγχο.

Μετά την ανασκόπηση, οι εκθέσεις θα τοποθετούνται στο φάκελο του μέλους του ακαδημαϊκού προσωπικού στην κοσμητεία.

Εάν υπάρξουν σημαντικές αλλαγές στις εξωτερικές δραστηριότητες κατά τη διάρκεια του έτους, αναμένεται από τα μέλη του ακαδημαϊκού προσωπικού να τις αναφέρουν έγκαιρα.

Εάν πιθανές ή πραγματικές συγκρούσεις συμφερόντων δεν μπορούν να επιλυθούν από τον Κοσμήτορα η υπόθεση παραπέμπεται στον Αντιπρύτανη για εξέταση. Εάν κριθεί αναγκαίο, ο Αντιπρύτανης μπορεί να προχωρήσει στη σύσταση επιτροπής για να βοηθήσει στην εξέταση. Υπάρχει δυνατότητα έφεσης στη Σύγκλητο για αποφάσεις που λαμβάνονται από τον Αντιπρύτανη.

Ετήσια κοινοποίηση από τους Κοσμήτορες, τον Αντιπρύτανη και τον Πρύτανη θα υποβάλλονται στο Συμβούλιο μέσω του Διευθυντή Διοίκησης.

Η κοινοποίηση έχει σκοπό να εστιάσει την προσοχή σε πιθανές περιπτώσεις συγκρούσεων συμφερόντων και πάνω από όλα να προσφέρει ένα κατάλληλο μηχανισμό εξασφάλισης εκ των προτέρων έγκρισης για συμμετοχή σε εξωτερικές δραστηριότητες. Η έγκριση δίδεται κατόπιν εξέτασης πιθανής σύγκρουσης συμφερόντων από διοικητικό λειτουργό ο οποίος δεν θα επωφεληθεί με οιονδήποτε τρόπο από τις αποφάσεις που θα ληφθούν.

Μια τέτοια ρητή εκ των προτέρων έγκριση αποσκοπεί στην παροχή μεγίστου βαθμού προστασίας τόσο στο μέλος του ακαδημαϊκού προσωπικού όσο και στο Πανεπιστήμιο.

Επιπρόσθετα, το μέλος του ακαδημαϊκού προσωπικού με εξουσιοδότηση υπογραφής για διαχείριση εξωτερικών και εσωτερικών κονδυλίων πρέπει να χρησιμοποιεί την κρίση του/της ούτως ώστε να αποφευχθούν πιθανές καταστάσεις που θα εμπεριέχουν τον κίνδυνο σύγκρουσης συμφερόντων σε σχέση με την αγορά προμηθειών, υπηρεσιών και εξοπλισμού.

5. Αποκλειστικές πληροφορίες

Σε περιπτώσεις παροχής συμβουλευτικών υπηρεσιών ή επιχορηγημένης έρευνας οι ερευνητές πιθανόν να έχουν πρόσβαση σε αποκλειστικές/εμπιστευτικές πληροφορίες.

Μέλη του ακαδημαϊκού και διοικητικού προσωπικού τα οποία εκτίθενται σε τέτοιου είδους πληροφορίες πρέπει να διασφαλίσουν ότι τέτοιου είδους πληροφορίες δεν θα αποκαλυφθούν. Τα άτομα και όχι το Πανεπιστήμιο φέρουν την ευθύνη διεκπεραίωσης συμφωνιών που δεν πρέπει να κοινοποιούνται σύμφωνα με απαίτηση του χορηγού.

Είναι επίσης αναγκαίο αποκλειστικές σχέσεις μεταξύ διαφόρων οργανισμών με τους οποίους συνεργάζονται τα μέλη του ακαδημαϊκού και διοικητικού προσωπικού να διέπονται από πλήρη εχεμύθεια.

6. Χρήση Διευκολύνσεων

Μόνο σε πολύ ειδικές περιπτώσεις μπορεί να γίνει χρήση του εξοπλισμού και των διευκολύνσεων του Πανεπιστημίου (εκτός της Βιβλιοθήκης) για υπηρεσίες προς εξωτερικές οντότητες συμπεριλαμβανομένων οργανισμών που ελέγχονται από μέλη του ακαδημαϊκού προσωπικού και τούτο μόνον κατόπιν ρητής γραπτής έγκρισης από τον/την Πρόεδρο του Τμήματος και τον/την Κοσμήτορα. Χρήση προσωπικών υπολογιστών που αποτελούν περιουσία του Πανεπιστημίου και χρησιμοποιούνται στο σπίτι, κατόπιν έγκρισης, μπορεί να γίνει χωρίς άλλη έγκριση.

7. Χρήση ονόματος

Η απλή αναγνώριση του Πανεπιστημίου Κύπρου ως εργοδότη ενός μέλους του ακαδημαϊκού προσωπικού θεωρείται ως η δέουσα.

Αντιθέτως το όνομα του Πανεπιστημίου Κύπρου δεν θα πρέπει να χρησιμοποιείται για σκοπούς διαφήμισης ή προώθησης προϊόντων ή υπηρεσιών από οποιοδήποτε άτομο ή οργανισμό. Σε ειδικές περιπτώσεις μπορεί να ζητείται η γνώμη του Αντιπρύτανη όσον αφορά στη χρήση του ονόματος του Πανεπιστημίου Κύπρου.

Εγκρίθηκαν κατά την 98^η Συνεδρία του Συμβουλίου, ημερομηνίας 22 Ιανουαρίου 2003.

ΚΥΠΡΙΑΚΗ ΔΗΜΟΚΡΑΤΙΑ

ΕΘΝΙΚΗ ΕΠΙΤΡΟΠΗ ΒΙΟΗΘΙΚΗΣ ΚΥΠΡΟΥ

Αρ. Φακ.: ΕΕΒΚ/ΕΠ /2020/04
Αρ. Τηλ.: 22809038 / 22809039/ 22819101
Αρ. Φαξ: 22353878

30 Σεπτεμβρίου, 2020

Καθ. Κωνσταντίνος Δέλτας
Καθηγητής Γενετικής
Τμήμα Βιολογικών Επιστημών
Πανεπιστήμιο Κύπρου
Τ. Θ. 20537
1678 Λευκωσία

Αγαπητέ Καθ. Δέλτα,

Ερευνητική πρόταση με τίτλο:
«Biobanking and the Cyprus Human Genome Project»

Επιθυμώ ν' αναφερθώ στο πιο πάνω θέμα και να σας πληροφορήσω ότι η διαδικασία βιοηθικής αξιολόγησης έχει ολοκληρωθεί.

2. Σύμφωνα με το έντυπο απόφασης (ΕΕΒΚ04) που έχει εκδώσει η Επιτροπή Βιοηθικής Αξιολόγησης στις 22 Ιουλίου 2020 και το οποίο σας έχει ήδη κοινοποιηθεί, η ερευνητική πρόταση εγκρίνεται υπό τους ακόλουθους όρους:

- i. Οι ανήλικοι συμμετέχοντες θα πρέπει να εξαιρεθούν από την φύλαξη των δειγμάτων τους στη Βιοτράπεζα του Πανεπιστημίου Κύπρου.
- ii. Για τη φύλαξη δειγμάτων στην Βιοτράπεζα θα πρέπει να χρησιμοποιείται το επικαιροποιημένο έντυπο συγκατάθεσης ΕΕΒΚ03 ως έχει κατατεθεί στην Επιτροπή στις 30/06/2020. Το έντυπο αυτό θα πρέπει να αντικαταστήσει το έντυπο συγκατάθεσης που χρησιμοποιείται μέχρι τώρα ως είχε εγκριθεί στο πλαίσιο του προγράμματος ΕΕΒΚ ΕΠ 2011 04.
- iii. Το επικαιροποιημένο έντυπο συγκατάθεσης ΕΕΒΚ 03, ως ανωτέρω αναφέρεται, θα πρέπει επίσης να δίδεται και σε οποιοδήποτε άλλο ερευνητή επιθυμεί να φυλάξει δείγματα ενηλίκων στη Βιοτράπεζα του Πανεπιστημίου Κύπρου νοουμένου ότι έχει υποβάλει αίτηση στην ΕΕΒΚ και έχει λάβει σχετική έγκριση.

.../2

3. Σας ευχόμαστε κάθε επιτυχία στη διεξαγωγή της ερευνητικής σας πρότασης και αναμένουμε ανατροφοδότηση για την εκπλήρωση των ανωτέρω αναφερόμενων όρων, όπως επίσης για την πρόοδο διεξαγωγής της έρευνας σας μέσω των νενομισμένων εντύπων, ως προνοούνται στους Κώδικες Πρακτικής (διαθέσιμοι στην ιστοσελίδα της Εθνικής Επιτροπής Βιοηθικής Κύπρου).

Με εκτίμηση,

Καθ. Κωνσταντίνος Ν. Φελλάς
Πρόεδρος
Εθνικής Επιτροπής Βιοηθικής Κύπρου

KOUSHOS KORFIOTIS PAPACHARALAMBOUS LLC
ADVOCATES & LEGAL CONSULTANTS

To whom it may concern,

We, KOUSHOS KORFIOTIS PAPACHARALAMBOUS LLC ("KKP"), confirm that we have an agreement with the Centre of Excellence – Biobank and Biomedical Research of the University of Cyprus ("Centre") for the provision of advisory services to support the compliance of the Centre with General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679. The services include, among others, the preparation and implementation of reports and assessments, such as risk analysis for information security, mapping and analysis of data processing activities, data protection impact assessment (DPIA), information security plan as well as other accountability mechanisms such as internal policies and procedures and external notices.

At the same time, we act as the external Data Protection Officers of the Centre and advise on various privacy and data protection matters in relation to its the activities.

For and on behalf of Koushos Korfiotis Papacharalambous LLC,

Loucas Koushos

ΚΟΥΣΗΟΣ ΚΟΡΦΙΟΤΗΣ ΠΑΠΑΧΑΡΑΛΑΜΒΟΥΣ LLC
ADVOCATES & LEGAL CONSULTANTS

ΣΥΝΘΕΣΗ ΕΚΤΙΜΗΣΗΣ ΑΝΤΙΚΤΥΠΟΥ

ΕΚΔΟΣΗ:	1.0
ΥΠΕΥΘΥΝΟΣ:	Γρηγόρης Μιχαήλ, Υπεύθυνος Πληροφορικής Ασφάλειας
ΣΥΝΤΑΧΤΗΚΕ ΑΠΟ:	ΚΟΥΣΙΟΣ ΚΟΡΦΩΤΗΣ ΠΑΠΑΧΑΡΑΛΑΜΠΟΥΣ Δ.Ε.Π.Ε. και Quadprime Cyprus Ltd
ΕΓΚΡΙΘΗΚΕ ΑΠΟ:	
ΗΜΕΡΟΜΗΝΙΑ ΕΓΚΡΙΣΗΣ:	

Εκτίμηση Αντικτύπου

Η εκτίμηση αντικτύπου προσωπικών δεδομένων είναι η διαδικασία που περιγράφει την επεξεργασία προσωπικών δεδομένων, αξιολογεί την αναγκαιότητα και αναλογικότητα της επεξεργασίας και βοηθά τη Βιοτράπεζα να διαχειριστεί τους κινδύνους για τα δικαιώματα και τις ελευθερίες των φυσικών προσώπων, που προκύπτουν από την επεξεργασία των προσωπικών τους δεδομένων, μέσα από αξιολόγηση αυτών των κινδύνων και τον καθορισμό των κατάλληλων μέτρων. Αποδεικνύει ότι ο Οργανισμός λαμβάνει τα κατάλληλα μέτρα που καθορίζει ο Γενικός Κανονισμός για την Προστασία Προσωπικών Δεδομένων. Επίσης αποτελεί πολύ βασικό εργαλείο ευθύνης και λογοδοσίας του Οργανισμού για την προστασία των δεδομένων ήδη από το σχεδιασμό και εξ ορισμού (Privacy by Design and by Default).

Εξ ορισμού διενεργείται εκτίμηση αντικτύπου ΜΟΝΟ για τις δραστηριότητες επεξεργασίας που παρουσιάζουν υψηλούς κινδύνους σύμφωνα με το άρθρο 35 του Κανονισμού και σύμφωνα με τον σχετικό κατάλογο που εκδίδει το Γραφείο της Επιτρόπου Προστασίας Δεδομένων Προσωπικού Χαρακτήρα. Ως εκ τούτου, η διενεργηθείσα μελέτη που αφορά στη «Συλλογή/αρχαιοθέτηση γενετικού και άλλου βιολογικού υλικού και προσωπικών δημογραφικών και ιατρικών δεδομένων, καθώς και δεδομένων που αφορούν γενικά στην κατάσταση της υγείας τους, από εθελοντές δότες, αποθήκευση στη Βιοτράπεζα και χρήση σε ερευνητικά προγράμματα που εκπονούν Κύπριοι ή ξένοι ερευνητές» απορρέει από ανάλυση των κύριων δραστηριοτήτων επεξεργασίας του Οργανισμού και η οποία αναγνωρίζεται να ενέχει υψηλό κίνδυνο για τα δικαιώματα και τις ελευθερίες των υποκειμένων των δεδομένων. Για τις καθιερωμένες δραστηριότητες επεξεργασίας για τις οποίες έχουν ήδη αναγνωριστεί οι σχετικοί κίνδυνοι και τα εφαρμοστέα μέτρα μέσα από μια άλλη επίσημη ή ανεπίσημη εκτίμηση κινδύνων – ο Οργανισμός δεν διενεργεί εκτίμηση αντικτύπου. Αν όμως υπάρξουν σημαντικές αλλαγές στη φύση, στο πεδίο, στο πλαίσιο ή τους σκοπούς της επεξεργασίας από την προηγούμενη εκτίμηση, θα αναθεωρηθούν οι κίνδυνοι μέσα από μια μελέτη εκτίμησης αντικτύπου. Επιπλέον, γίνεται προεπισκόπηση στη βάση κριτηρίων που κατατάσσουν μια επεξεργασία ως "υψηλού κινδύνου" σύμφωνα με τον Κανονισμό.

Η πρώτη μελέτη εκτίμησης αντικτύπου για το Κέντρου Αριστείας biobank.cy - Βιοτράπεζα και Βιοϊατρική Έρευνα, διενεργήθηκε σε συνεργασία με τις KKP LLC και Quadprime Cyprus Ltd (συμβουλευτικές υπηρεσίες για την υποστήριξη της συμμόρφωσης του Κέντρου με τον Γενικό Κανονισμό Προστασίας Δεδομένων (ΕΕ) 2016/679) το Φεβρουάριο του 2020.

Πιο κάτω ακολουθεί διάγραμμα που παραθέτει τα κύρια στάδια και τη διαδικασία που ακολουθήθηκε για τη διενέργεια της εκτίμησης αντικτύπου.

Διάγραμμα Ροής Εκτίμησης Αντικτύπου

1) Αναγνώριση ανάγκης για εκτίμηση αντικτύπου

Καθορίστηκε κατά πόσο η δραστηριότητα επεξεργασίας παρουσιάζει υψηλούς κινδύνους σύμφωνα με το άρθρο 35 του Κανονισμού και σύμφωνα με τον σχετικό κατάλογο που εκδίδει το Γραφείο της Επιτρόπου Προστασίας Δεδομένων Προσωπικού Χαρακτήρα.

2) Περιγραφή της δραστηριότητας επεξεργασίας και των αντίστοιχων προσωπικών δεδομένων

Έγινε ανάλυση της κύριας δραστηριότητας επεξεργασίας και παρεπόμενων διεργασιών και αναγνώριση των προσωπικών δεδομένων υπό επεξεργασία. Στη συνέχεια έγινε έλεγχος για το μέγεθος της κλίμακας επεξεργασίας των δεδομένων, επηρεασμός των δικαιωμάτων των ασθενών και άλλων, ενδεχόμενη υιοθέτηση τεχνολογίας διεισδυτικού χαρακτήρα για την ιδιωτικότητα, κ.λπ.

3) Αξιολόγηση αναγκαιότητας και αναλογικότητας

Έλεγχος για το κατά πόσο η δραστηριότητα επεξεργασίας δεδομένων είναι αναγκαία και αναλογική σε σχέση με τους επιδιωκόμενους σκοπούς.

4) Εντοπισμός και αξιολόγηση των κινδύνων για τα δικαιώματα και τις ελευθερίες των ατόμων

Καθορίστηκαν οι πηγές κινδύνου, οι κύριες απειλές που μπορούν να προκαλέσουν τον εν λόγω κίνδυνο, οι κύριες πιθανές επιπτώσεις σε σχέση με την προστασία των δεδομένων αλλά και της ιδιωτικής ζωής των υποκειμένων που μπορεί να επιφέρει η απειλή, η εκτίμηση της σοβαρότητας του κινδύνου αλλά και η εκτιμώμενη πιθανότητα επέλευσης του κινδύνου. Τέλος, σε περίπτωση επέλευσης του κινδύνου, καθορίστηκε η τυχόν παραβίαση που μπορεί να υπάρξει όσον αφορά στα δικαιώματα και τις ελευθερίες των ατόμων που πρόσφεραν τα δεδομένα τους για επεξεργασία. Η αξιολόγηση των πιο πάνω έγινε στη βάση τεκμηριωμένων κριτηρίων και κλιμάκων ταξινόμησης του κινδύνου (ποιοτική ανάλυση).

5) Μέτρα ελέγχου των κινδύνων

Έγινε καθορισμός των απαραίτητων μέτρων τα οποία αποφασίστηκαν σε επίπεδο ομάδας εργασίας διενέργειας της εκτίμησης αντικτύπου και μετέπειτα της διεύθυνσης του Κέντρου Αριστείας ή /και μέσω της διαβούλευσης των εμπλεκόμενων μερών (όπου εφαρμόζεται), για περιορισμό του κινδύνου.

6) Παρακολούθηση, αναθεώρηση και βελτίωση

Αν οι κίνδυνοι παραμένουν υψηλοί παρά τα μέτρα ελέγχου για μετριασμό του επιπέδου των κινδύνων, που σημαίνει ότι ο Υπεύθυνος Επεξεργασίας αδυνατεί να προσφέρει λύση στο πλαίσιο των τελευταίων εξελίξεων, του κόστους εφαρμογής και τη φύση, το πεδίο εφαρμογής, το πλαίσιο και τους σκοπούς της επεξεργασίας, καθώς και τους κινδύνους διαφορετικής πιθανότητας επέλευσης και σοβαρότητας, ο Υπεύθυνος Επεξεργασίας θα διαβουλευτεί με την αρμόδια αρχή και κατ' επέκταση με τα άτομα που επηρεάζονται για αναζήτηση περαιτέρω θεραπείας των κινδύνων.

Σε κάθε περίπτωση, η εκτίμηση αντικτύπου ως δυναμική διεργασία παρακολουθείται, επανεξετάζεται και αναθεωρείται με στόχο να εκτιμήσει εάν η επεξεργασία των δεδομένων προσωπικού χαρακτήρα διενεργείται σύμφωνα με την εκτίμηση αντικτύπου στην προστασία δεδομένων και για βελτιστοποίηση της ασφάλειας επεξεργασίας προσωπικών δεδομένων ειδικά όταν μεταβάλλεται ο κίνδυνος.

ΡΗΤΡΑ ΕΜΠΙΣΤΕΥΤΙΚΟΤΗΤΑΣ

Ο/η υπογεγραμμένος/η με αριθμό πολιτικής ταυτότητας, εργοδοτούμενος/η του Κέντρου Αριστείας για Βιοτρέπεζα και Βιοϊατρική Έρευνα, CY-Biobank, του Πανεπιστημίου Κύπρου (ΠΚ) στη θέση με καθήκοντα που εμπεριέχουν Επεξεργασία Δεδομένων Προσωπικού Χαρακτήρα, αναγνωρίζω το απόρρητο των εν λόγω δεδομένων.

Ως εκ τούτου, δεσμεύομαι, σύμφωνα με τον **περί της Προστασίας των Φυσικών Προσώπων Έναντι της Επεξεργασίας των Δεδομένων Προσωπικού Χαρακτήρα και της Ελεύθερης Κυκλοφορίας των Δεδομένων αυτών Νόμο του 2018 (Ν. 125(I)/2018)** και τον Γενικό Κανονισμό για την Προστασία Δεδομένων (ΕΕ) 2016/679 του Ευρωπαϊκού Κοινοβουλίου, να παίρνω όλα τα προληπτικά μέτρα σύμφωνα με τις χρήσεις και την εξέλιξη της τεχνολογίας στο πλαίσιο των καθηκόντων μου, προκειμένου να προστατεύεται το απόρρητο των δεδομένων στα οποία έχω πρόσβαση, και ιδίως να αποτραπεί η οποιαδήποτε τροποποίηση, καταστροφή, ή μη εξουσιοδοτημένη διαβίβαση, σε πρόσωπα που δεν επιτρέπεται να λάβουν αυτές τις πληροφορίες. Ειδικότερα, δεσμεύομαι:

- Να μην χρησιμοποιώ τα δεδομένα στα οποία έχω πρόσβαση για σκοπούς άλλους από εκείνους που καθορίζονται στα καθήκοντά μου
- Να αποκαλύπτω αυτά τα δεδομένα μόνο σε πρόσωπα δεόντως εξουσιοδοτημένα να τα παραλάβουν, είτε πρόκειται για ιδιωτικά, δημόσια, φυσικά ή νομικά πρόσωπα
- Να μην δημιουργώ οποιαδήποτε αντίγραφα των δεδομένων εκτός από εκείνα που είναι αναγκαία για την εκπλήρωση των αρμοδιοτήτων και των καθηκόντων μου
- Να λαμβάνω όλα τα μέτρα σύμφωνα με τις χρήσεις λαμβάνοντας υπόψη τις τελευταίες εξελίξεις στο πλαίσιο των καθηκόντων μου, προκειμένου να αποτραπεί η δόλια ή μη εξουσιοδοτημένη χρήση των δεδομένων
- Να λαμβάνω όλα τα προληπτικά μέτρα σύμφωνα με τις χρήσεις και τις τελευταίες εξελίξεις ώστε να διασφαλίζεται το κατάλληλο επίπεδο ασφάλειας έναντι των κινδύνων
- Να διασφαλίσω, εντός των ορίων των καθηκόντων μου, ότι θα χρησιμοποιώ μόνο ασφαλή μέσα επικοινωνίας για τη μεταφορά αυτών των δεδομένων εκτός του Κέντρου Αριστείας για τη Βιοτρέπεζα και Βιοϊατρική Έρευνα του Πανεπιστημίου Κύπρου
- Να διασφαλίσω, εντός των ορίων των καθηκόντων μου, τα δικαιώματα πρόσβασης και διόρθωσης των δεδομένων
- Σε περίπτωση αναστολής ή αλλαγής των αρμοδιοτήτων μου, ή αποχώρησης από τη θέση αυτή, να επιστρέψω εντελώς τα δεδομένα, αρχεία που φυλάω στον υπολογιστή ή οποιοδήποτε άλλο μέσο που περιέχει αυτά τα δεδομένα

- Την τήρηση πλήρους εχεμύθειας έναντι παντός τρίτου και δηλώνω ότι θα απέχω γενικά από κάθε ενέργεια που μπορεί να θίξει κεκτημένα δικαιώματα του CY-Biobank ή του Πανεπιστημίου Κύπρου. Στο πλαίσιο αυτό έχω, επίσης, λάβει γνώση και δέχομαι ανεπιφύλακτα τους όρους του **Κώδικα Δεοντολογίας της Έρευνας, (Παράρτημα Ι)** ο οποίος ορίζει, μεταξύ άλλων, την υποχρέωση εμπιστευτικότητας (άρθρο 2.5) για όλους τους εργοδοτούμενους του ΠΚ που έρχονται σε επαφή με εμπιστευτικές πληροφορίες σχετικές με ερευνητικές δραστηριότητες.

Αυτή η ρήτρα Εμπιστευτικότητας ισχύει για όλη τη διάρκεια της εργοδότησής μου στην παρούσα θέση και θα παραμένει σε ισχύ, χωρίς να περιορίζεται σε οποιαδήποτε στιγμή μετά την αναστολή ή αλλαγή των αρμοδιοτήτων μου, ή αποχώρηση από τη θέση αυτή, δεδομένου ότι η ρήτρα αυτή σχετίζεται με τη χρήση και τη διαβίβαση δεδομένων προσωπικού χαρακτήρα.

Έχω ενημερωθεί ότι οποιαδήποτε παραβίαση αυτής της δέσμευσής μου με εκθέτει σε πιθανά ποινικά και πειθαρχικά μέτρα σύμφωνα με τις νομικές διατάξεις σε ισχύ.

Υπογραφή Εργοδοτούμενου:

Ημερομηνία:

Παράρτημα I

7.4 Κώδικας Δεοντολογίας Έρευνας

Πεδίο εφαρμογής

Ο παρών κώδικας εφαρμόζεται σε όλες τις ερευνητικές δραστηριότητες που διεξάγονται υπό την ευθύνη ή με συμμετοχή των υπηρετούντων μελών Δ.Ε.Π., Ε.Ε.Π, καθώς και των υπόλοιπων μελών του Διδακτικού Προσωπικού (π.χ. Επισκέπτες Ακαδημαϊκοί, Ειδικοί Επιστήμονες), των μελών του Διοικητικού Προσωπικού, των Προπτυχιακών και Μεταπτυχιακών φοιτητών ως μελών της Ακαδημαϊκής Κοινότητας, στους χώρους του Πανεπιστημίου Κύπρου ή εκτός αυτών, με ή χωρίς χρηματοδότηση. Οι πρόνοιες του παρόντος εφαρμόζονται, επίσης και στις περιπτώσεις παροχής εμπειρογνομosύνης, εξειδικευμένων υπηρεσιών, προγραμμάτων κατάρτισης ή άλλων επιστημονικών εφαρμογών. Βασικός σκοπός της ύπαρξης του Κώδικα Δεοντολογίας είναι η εξασφάλιση της απρόσκοπτης παραγωγής πρωτογενούς ή και εφαρμοσμένης έρευνας στο Π.Κ. με τρόπο ωφέλιμο προς τον άνθρωπο και την κοινωνία.

Ο παρών Κώδικας Δεοντολογίας είναι σύμφωνος με το Σύνταγμα της Κυπριακής Δημοκρατίας, την Ευρωπαϊκή Σύμβαση των Δικαιωμάτων του Ανθρώπου, το δίκαιο της Ευρωπαϊκής Ένωσης και εν γένει την ισχύουσα εθνική και διεθνή νομοθεσία. Τis Ο κώδικας είναι σύμφωνος με κώδικες καλής πρακτικής, τις αρχές δεοντολογίας και τις διαδικασίες που απαιτούνται από την Εθνική Επιτροπή Βιοηθικής, οι οποίες και αποτελούν απαραίτητο συμπλήρωμά του.

Ο παρών Κώδικας πρέπει να συνδυάζεται περαιτέρω με τα παρακάτω:

- [Πολιτική διανοητικής ιδιοκτησίας Π.Κ.](#)
- [Πολιτική προστασίας προσωπικών δεδομένων Π.Κ.](#)
- [Ευρωπαϊκό Κώδικα Δεοντολογίας](#) για την ακεραιότητα της έρευνας

1. Αρχές

1.1 Γενικές Αρχές

Οι ορθές ερευνητικές πρακτικές βασίζονται σε θεμελιώδεις αρχές της ακεραιότητας της έρευνας. Η έρευνα πρέπει να διεξάγεται με σεβασμό στην επιστημονική αλήθεια, στην ακαδημαϊκή ελευθερία, στη ζωή, τη φύση και το περιβάλλον, στη βιολογική και πνευματική ακεραιότητα του ανθρώπου, στην ανθρώπινη αξιοπρέπεια, στη διανοητική ιδιοκτησία και στα προσωπικά δεδομένα. Κατά την έρευνα πρέπει να αποφεύγεται κάθε δυσμενής διάκριση των συμμετεχόντων λόγω, ενδεικτικά και όχι περιοριστικά, εθνότητας, φυλής, εθνικής καταγωγής, γλώσσας, φύλου, θρησκείας, ιδιωτικής ζωής, σεξουαλικού προσανατολισμού, ταυτότητας φύλου, σωματικής ικανότητας ή κοινωνικοοικονομικής κατάστασης. Κατά τη διεξαγωγή έρευνας οι ερευνητές/τριες οφείλουν όπως λαμβάνουν υπόψη τυχόν επιπτώσεις δύναται να έχει η εν λόγω έρευνα σε ευάλωτες ομάδες του πληθυσμού.

1.2 Αξιοπιστία και υπευθυνότητα στη διεξαγωγή της έρευνας

Κάθε επιστημονική έρευνα πρέπει να διεξάγεται με τρόπο που εγγυάται την αξιοπιστία της, η οποία αντανάκλαται στο σχεδιασμό, τη μεθοδολογία, την ανάλυση, τη χρήση των πόρων και την ανακοίνωση των αποτελεσμάτων της, διασφαλίζοντας έτσι την ποιότητά της. Όλα τα μέλη της πανεπιστημιακής κοινότητας που συμμετέχουν στη διεξαγωγή έρευνας θα πρέπει να γνωρίζουν, να σέβονται και να τηρούν τους κώδικες δεοντολογίας έρευνας του οικείου επιστημονικού ή/και επαγγελματικού τους κλάδου. Ο σεβασμός αυτός θα πρέπει να αφορά όλα τα στάδια της έρευνας, από τον σχεδιασμό και την επιλογή του δείγματος, τη

μεθοδολογία ή την εξασφάλιση συγκατάθεσης από τους συμμετέχοντες σε αυτήν, μέχρι και την ανάλυση, έκδοση και διάχυση των αποτελεσμάτων. Οι ερευνητές δεν πρέπει να επαναλαμβάνουν προηγούμενες έρευνες άλλων παρά μόνο αν δικαιολογείται επιστημονικά η επανάληψη. Η λογοκλοπή και η ιδιοποίηση ξένων επιτευγμάτων απαγορεύονται.

1.3 Ευθύνη και λογοδοσία

Η προσωπική και συλλογική ευθύνη συνδέονται οργανικά με την ηθική συμπεριφορά που θα πρέπει να επιδεικνύουν τα μέλη του Πανεπιστημίου Κύπρου. Συγκεκριμένα, κάθε ερευνητής/νήτρια και κάθε ερευνητική ομάδα αναμένεται να επιδεικνύει τη δέουσα υπευθυνότητα σε κάθε ενέργεια ή απόφαση που λαμβάνει και να αναλαμβάνει τη σχετική ευθύνη. Την ίδια στιγμή όλοι/όλες, είτε προσωπικά, είτε συλλογικά, θα πρέπει να είναι σε θέση να αιτιολογούν με σαφή και δεοντολογικά σωστό τρόπο τις επιλογές τους και τις πράξεις ή παραλείψεις τους στο πλαίσιο διεξαγωγής της έρευνας και της διάχυσης των αποτελεσμάτων της. Ως παραπτώματα στον τομέα της έρευνας νοούνται κατά παράδοση η κατασκευή, ή αλλοίωση ερευνητικών αποτελεσμάτων, η παραποίηση ή η λογοκλοπή (η αποκαλούμενη κατηγοριοποίηση FFP- fabrication, falsification, plagiarism) κατά την υποβολή προτάσεων, τη διεξαγωγή ή τον έλεγχο ερευνητικών δραστηριοτήτων, ή κατά την κοινοποίηση ερευνητικών αποτελεσμάτων.

1.4 Κοινωνική Υπευθυνότητα

Οι ερευνητές/νήτριες οφείλουν να διεξάγουν τις έρευνές τους με σεβασμό προς το περιβάλλον, την αειφόρο πολιτική και την ευρύτερη κοινωνία, να διαχέουν τα αποτελέσματα της έρευνας με κατανοητό τρόπο στο κοινωνικό σύνολο και να συμβάλουν στην πολιτισμική και οικονομική βελτίωση της ευρύτερης κοινωνίας. Οφείλουν ακόμη να ασκούν την ερευνητική τους δραστηριότητα με κύριο σκοπό την προαγωγή της επιστημονικής γνώσης και το όφελος του κοινωνικού συνόλου και να τηρούν τις διατάξεις της νομοθεσίας που αναφέρονται στα ερευνητικά αντικείμενα, τις αρχές ηθικής, τους κανόνες ορθής πρακτικής στην έρευνα, και τους κανόνες δεοντολογίας του επαγγέλματός τους και του παρόντος Κώδικα.

1.5 Υπεύθυνη χρήση των πόρων του πανεπιστημίου

Οι πόροι του Πανεπιστημίου Κύπρου δεν ανήκουν σε κανέναν ατομικά ή συλλογικά, αλλά στο σύνολο της ακαδημαϊκής κοινότητας. Η υλικοτεχνική υποδομή του Πανεπιστημίου στην ολότητά της διατίθεται προς χρήση στους/στις ερευνητές/νήτριες με την υποχρέωση αυτή να γίνεται υπεύθυνα, δηλαδή με φροντίδα για αποφυγή οποιασδήποτε σπατάλης ή καταστροφής, με σεβασμό στις αρχές και στους κανόνες χρηστής διαχείρισης.

2. Ορθές ερευνητικές πρακτικές

2.1 Ελευθερία και διαφάνεια στη συγκατάθεση

Οιαδήποτε πρόσωπα που συμμετέχουν σε έρευνα πρέπει καταρχήν να δίνουν τη γραπτή συγκατάθεσή τους χωρίς την παραμικρή μορφή πίεσης και έχοντας πλήρη γνώση και επίγνωση των οποιωνδήποτε συνεπειών από τη συμμετοχή τους. Σε περίπτωση συμμετοχής ανηλίκων σε έρευνα, πρέπει να λαμβάνεται η γραπτή συγκατάθεση του γονέα ή κηδεμόνα. Ο/η ερευνητής/νήτρια οφείλει να διασφαλίζει, στο μέτρο του δυνατού, ότι οι συμμετέχοντες δεν θα επηρεαστούν αρνητικά από τη συμμετοχή τους στην έρευνα και να παρακολουθεί στενά περιπτώσεις στις οποίες διακρίνονται επιπτώσεις, ως απόρροια της εν λόγω συμμετοχής. Οι επιπτώσεις δύνανται να έχουν διαφορετική μορφή ανάλογα με τα αντικείμενα της έρευνας και το επιστημονικό πεδίο εκάστου/ης ερευνητή/τριας. Συγκεκριμένα η συγκατάθεση θεωρείται ότι είναι συνειδητή, όταν τα άτομα, στα οποία διενεργείται η έρευνα, έχουν σαφώς πληροφορηθεί τους σκοπούς της έρευνας από τον/την ή τους/τις υπεύθυνους/ες για τη διεξαγωγή της έρευνας, για τις ερευνητικές μεθόδους και για τις πιθανές συνέπειες από τη διεξαγωγή και δημοσίευση των αποτελεσμάτων της έρευνας. Εξαιρούνται οι περιπτώσεις όπου η εν λόγω πληροφόρηση θα

αλλοιώνει τα ερευνητικά συμπεράσματα και είναι αναγκαίο, σύμφωνα με τη φύση της έρευνας, τα άτομα στα οποία διενεργείται να μην την γνωρίζουν, ώστε η συμπεριφορά τους να παραμείνει ανεπηρέαστη. Η ελεύθερη συγκατάθεση προϋποθέτει ότι τα άτομα που αποτελούν αντικείμενο έρευνας δεν έχουν δεχθεί οιαδήποτε πίεση να συμμετάσχουν στην έρευνα και ότι μπορούν ανά πάσα στιγμή και αναπιλοлогіτως να ανακαλέσουν τη συγκατάθεσή τους.

2.2 Προστασία της ιδιωτικότητας

Οι ερευνητές/νήτριες δεσμεύονται να μη δημοσιεύσουν πληροφορίες που αφορούν τον ιδιωτικό βίο των ατόμων στα οποία διενεργήθηκε η έρευνα, εκτός εάν αυτά έχουν δώσει τη συγκατάθεσή τους. Εννοείται ότι σε περίπτωση που οι πληροφορίες που έχουν δοθεί οδηγούν τον/την ερευνητή/νήτρια στο συμπέρασμα ότι υπάρχει κίνδυνος για την ασφάλεια ή τη ζωή του συμμετέχοντος ή άλλων προσώπων, οφείλει στο βαθμό και με τη διαδικασία που ορίζεται διά νόμου και προς αποφυγή επικείμενου κινδύνου, να αποκαλύψει τον εν λόγω κίνδυνο στις αρμόδιες πανεπιστημιακές αρχές. Όταν η έρευνα αφορά μικρό αριθμό προσώπων ή οργανισμών η αναγνώριση των οποίων είναι εύκολη, ο ερευνητής/νήτρια πρέπει να απέχει από τη δημοσίευση πληροφοριών που θα οδηγούσαν στην ταυτοποίησή τους. Τα στοιχεία της έρευνας που μπορεί να οδηγήσουν σε υπόδειξη και αναγνώριση των προσώπων και ειδικότερα αυτά που αφορούν τον ιδιωτικό βίο, δέον να καταστρέφονται μετά από εύλογο χρονικό διάστημα, εκτός εάν η διατήρησή τους είναι απαραίτητη. Για όσο διάστημα διατηρούνται πρέπει να διαφυλάσσεται η εμπιστευτικότητά τους με τη λήψη των κατάλληλων μέτρων και να απαγορεύεται η πρόσβαση σε μη εξουσιοδοτημένα πρόσωπα.

2.3 Υπεύθυνη επεξεργασία και διαχείριση προσωπικών δεδομένων

Οι ερευνητές/νήτριες του Πανεπιστημίου Κύπρου αναλαμβάνουν τη δέσμευση να τηρούν με σχολαστικότητα τη νομοθεσία και τις ορθές πρακτικές που προβλέπονται για τη συλλογή, επεξεργασία, φύλαξη και χρήση προσωπικών δεδομένων. Το Πανεπιστήμιο Κύπρου με κάθε τρόπο είναι αποφασισμένο να διαφυλάξει τα δικαιώματα και τις ελευθερίες όλων εκείνων, των οποίων προσωπικά δεδομένα χρησιμοποιούνται με οιοδήποτε τρόπο σε έρευνες. Η εμπιστευτικότητα και η ασφαλής φύλαξη προσωπικών δεδομένων θα πρέπει να αποτελούν διαρκή μέριμνα των ερευνητών και οι ερευνητές/τριες θα πρέπει να συμμορφώνονται πλήρως με τον Κανονισμό (ΕΕ) 2016/679 του Ευρωπαϊκού Κοινοβουλίου και του Συμβουλίου της 27ης Απριλίου 2016 για την προστασία των φυσικών προσώπων έναντι της επεξεργασίας των δεδομένων προσωπικού χαρακτήρα και την Πολιτική Προστασίας Προσωπικών Δεδομένων του Πανεπιστημίου.

2.4 Πρακτικές και διαχείριση δεδομένων

Οι ερευνητές/τριες οφείλουν να διασφαλίζουν την κατάλληλη διαχείριση και επιμέλεια όλων των δεδομένων και των υλικών έρευνας, συμπεριλαμβανομένων των μη δημοσιευμένων, διατηρώντας τα με ασφάλεια για εύλογο χρονικό διάστημα. Οφείλουν επίσης να διασφαλίζουν ότι οι τρόποι πρόσβασης στα δεδομένα χαρακτηρίζονται από διαφάνεια και ότι η πρόσβαση σε αυτά είναι όσο το δυνατόν πιο ανοικτή, όσο περιορισμένη απαιτείται και, κατά περίπτωση, σύμφωνα με τις αρχές FAIR – Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, ReUsable· δηλαδή, με δυνατότητα ανεύρεσης, πρόσβασης, διαλειτουργικότητας και επαναχρησιμοποίησης για τη διαχείριση δεδομένων.

2.5 Υποχρέωση εμπιστευτικότητας

Οι ερευνητές/νήτριες, καθώς και όλα τα εξουσιοδοτημένα πρόσωπα οφείλουν να μην ανακοινώνουν σε μη εξουσιοδοτημένα πρόσωπα εμπιστευτικές πληροφορίες που περιήλθαν σε αυτούς κατά τη διάρκεια διαπραγματεύσεων νέας ερευνητικής συνεργασίας, καθώς και κατά την εκπόνηση ενός ερευνητικού έργου. Ο περιορισμός αυτός αφορά και όλους τους

εργοδοτούμενους του Πανεπιστημίου Κύπρου οι οποίοι χωρίς να είναι ρητώς εξουσιοδοτημένοι, είναι δυνατόν να έλθουν σε επαφή με τέτοιου είδους εμπιστευτικές πληροφορίες.

Οι ερευνητές/νήτριες, καθώς και όλα τα εξουσιοδοτημένα πρόσωπα οφείλουν να μην ανακοινώνουν σε μη εξουσιοδοτημένα πρόσωπα εμπιστευτικές πληροφορίες που περιήλθαν σε αυτούς κατά τη διάρκεια διαπραγματεύσεων νέας ερευνητικής συνεργασίας, καθώς και κατά την εκπόνηση ενός ερευνητικού έργου. Ο περιορισμός αυτός αφορά και όλους τους εργοδοτούμενους του Πανεπιστημίου Κύπρου οι οποίοι χωρίς να είναι ρητώς εξουσιοδοτημένοι, είναι δυνατόν να έλθουν σε επαφή με τέτοιου είδους εμπιστευτικές πληροφορίες. Ο όρος εμπιστευτικές πληροφορίες, για σκοπούς έρευνας, αφορά πληροφορίες που παρέχονται προφορικά, εγγράφως, ηλεκτρονικά ή με οποιοδήποτε άλλον τρόπο και που περιλαμβάνουν ενδεικτικά αλλά όχι περιοριστικά, τεχνικές και μη τεχνικές πληροφορίες, που αφορούν ευρεσιτεχνίες, θέματα διανοητικής και πνευματικής ιδιοκτησίας, εμπορικά σήματα και σχέδια, αναλύσεις, μελέτες, δεδομένα, πληροφορίες χαρακτηρισμένες ως ιδιόκτητες, τεχνογνωσία, διαδικασίες, λογισμικό.

Δεν περιλαμβάνονται πληροφορίες (α) που κατά τον χρόνο της αποκάλυψης είναι ευρέως διαθέσιμες στο κοινό, εκτός από τις περιπτώσεις που η αποκάλυψη έχει γίνει από τον Παραλήπτη, ή (β) που ο Παραλήπτης έχει λάβει από ανεξάρτητες πηγές ελεύθερες από οποιαδήποτε υποχρέωση εμπιστευτικότητας, ή (γ) που επιβάλλεται να αποκαλυφθούν λόγω δημοσίου συμφέροντος βάσει νόμου ή δικαστικής διαδικασίας.

2.6 Προστασία διανοητικής ιδιοκτησίας

Το Πανεπιστήμιο Κύπρου και οι ερευνητές/νήτριες οφείλουν να τηρούν τη νομοθεσία για την προστασία της διανοητικής ιδιοκτησίας. Ειδικότερα, το καθεστώς απόδοσης και διαχείρισης της διανοητικής ιδιοκτησίας και συγγενών δικαιωμάτων σε σχέση με τα αποτελέσματα της έρευνας πρέπει να είναι εκ των προτέρων σαφώς προσδιορισμένο, έτσι ώστε να είναι σαφές ποιος/ποια ή ποιοι/ποιοι είναι οι εκάστοτε δικαιούχοι. Οι ερευνητές/νήτριες θα πρέπει να καθοδηγούνται σχετικά από την Πολιτική Διανοητικής Ιδιοκτησίας του Πανεπιστημίου και να διασφαλίζουν ότι τυχόν συμβάσεις ή συμφωνίες που σχετίζονται με ερευνητικά αποτελέσματα περιλαμβάνουν ισότιμες και δίκαιες διατάξεις για τη διαχείριση της χρήσης, της κυριότητας και/ή της προστασίας των εν λόγω αποτελεσμάτων βάσει δικαιωμάτων πνευματικής ιδιοκτησίας.

2.7 Διάχυση της γνώσης

Οι ερευνητές/νήτριες οφείλουν να διασφαλίζουν ότι το έργο τους καθίσταται διαθέσιμο σε συναδέλφους με έγκαιρο, ανοικτό, διαφανή και ακριβή τρόπο, εκτός εάν έχει συμφωνηθεί διαφορετικά, και να είναι ειλικρινείς κατά τη γνωστοποίησή του στο ευρύ κοινό, καθώς και σε παραδοσιακά μέσα ενημέρωσης και σε μέσα κοινωνικής δικτύωσης. Οφείλουν επίσης να αναγνωρίζουν, με ενδεδειγμένο τρόπο το Πανεπιστήμιο Κύπρου, καθώς και το σημαντικό έργο και την πνευματική συμβολή τρίτων, οι οποίοι επηρέασαν την κοινοποιούμενη έρευνα, συμπεριλαμβανομένων συνεργατών, συμμετεχόντων, βοηθών και χρηματοδοτών.

2.8 Αποφυγή σύγκρουσης συμφερόντων

Τα μέλη του Πανεπιστημίου και συγκεκριμένα οι ερευνητές/νήτριες δεσμεύονται ότι κατά τη διεξαγωγή της έρευνάς τους θα εντοπίζουν και θα αποφεύγουν καταστάσεις, δραστηριότητες και ενέργειες που συνιστούν σύγκρουση συμφερόντων. Ακόμη περισσότερο, οι ερευνητές/νήτριες θα πρέπει να καταβάλουν κάθε δυνατή προσπάθεια να εντοπίζουν και να διαχειρίζονται κατάλληλα σχέσεις και επιλογές που θα μπορούσαν να καταλήξουν σε σύγκρουση συμφερόντων.

2.9 Συλλογική έρευνα

Οι ερευνητές/νήτριες έχουν υποχρέωση αμοιβαίου σεβασμού και δικαίωμα ίσης μεταχείρισης. Όλοι οι εταίροι σε ερευνητικές συνεργασίες αναλαμβάνουν ευθύνη για την ακεραιότητα της έρευνας και συμφωνούν εξ αρχής σχετικά με τους στόχους της έρευνας και τη διαδικασία κοινοποίησης των πορισμάτων της έρευνας με όσο το δυνατόν πιο διαφανή και ανοικτό τρόπο. Συμφωνούν επίσης, κατά την έναρξη της συνεργασίας τους, σχετικά με τις προσδοκίες τους και τα πρότυπα ακεραιότητας της έρευνας, τις εφαρμοστέες νομοθετικές και κανονιστικές διατάξεις, την προστασία των δικαιωμάτων πνευματικής ιδιοκτησίας των συνεργατών και τις διαδικασίες χειρισμού συγκρούσεων και ενδεχόμενων περιπτώσεων παραπτώματων.

2.10 Τήρηση κανόνων ασφαλείας

Οι ερευνητές/νήτριες του Π.Κ. οφείλουν να εφαρμόζουν όλους τους αναγνωρισμένους στο οικείο επιστημονικό πεδίο κανόνες ασφαλείας, καθώς και όσους ορίζονται ειδικά από το Π.Κ (βλ. ιστοσελίδα Π.Κ [«Ασφάλεια και υγεία στην εργασία»](#)). Σε περίπτωση που η ορθή τήρηση κανονισμών ασφαλείας εξαρτάται από θέματα υποδομών/εξοπλισμού ενημερώνουν τους αρμοδίους, ώστε να ληφθούν άμεσα τα απαραίτητα μέτρα. Οι ερευνητές/τριες δεσμεύονται να καταγράφουν ανά χρονικά διαστήματα που κρίνουν αναγκαίο, προβλήματα που αντιμετωπίζουν ή πιστεύουν πως πρόκειται να αντιμετωπίσουν σε σχέση με την ασφάλεια και να τα αποστέλλουν γραπτώς στις αρμόδιες υπηρεσίες του Π.Κ. για την έγκαιρη αντιμετώπιση ή/και πρόληψή τους.

3. Ειδικά Αντικείμενα έρευνας

3.1 Έρευνα με αντικείμενο τον άνθρωπο-Βιοηθική

Όσοι διενεργούν έρευνα σε ανθρώπους πρέπει να είναι ενήμεροι για τις αρχές ηθικής και τους ειδικότερους κανόνες δεοντολογίας που διέπουν το αντικείμενό τους. Ειδικά, κάθε έρευνα που περιλαμβάνει ανθρώπους πρέπει να διεξάγεται σύμφωνα με τις θεμελιώδεις βιοηθικές αρχές της αυτονομίας των προσώπων, της ωφέλειας, της μη βλάβης και της δικαιοσύνης.

3.2 Έρευνα με αντικείμενο πτώμα

Όσοι διενεργούν έρευνα σε πτώματα, οφείλουν να το πράττουν με βάση τις αρχές που διατυπώνονται στο 3.1 και αφού έχουν λάβει γραπτώς τη συγκατάθεση των οικείων και νομίμως υπεύθυνων προσώπων.

3.3 Έρευνα με αντικείμενο τα ζώα

Η έρευνα σε ζώα εργαστηρίου πρέπει να διενεργείται μόνον εφόσον δεν υπάρχει εναλλακτικός τρόπος έρευνας, στον απολύτως αναγκαίο αριθμό ζώων και με ιδιαίτερη μέριμνα των ερευνητών να αποφεύγονται η άσκοπη ταλαιπωρία και ο πόνος. Η μεταχείριση των ζώων υπόκειται στους κανόνες της ορθής ερευνητικής πρακτικής και τις προβλέψεις της κείμενης νομοθεσίας.

3.4 Έρευνα σχετικά με το φυσικό, οικιστικό και πολιτιστικό περιβάλλον

Καμία έρευνα δεν δικαιολογεί προσβολή του φυσικού περιβάλλοντος κατά παραβίαση των ηθικών/ δεοντολογικών κανόνων και των ισχυόντων νόμων για την προστασία του, καθώς και για τη διαχείριση των αποβλήτων. Κάθε έρευνα οφείλει να διεξάγεται με βάση την αρχή της περιβαλλοντικής ευθύνης και να ενισχύει την ανάπτυξη περιβαλλοντικά φιλικών

τεχνολογιών. Καμία έρευνα δεν δικαιολογεί προσβολή του πολιτιστικού περιβάλλοντος, όπως αυτό προστατεύεται από δεοντολογικούς κανόνες και την κείμενη νομοθεσία.

Πηγές

- [Ευρωπαϊκός Κώδικας Δεοντολογίας](#) για την ακεραιότητα στην έρευνα
- [Εθνική Επιτροπή Βιοηθικής](#)- Νομοθεσία
- [Κώδικας Δεοντολογίας στην Έρευνα](#)-Αριστοτέλειο Πανεπιστήμιο Θεσσαλονίκης
- [Κώδικας Ηθικής και Δεοντολογίας της Έρευνας](#)-Πανεπιστήμιο Κρήτης
- [Δήλωση εμπιστευτικότητας](#)- Βουλή των Ελλήνων
- [Research Ethics Policy](#)-Faculty of Law, University of Cambridge
- [Policy on the ethics of research involving Human Participants and Personal Data](#)- University of Cambridge
- [Academic integrity in research. Code of Practice and Procedure](#) - University of Oxford
- [Ethical Code of Behavior](#)-University of Bologna
- [Cornel code of academic integrity](#)- Cornell University
- [General Principles on the ethical conduct of research and scholarship](#)- University of Illinois
- [Research ethics policy](#)- University of Tasmania
- [Ethical Principles of Psychologists and Code of Ethics](#)-American Psychological Association

Εγκρίθηκε κατά τη συνεδρία της Συγκλήτου αρ. 19/2019, ημερ. 03/07/2019 και επικυρώθηκε κατά τη συνεδρία της Επιτροπής Προσωπικού και Κανονισμών αρ. 11/2019, ημερ. 30/7/2019.

ΠΟΛΙΤΙΚΗ ΑΣΦΑΛΕΙΑΣ ΠΛΗΡΟΦΟΡΙΩΝ

ΕΚΔΟΣΗ:	1.0
ΥΠΕΥΘΥΝΟΣ:	Γρηγόρης Μιχαήλ, Υπεύθυνος Πληροφορικής Ασφάλειας
ΣΥΝΤΑΧΤΗΚΕ ΑΠΟ:	ΚΟΥΣΙΟΣ ΚΟΡΦΩΤΗΣ ΠΑΠΑΧΑΡΑΛΑΜΠΟΥΣ Δ.Ε.Π.Ε.
ΕΓΚΡΙΘΗΚΕ ΑΠΟ:	
ΗΜΕΡΟΜΗΝΙΑ ΕΓΚΡΙΣΗΣ:	

Πολιτική ασφάλειας πληροφοριών

Ο Οργανισμός έχει καθιερώσει πολιτική ασφάλειας πληροφοριών συνυφασμένη με την πολιτική προστασίας προσωπικών δεδομένων στη βάση νομοθετικών, κανονιστικών και άλλων συμβατικών απαιτήσεων ώστε να διασφαλίζει:

- Το απόρρητο, την ακεραιότητα, τη διαθεσιμότητα και την αξιοπιστία των συστημάτων πληροφορικής, άλλων φορέων πληροφοριών και άλλων υπηρεσιών που χρησιμοποιούνται για επεξεργασία των προσωπικών δεδομένων των εθελοντών στη Βιοτράπεζα και των εργαζομένων σε συνεχή βάση.
- Την δυνατότητα αποκατάστασης της διαθεσιμότητας και της πρόσβασης σε δεδομένα προσωπικού χαρακτήρα σε εύθετο χρόνο σε περίπτωση φυσικού ή τεχνικού συμβάντος.
- Τη διαχείριση περιστατικών ασφαλείας συμπεριλαμβανομένων παραβιάσεων προσωπικών δεδομένων και μείωση των εγγενών κινδύνων και βλαβών σε φυσικά πρόσωπα (υποκείμενα των δεδομένων) και την ανάκτηση, όπου είναι εφικτό, των δεδομένων και πληροφοριών του Κέντρου
- Την τακτική δοκιμή, εκτίμηση και αξιολόγηση της αποτελεσματικότητας των τεχνικών και των οργανωτικών μέτρων που λαμβάνει ο Οργανισμός όπως επίσης και οι εκτελούντες την Επεξεργασία (συνεργάτες) για τη διασφάλιση της ασφάλειας της επεξεργασίας στη βάση κατάλληλων εκτιμήσεων κινδύνων και τρωτότητας.

Η πολιτική αυτή εφαρμόζεται σε όλα τα συστήματα και στοιχεία πληροφοριών συμπεριλαμβανομένου του εξοπλισμού πληροφορικής, δικτυακό εξοπλισμό και τηλεπικοινωνιακό εξοπλισμό όπως και εξοπλισμό επεξεργασίας φυσικών αρχείων σε έντυπη μορφή, δηλαδή φωτοτυπικών μηχανών, shredders, συσκευές φαξ, συστήματα αρχειοθέτησης, χρηματοκιβώτια κ.λπ., που ανήκουν ή λειτουργούν στις εγκαταστάσεις του Οργανισμού. Η πολιτική ή μέρος αυτής εφαρμόζεται και από τους εκτελούντες την επεξεργασία για λογαριασμό του Οργανισμού, όπως περιγράφεται σε ρήτρα προστασίας δεδομένων ως μέρος των συμβάσεων με εκτελούντες την επεξεργασία.

Το σύστημα προστασίας προσωπικών δεδομένων του Οργανισμού έχει αναπτυχθεί στη βάση των πιο κάτω αρχών:

- Προστασία του Οργανισμού από ευθύνη ή ζημιά μέσω της κατάχρησης των συστημάτων πληροφορικής. Είναι ευθύνη όλου του προσωπικού να έχουν κατά νου την ανάγκη για ασφάλεια των δεδομένων σε ολόκληρο τον Οργανισμό και να γνωρίζουν και να συμμορφώνονται με την πολιτική αυτή και όλες τις τρέχουσες και σχετικές νομοθεσίες.
- Οι πληροφορίες πρέπει να είναι ασφαλείς και να διατίθενται αποκλειστικά σε όσους έχουν μια εξουσιοδότηση για την πρόσβαση (ανάγκη γνώσης) και την επεξεργασία σύμφωνα με τα καθήκοντα και τις ευθύνες τους στο πλαίσιο του Κανονισμού. Η πρόσβαση και η εξουσιοδότηση επεξεργασίας παρέχονται σύμφωνα με το επίπεδο διαβάθμισης των πληροφοριών.
- Όλες οι πληροφορίες διαβαθμίζονται σύμφωνα με το επίπεδο του κινδύνου. Είναι ευθύνη όλου του προσωπικού που έχουν πρόσβαση σε δεδομένα να τα χειρίζονται κατάλληλα στη βάση της διαβάθμισης.
- Πρέπει ανά πάσα στιγμή να διασφαλίζεται η ορθότητα (Ακεραιότητα) των πληροφοριών.
- Οι πληροφορίες να προστατεύονται πάντα από μη εξουσιοδοτημένη πρόσβαση.
- Κάθε παραβίαση της ασφάλειας θα διερευνάται και εάν εμπίπτει στον ορισμό παραβίασης προσωπικών δεδομένων θα εφαρμόζεται το σχέδιο ανταπόκρισης σε παραβιάσεις δεδομένων σύμφωνα με το άρθρο 33 του ΓΚΠΔ.

- Μια ευέλικτη και αποτελεσματική οργάνωση προστασίας δεδομένων με συμμετοχή προσωπικού και εξωτερικών ειδικών με καθορισμό καθηκόντων και αρμοδιοτήτων για την προστασία των δεδομένων, καθώς επίσης και για καθορισμό των αναγκών για ενημέρωση, εκπαίδευση και κατάρτιση του προσωπικού και άλλων συμμετόχων.
- Συνεχής προσπάθεια για αλλαγή κουλτούρας απέναντι στην προστασία των δεδομένων του Οργανισμού μέσα από την ατομική και συλλογική αξιολόγηση των κινδύνων.
- Διατήρηση αποτελεσματικών μηχανισμών επιχειρησιακής συνέχειας και δοκιμές σε τακτά διαστήματα ώστε να διασφαλίζεται η ανθεκτικότητα του Οργανισμού σε καταστροφικά γεγονότα.

Ο Οργανισμός αναμένει την μέγιστη συμμόρφωση στην παρούσα πολιτική από το προσωπικό και τους συνεργάτες προμηθευτές (εκτελούντες την επεξεργασία) και φροντίζει ώστε μέσα από ρήτρες εμπιστευτικότητας και συμβάσεις αντίστοιχα, το προσωπικό και οι προμηθευτές να υποστηρίξουν το σύστημα προστασίας πληροφοριών του Οργανισμού. Τυχόν παραβίαση της παρούσας πολιτικής ενδέχεται να επιφέρει στον Οργανισμό νομικές ή άλλες ευθύνες και ως εκ τούτου δεσμευόμαστε όπως διερευνούμε το κάθε περιστατικό παραβίασης της παρούσας πολιτικής και την λήψη διορθωτικών μέτρων συμπεριλαμβανομένων και πειθαρχικών ή ποινικών μέτρων εκεί που απαιτείται ώστε να διαφυλάξουμε τα νόμιμα συμφέροντα και την δημόσια εικόνα του Οργανισμού.

Material/Data Transfer Agreement

DRAFT

1 Parties

This Material/Data Transfer Agreement (hereinafter referred to as the “MTA/DTA”) is concluded by and between:

- (1) The University of Cyprus, with its registered offices at University Avenue 1, Nicosia 2109, Cyprus, herein represented by **TITLE, NAME** acting on its behalf and on behalf of the (**Laboratory name and/or Department**), herein represented by (name, title/position) (hereinafter “*Provider*”)
- (2) (**Name of Organisation**), formed under the laws of (**law Title, where exists**) of (**City, District, Country**), with its registered offices at (**organisation address**), herein represented by (**name of Legal Representative, title/position**), acting on its behalf and on behalf of the (**Department**), herein represented by (Title, **name**) (hereinafter “*Recipient*”).

2 Definitions

- 1.1. “*Original Material/Data*” means “**Click here to enter text.**”, as described in ANNEX 1, portions or Progeny thereof. ANNEX1 constitutes an integral part of this MTA/DTA.
- 1.2. “*Provider*” means the legal entity as defined above.
- 1.3. “*Providing Scientist*” means the scientific employee of *Provider* that supplies the “*Original Material/Data*” to the *Recipient*.
- 1.4. “*Recipient*” means the legal entity as defined above.
- 1.5. “*Recipient Scientist*” means the scientist in charge and/or scientific employee of *Recipient* performing the intended experiments/analysis with *Material/Data* as identified in ANNEX 1.
- 1.6. “*Progeny*” means unmodified descendant from the “*Original Material/Data*”, such as cell from cell.
- 1.7. “*Unmodified derivatives*” means substances and other materials/products/data created by the *Recipient* which constitute an unmodified functional subunit or product of the “*Original Material/Data*”.
- 1.8. “*Modifications*” means substances, other materials, or processed data created by the *Recipient* which contain/incorporate the “*Original Material/Data*”.

- 1.9. “*Proprietary information*” means any information, data and know-how relating to the *Original Material/Data* which may include but not limited to information on its use, handling and reproduction, as described in ANNEX 1.
- 1.10. “*Material/Data*” means *Original Material/Data, Unmodified Derivatives, Original Material/Data* contained in *Modifications and Proprietary Information*.

3 Supply of the *Material/Data*

- 2.1. *Provider* will deliver to Recipient the Original *Material/Data* and Proprietary Information which *Provider* considers appropriate. The Original *Material/Data* and Proprietary Information are and remain the exclusive property of the *Provider*. Subject to the terms and conditions of this MTA/DTA, *Provider* hereby grants Recipient a non-exclusive, royalty-free license to use the *Material/Data* as described in ANNEX 1.
- 2.2. The *Original Material/Data* is provided for a fee, which will be determined based on nature and amount of material and data to be provided. Under certain circumstances on a case-by-case basis, the material and/or data may be provided cost-free; Also, a handling fee may be charged for its collection, preparation and shipment to the Recipient. As applicable, both items are specified in ANNEX 1. Upon receiving the payment, the Original *Material/Data* shall be shipped to Recipient. Recipient and *Provider* agree that no further payments shall be required unless Recipient chooses to license the *Material/Data* from *Provider*, as may be necessary under paragraph 5.2. below.
- 2.3. The *Original Material/Data* provided to the Recipient Scientist pursuant this MTA/DTA and Unmodified Derivatives thereof will be maintained within the sole possession and control of the Recipient Scientist and staff under his or her direct supervision who are bound by obligations not less strict than those set out herein and must not be released to any person other than the Recipient Scientist.

4 Use of the *Material/Data*

- 3.1. The *Material/Data* shall be handled confidentially by the Recipient and treated as the valuable, confidential and proprietary information of the *Provider*. *Provider* understands and agrees that, for the performance of Recipient’s intended experiments as described in ANNEX 1, the Recipient shall not disclose the *Material/Data*, in whole or in part, to any other third party unless authorized in writing by the *Provider*.

- 3.2. The *Recipient* will not transfer the *Material/Data* to any third party and will direct any third-party requests to the *Provider*. The *Provider* will retain such unrestricted right to distribute the *Material/Data* to other academic, research, commercial or non-commercial entities.
- 3.3. The *Recipient* shall use the *Material/Data* in compliance with all laws and regulations applicable to such *Material/Data* in the *Recipient's* place and country, including regulations and guidelines for work with recombinant DNA. The *Material/Data* being experimental in nature must not be used in therapy involving humans or animals, in clinical trials or for diagnostic purposes involving human subjects, unless otherwise specified in this agreement.
- 3.4. The *Material/Data* shall be used for experimental, research and/or educational purposes only, as described in ANNEX 1. Accordingly, and without limitation, *Recipient* is not allowed to use the *Material/Data* for any commercial purpose or for the direct benefit of any commercial entity or use the *Material/Data* for the production of products for any commercial purpose or for the direct benefit of any commercial entity without prior informing the provider.
- 3.5. Upon request, the *Recipient* shall inform the *Provider* on the status of its research.

5 Publications

- 4.1. Any publication of *Recipient Scientist* based on the *Original Material/Data, Proprietary Information, Unmodified derivatives* or *Modifications* thereof shall co-author *Providing* and *Recipient Scientists* and/or any other *Provider* and/or *Recipient* researcher(s) according to common scientific practices based on their actual contribution to the publication. Should co-authorship be not permitted on specific Journals with restrictive authorship criteria, a sufficient acknowledgment of *Provider's* contribution is required. Any verbal communication, be it at a conference, academic lecture or other public presentation referring to the *Material/Data* shall acknowledge the *Provider* as source of the *Original Material/Data*.
- 4.2. The *Recipient Scientist* shall submit to the *Providing Scientist* any publication related to the *Material/Data* two (2) weeks prior to submitting the publication to a third party, and shall act in accordance to Article 5.3 of this *MTA/DTA*. *Provider* agrees to keep the *Recipient's* publication confidential until published by *Recipient*. Noted that in case the co-authorship criteria above are met the *Providing Scientists* should be given a period of sixty (60) days prior to the publication to respond.

6 Intellectual Property

- 5.1. *Recipient* agrees not to file for any intellectual property protection for *Original Material/Data* and/or *Proprietary Information*.
- 5.2. *Recipient* acquires no rights under any patents nor any rights to use any products or processes derived from or including *Material/Data* for profit-making or commercial purposes. *Recipient* agrees to negotiate in good faith a license with the *Provider* before making any profit-making or commercial use of any product or process derived from or including the *Material/Data*. The *Provider* has no obligation to grant a license to the *Recipient*, and may grant exclusive or non-exclusive licenses to others who may be investigating uses of the *Material/Data*.
- 5.3. When the research involving any and all part of the *Material/Data* results in an invention or a patentable *Modification* of the *Material/Data*, the *Recipient* shall promptly disclose this development to the *Provider*. *Recipient* and *Provider* shall decide in common and negotiate in good faith about the inventorship, taking in due consideration the *Provider's* contribution to the invention through its *Material/Data* and any potential essential scientific contribution per academic standards and any applicable laws and regulations relating to inventorship. Decisions about all further proceedings, such as filing for a patent application or exploitation, shall be made after inventorship or any actual contribution thereof, is determined.
- 5.4. At *Provider's* request, *Recipient* agrees to return generated results and data to the *Provider* once the recipient's research/analysis is published or concluded. Such transfer shall be free of charge, but an appropriate handling/shipping fee may be charged by *Recipient*.

7 Warranty and liability

- 6.1. Any *Material/Data* provided pursuant to this *MTA/DTA* is understood to be experimental in nature. To the extent allowable under applicable laws, *Provider* makes no representations and extends no warranties of any kind, express or implied, including but not limited to warranties of the quality, merchantability and fitness for a particular purpose. *Provider* makes no representation that the use of the *Material/Data* will not infringe any patent or other proprietary rights of a third party. *Provider* also warrants that it has obtained all necessary patient consents and regulatory ethical approvals connected to the *Material/Data*.
- 6.2. Any materials developed, made or discovered in the course of *Recipient* research studies using the *Material/Data*, is provided to the *Provider* "as is". The *Recipient* makes no representations and extends no warranties of any kind, express or implied, including but not limited to warranties of merchantability and fitness for a particular

purpose. *Recipient* makes no representation that the use of the materials developed, made or discovered in the course of *Recipient* research studies will not infringe any patent or other proprietary rights of a third party.

- 6.3. *Recipient* assumes all and any liability for *Recipient's* acceptance, use, storage or disposal of the *Material/Data*. *Recipient* shall hold harmless, defend and indemnify, the *Provider* (including any agent or representative) from any loss, claim, damage, demand or liability, of whatsoever kind or nature (including but not limited to legal expenses), which could be raised by the *Recipient*, or made against the *Recipient* by any other party, due to, or arising from, the acceptance, use, storage or disposal of the *Material/Data* by the *Recipient*. Without limiting the foregoing, *Provider* makes no representation as to testing of the *Material* for the presence or absence of any pathogens, and *Recipient* and *Recipient Scientist* assume all risk of harm with respect to any such pathogens.

8 Miscellaneous

- 7.1. The parties shall use all endeavours to solve any dispute that might arise in connection to this *MTA/DTA* by mutual arrangement. Any unresolved dispute relating to this *MTA/DTA* shall be exclusively settled under the governing law of the defending party.
- 7.2. This *MTA /DTA* shall enter into force on ("*Effective Date*"). It expires after five (5) years or after the conclusion of the experiments according to ANNEX 1, whichever occurs first. Either party may terminate this *MTA/DTA* at any time. *Recipient* will discontinue all use of and return or destroy, subject to the Providers advice, the *Original Material/Data* and related information within thirty (30) days of termination. In case the *Material/Data* are decided to be returned to the Provider, any shipping and/or insurance costs will be bourn by the latter.
- 7.3. In the event the *Material/Data* or part of it should be under physical control of the *Recipient* before this *MTA/DTA* is signed, the terms and provisions shall apply for this *Material/Data* retroactively.
- 7.4. Paragraphs 4, 5 and 6 will survive the termination or expiration of this *MTA/DTA*, which may be amended only by a written and fully-signed subsequent agreement between the parties.
- 7.5. The representatives hereby expressly certify that they are authorized to sign this *MTA/DTA* on behalf of their respective institution.

9 Signatures

At Nicosia

Signed for and on behalf of the *Provider* by its duly authorized representative and *Providing Scientist*

Provider

Provider's Scientist

Title & Name

Title & Name

Signature

Date

At (City)

Signed for and on behalf of the *Recipient* by its duly authorized representative and *Recipient Scientist*

Recipient

Recipient Scientist

Title & Name

Title & Name

Signature

Date

ANNEX 1

It is hereby acknowledged that the Department/Laboratory of [Click here to enter text.](#) of the *Provider* will supply *Recipient* with the following *Original Material/Data* and *Proprietary Information* which resulted from research at *Provider* or collaborative laboratories.

1. *Providing Scientist's name, full address, telephone number and e-mail:*

Professor Name
University of Cyprus
Department of [Click here to enter text.](#)
P.O. Box 20537
1678 Nicosia
Cyprus
Phone : [Click here to enter text.](#)
Email : [Click here to enter text.](#)

2. *Address to send the Original Material/Data:*

Professor Name
Department of [Click here to enter text.](#)
(Address)
Phone: [Click here to enter text.](#)
GSM : [Click here to enter text.](#)
Fax: [Click here to enter text.](#)
Email: [Click here to enter text.](#)

3. *Description of the Original Material/Data and Proprietary Information:*

4. *Description of the intended experiments:*

5. *Preparation fee:*

If applicable

6. *Shipping fee:*

If applicable, cost of shipment by express mail to be paid by *Recipient*.

<p>CONSENT FORMS for participation in a research program (The form consists of 8 pages in total)</p>
<p>Title of the program in which you are invited to participate</p>
<p>Biobank of the University of Cyprus Biobanking and the Cyprus Human Genome Project – CY-Biobank</p>

This document provides explanations in plain and clear language regarding what you will be requested to do and/or what may happen to you, if you agree to participate in the program:

1. Any risks that may exist or any inconvenience you may incur from participating in the program.
2. Detailed explanations are provided regarding who will have access to your data and to the data obtained from the program you are participating in, and/or any other material/data that you will be asked to voluntarily provide for the program.
3. The time period during which the program supervisors will have access to the information and/or material about you is specified.
4. Explanations are provided regarding what the program supervisors hope to learn from the program as a result of your participation.
5. An estimate of the benefit the investigators and/or sponsors of this program may have as a result of this program is provided.
6. **You should not participate if you do not wish to do so or if you have any doubts regarding your participation in the program.**
7. If you decide to participate, you must indicate whether you have participated in any other research program within the last 12 months.
8. If you decide not to participate and you are a patient, your treatment will not be affected by your decision.
9. **You are free to withdraw your consent for participation in the program at any time you wish.**
10. If you are a patient, your decision to withdraw your consent will not affect your treatment in any way.
11. All pages of the consent forms must bear your full name and signature.

Principal Investigator of the Program in which you are asked to participate
<p>Professor Constantinos Deltas University of Cyprus Medical School Director, Center of Excellence – Biobanking and Biomedical Research University of Cyprus</p>

Last name:		First name:	
Signature:		Date:	

<p>CONSENT FORMS for participation in a research program (The form consists of 8 pages in total)</p>
<p>Title of the program in which you are invited to participate</p>
<p>Biobank of the University of Cyprus Biobanking and the Cyprus Human Genome Project – CY-Biobank</p>

<p>Duration of the program:</p>
<p>The Biobank has operational approval by the Cyprus National Bioethics Committee (CNBC) until 2036. After that, an approval renewal will be requested.</p>

<p>Are you providing consent for yourself or someone else?</p>	
<p>If you are providing consent for someone else give details and his/her name.</p>	

Question	Yes or No
Did you complete the consent forms yourself?	
Within the last 12 months, have you participated in any other research program?	
Did you read and understand the information for patients and/or volunteers?	
Did you have a chance to ask questions and discuss about the program?	
Did you receive satisfactory answers and explanations to your questions?	
Do you understand that you can withdraw from the program at any time you wish?	
Do you understand that, if you withdraw from the program, you will not have to provide any explanation for your decision?	
(For patients) Do you understand that, if you withdraw from the program, there will be no consequences on any treatment you are receiving or may receive in the future?	
Do you agree to participate in the program?	
With which supervisor did you discuss?	

Last name:		First name:	
Signature:		Date:	

CONSENT FORMS
for participation in a research program
(The form consists of 8 pages in total)

Title of the program in which you are invited to participate

Biobank of the University of Cyprus
Biobanking and the Cyprus Human Genome Project – CY-Biobank

Brief description of the program (procedures and purpose).

You are invited to participate as a volunteer to the Biobank of the University of Cyprus and contribute to research programs that will be implemented and are associated with our health.

What is a Biobank? A Biobank is an organized collection of medical records and information that are accompanied by biological material in the form of DNA, serum, plasma, urine and other (e.g. biopsies, hair, nasopharyngeal swab etc.) with the aim to support basic or applied medical research. Biobanks as research infrastructures, promote the discovery of new knowledge to separately help each patient (personalized medicine), with the development of innovative treatments and improved processes of diagnosis and patient management.

The Biobank was created with competitive funding from the Republic of Cyprus and the European Regional Development Fund, through the Cyprus Research Promotion Foundation (Project: *Strategic Infrastructure: NEW INFRASTRUCTURE/STRATEGIC/0308/24*) and was approved by the Cyprus National Bioethics Committee in 2011 (File No: *EEBK/ΕΠ/2011/04*).

According to its official approval, the University of Cyprus Biobank **specializes in kidney and other genetic diseases**.

In 2019, further funding was obtained through competition under the European Horizon 2020 program to expand this research infrastructure as part of the Center of Excellence in Biobanking and Biomedical Research.

Main objectives of the project:

- a. Enhancement of the Biobank in order to support its research capacity by involving as many volunteer donors as possible, both healthy and not.
- b. The study of the Cypriot genome (DNA) in order to discover information that will lead to a deeper understanding of the Cypriot genetic heritage and to enhance studies for better diagnosis, prognosis and prevention of diseases.
- c. The study of specific hereditary diseases, or diseases involving complex genetic and environmental factors, in order to acquire knowledge that will help us discover better medication for the benefit of the general public.

How will the objectives of the program be achieved? Your altruistic involvement is needed, as well as that of thousands of Cypriot volunteer donors, to support research studies. To do this you need to give us access to your medical record and donate blood, and other biological material to be used in research. Your medical record may be the content of your GESY file, together with any other information you may provide to the Biobank. It is specified that access to your medical files will only be possible following your written consent, provided by signing this document.

Any research program implemented must first be approved by the Cyprus National Bioethics Committee. Use of your personal information will be strictly confidential and secure, in accordance with Cyprus law 125(I)/2018) for implementation of the **European Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679**.

Sending Information and Samples Abroad: It is possible that, in the context of research programs, collaborations with researchers in other centers or universities, in Cyprus and abroad, may be undertaken in order to enhance and improve research results. Samples or coded items of your personal file may be sent to researchers abroad in the framework of such collaborations, always with SECURITY, ANONYMITY and confidentiality. By signing this consent form you agree that the Biobank can analyse any biological material provided and use the results of these analyses for the benefit of society and the general public.

As provided by law, the processing controller is the Center of Excellence in Biobanking and Biomedical Research (CY-Biobank) and the University of Cyprus. The responsibility for data protection (Data Protection Officer – DPO) lies with the legal firm KOUSIOS KORFIOTIS PAPACHARALAMBOUS (<https://kkplaw.com/>).

Last name:		First name:	
Signature:		Date:	

CONSENT FORMS
for participation in a research program
(The form consists of 8 pages in total)

Title of the program in which you are invited to participate

Biobank of the University of Cyprus
Biobanking and the Cyprus Human Genome Project – CY-Biobank

Details of what will be asked and/or happen to the program participants.

Registering and participating as a volunteer donor, either as a patient or as a healthy person, is deemed useful for the success of the Biobank goals and the wider project as described above, and does not pose any risk nor will it affect the treatment you are provided or you will be provided by your doctor, if you are a patient.

You will be asked to provide personal information about yourself and your medical history and access to your medical record. You may also be asked to provide recent blood and urine test results. You will then be asked to provide some biological material as described in a different question below.

As part of your participation in the program, you will not suffer further discomfort or undergo a biopsy, if this is not appropriate or you do not wish to. Anything that needs to be done in the context of the investigation will always be discussed with your doctor and will be performed after you have been informed and signed this consent form. The results of the research are likely to have a direct or indirect medical benefit for you, your children, or other relatives. However, it should be made clear that due to the nature of the research, exporting useful results may take many months or years or something useful may never arise for you personally or your family members.

If you agree, and where applicable, you will complete a questionnaire for your personal and family history and undergo a series of specialized examinations and blood tests related to your physical condition and health, such as physical measurements (height, weight, waist hip circumference, etc.), blood pressure measurement and arterial stiffness, grip force, spirometry, retinal image, etc. You will not incur any costs.

The above is only indicative and will be useful for your health, no matter which program you will participate in the future. If you are invited to join the Biobank under a specific research program upon your doctor's invitation, you may only undergo some of the above tests/analyses and additionally undergo some others for which your doctor will decide, **given that the program is approved by the Cyprus National Bioethics Committee**.

Please note that it is your right to accept only part of the tests or analyses required.

The results of haematological & biochemical tests and examinations will be shared with you during your visit to the Biobank by a healthcare professional.

Last name:		First name:	
Signature:		Date:	

<p>CONSENT FORMS for participation in a research program (The form consists of 8 pages in total)</p>
<p>Title of the program in which you are invited to participate</p>
<p>Biobank of the University of Cyprus Biobanking and the Cyprus Human Genome Project – CY-Biobank</p>

<p>Details of the research program funding.</p>
<p>The program is funded as follows:</p> <p>European Union: EUR 15 million (for 7 years, until September 2026) Republic of Cyprus: EUR 15 million University of Cyprus: EUR 8 million</p> <p>Funding from Cypriot sources is for 15 years, until September 2034.</p>

<p>Details of any risks that may exist or any inconvenience that program participants may incur</p>
<p>No discomfort is anticipated, beyond the collection of blood and urine or other biological material. Some people may have a small bruise at the puncture site, which will normally go away in a few days.</p> <p>DNA analysis will be performed with the latest methods for determining the order of the genetic code “letters”, i.e. the nucleotides, which are the molecules making up the DNA. By using these methods, as described in this form, the program allows for the determination of the sequence of the letters of the genome in at least 500 healthy family trios. Understanding the information that lies within the DNA is a difficult and complicated process. As technology advances, by studying the DNA experts are able to uncover useful information regarding your health and other behavioural characteristics, such as your mental health, increased risk for a cardiac condition or cancer etc, as well as genetic factors protecting from some chronic conditions, such as hypertension, diabetes and dementia. For some conditions it might be easier to come to conclusions, whereas for others great effort and discovery of new knowledge are required. Your voluntary participation will contribute towards achieving these noble goals of science and medicine. Your personal results might be ANONYMOUSLY included in local or international databases, along with the results from thousands of other volunteers across the world, for the enhancement of the world effort for combating diseases.</p> <p>As with any database, an extremely small risk of a data breach cannot be completely ruled out. The University of Cyprus implements every available measure to eliminate this danger. The University of Cyprus IT Infrastructure Service, in collaboration with external advisors with expertise in data handling and protection, implements practices and mechanisms that protect against any theft or leak such as: storing data and servers in secure data centers that are under constant visual surveillance, software and virtual machine protection (Firewalls, Intrusion Detection/Prevention Systems), Use of Private Network Address (IP), High Availability Architecture, use of sophisticated passwords, use of antivirus software, and implementation of data center security policies. All of the above measures are the best practices for data security, to ensure data will never be acquired by non-authorised individuals and institutions, without your consent.</p>

Last name:		First name:	
Signature:		Date:	

<p>CONSENT FORMS for participation in a research program (The form consists of 8 pages in total)</p>
<p>Title of the program in which you are invited to participate</p>
<p>Biobank of the University of Cyprus Biobanking and the Cyprus Human Genome Project – CY-Biobank</p>

Details of the information and/or material that will be collected for the program, as well as details of who will have access to this information and/or material, and for how long.

You will be asked for information about your demographics and your overall health, by requesting access to your medical record. From your medical record, data will be extracted about your symptoms, blood and urine tests, genetic or other tests, results and data from ultrasounds or other imaging methods, and generally anything that is considered evidence and gives information about your health. By providing your personal information and biological material, information regarding close relatives might ensue, which will ALWAYS REMAIN CONFIDENTIAL.

You will be asked to provide biological material as follows:

- a. Blood from which DNA and / or RNA, plasma, serum, cells will be isolated
- b. Mouthwash or saliva for isolation of DNA and / or RNA or another biological molecule
- c. Urine or hair or nasopharyngeal swab or other material
- d. Genetic/protein or other material from a biopsy that you may have undergone (or will undergo in the future) for medical reasons, with your consent.

Depending on the goals of the research programs and funding in the upcoming years, your biological samples may be subjected to a series of analyses. This information will be accessible to those directly involved in the research, i.e. doctors, the project coordinator and researchers who sign a confidentiality form. The unlimited future distribution of material and data to other researchers in Cyprus or abroad will be anonymized so that the file and data cannot be linked to you.

In case of any complaint for any reason, please contact:

Marios Demetriades
Head of Research Support Service
University of Cyprus, PO. 20537, 1678 Nicosia
Tel: (+357) 22894287 | Fax: (+357) 22895506
E-mail: demetriades.a.marios@ucy.ac.cy

Access is granted until 2036, as per the Biobank operation approval. An operation approval renewal will then be requested.

Last name:		First name:	
Signature:		Date:	

CONSENT FORMS
for participation in a research program
(The form consists of 8 pages in total)

Title of the program in which you are invited to participate

Biobank of the University of Cyprus
Biobanking and the Cyprus Human Genome Project – CY-Biobank

In case new information that directly affects your health arises, would you like to be notified?

YES <input style="width: 50px; height: 20px;" type="checkbox"/>	NO <input style="width: 50px; height: 20px;" type="checkbox"/>	I CAN NOT DECIDE NOW, PLEASE ASK ME AGAIN IN CASE SUCH A NEED OCCURS <input style="width: 50px; height: 20px;" type="checkbox"/>
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Expected benefit for the participants

If you are healthy, data that may be useful for preventative purposes may emerge. As a result, you will be able to take some measures to protect your health. If you are a patient it is likely that the genetic or other justification for your illness will be found. This may help receive better treatment in the future. This may also extend to your close relatives, such as your children. While it may be possible in the future for researchers or the University of Cyprus to have financial benefits from the use of research results, you will not benefit financially, and you will not incur any financial burden.

Expected benefit for investigators and/or sponsors

There is no financial benefit to researchers or funders unless marketable copyrights arise. The main benefit for researchers is research publications in reputable journals that will give recognition and career advancement.

Details regarding the conditions of termination or premature discontinuation of the research program.

No conditions for termination or early interruption of the program are anticipated.

Details of what data will be obtained with the context of the program, as well as details of who will have access to this data and for how long.

New knowledge will emerge about the aetiology of some of the diseases that you or other people suffer, new information that will help better diagnose or even treat illnesses, knowledge that may help invent new drugs for diseases such as heart diseases, kidney diseases, cancers, etc.

Access will be for as many years as the Biobank operates legally, because it will be very useful as reference data for future research. Persons other than the research team may have access anonymously, in accordance with the approval to be obtained following an application to the CNBC.

Last name:		First name:	
Signature:		Date:	

CONSENT FORMS
for participation in a research program
(The form consists of 8 pages in total)

Title of the program in which you are invited to participate

Biobank of the University of Cyprus
Biobanking and the Cyprus Human Genome Project – CY-Biobank

Description of procedures for handling data and/or biological samples of participants that will withdraw from the study before completion.

In order not to interfere with the credibility of the research results that may be ongoing, and to minimize the loss of scientific benefit, if you decide to withdraw, you will be asked by the project manager if you agree for the Biobank to keep all of your data and biological samples that have been collected up to that point, in full anonymity and disconnected from your identifiable folder.

If you do not agree, the Biobank will delete your personal data and results and destroy the biological samples.

Place where data and/or biological samples that will be obtained within the context of the program will be stored and duration of storage

Your demographic and clinical data will be digitally imported and stored in the REDCap program, which is an approved and secure web application for storing the data before importing it into the Biobank database. The University of Cyprus is licensed to use this application in a secure and controlled environment.

The University of Cyprus has a dedicated suite for the storage of records and samples, which is the Biobank. All biological samples collected will be stored encoded in the Biobank in specially-locked -80°C freezers located in a separate locked room, or by another freezing mechanism.

The key is only accessible to the Coordinator and the person in charge of the Biobank. For the purposes of research and / or analysis of data derived from research programs, coded biological samples and anonymous results will be analysed by partners in Cyprus or abroad. The records and samples will be kept until 2036.

The present approval by the Cyprus National Bioethics Committee for the operation of the Biobank expires in 2036 and an extension will be requested.

Full contact details and position of individual to whom the participants can file a complaint relating to the program he/she is participating in.

Marios Demetriades
Head of Research Support Service
University of Cyprus, PO. 20537, 1678 Nicosia
Tel: (+357) 22894287 | Fax: (+357) 22895506
E-mail: demetriades.a.marios@ucy.ac.cy

Full contact details and position of individual the participants can contact for more information or clarifications regarding the research program

Prof. Constantinos Deltas
University of Cyprus Medical School
Director, Center of Excellence in Biobanking and Biomedical Research (<https://biobank.cy/>)
Panepistimiou 1, 2109, Nicosia
Tel: 22892815 / 22-892882 Email: Deltas@ucy.ac.cy

Last name:		First name:	
Signature:		Date:	

CONSENT FORMS

For the participation of minors in a research programme

(The forms are comprised of pages)

Title of the Programme you are invited to participate

Biobanking and the Cyprus Human Genome Project – CY-Biobank

This form provides the explanations in plain and comprehensible language regarding what is being requested from you and/or what will happen to you if you agree to join the programme:

1. All risks that may exist or any inconvenience you may incur from participating in the programme.
2. The person(s) who will have access to your information and will arise from the programme you will take part in and/or other material/data that you voluntarily provide for the programme.
3. The time period during which the principal investigator will have access to your information and/or material concerning you.
4. What the principal investigator hope to learn as a result of your participation.
5. Estimation of the benefit that can be gained for researchers and/or sponsors of this programme.
6. **You should not participate if you do not wish to, or if you have any concerns about your participation in the programme.**
7. If you decide to join, you must indicate if you have participated in any other research programmes within the last 12 months.
8. If you decide not to participate and you are a patient, your treatment will not be affected by your decision.
9. **You are free to withdraw your consent to participating in the programme at any time.**
10. If you are a patient, your decision to withdraw your consent will not have any effect on your treatment.
11. All pages of consent forms must bear your full name and signature.

Principal Investigator of the Programme you are invited to participate in

**Professor Constantinos Deltas
University of Cyprus Medical School
Director, Center of Excellence – Biobanking and Biomedical Research
University of Cyprus**

Father:

Surname:		Name:	
Signature:		Date:	

Mother:

Surname:		Name:	
Signature:		Date:	

Legal Guardian:

Surname:		Name:	
Signature:		Date:	

Participant:

Surname:		Name:	
Signature:		Date:	

(Form EEBK03-1)

CONSENT FORMS
For the participation of minors in a research programme
(The forms are comprised of pages)
Title of the Programme you are invited to participate
Biobanking and the Cyprus Human Genome Project – CY-Biobank

Programme Duration:
15 years.

Do you give consent for yourself or for someone else?	
If you have responded for another person, please provide details and name.	

Question	YES or NO
Did you fill in your consent forms personally?	
Over the past 12 months, have you been involved in any other research programme?	
Did you read and understand the information regarding patients and/or volunteers?	
Have you had the opportunity to ask questions and discuss the Programme?	
Have you been given satisfactory answers and explanations to any of your questions?	
Do you understand that you can withdraw from the programme whenever you wish?	
Do you understand that if you withdraw, you do not need to give any explanations for your decision?	
(For patients) do you understand that, if you withdraw, there will be no impact on any treatment you get or you can get in the future?	
Do you agree to join the programme?	
With whom did you speak with?	

Father:

Surname:		Name:	
Signature:		Date:	

Mother:

Surname:		Name:	
Signature:		Date:	

Legal Guardian:

Surname:		Name:	
Signature:		Date:	

Participant:

Surname:		Name:	
Signature:		Date:	

(Form EEBK03-1)

CONSENT FORMS

For the participation of minors in a research programme

(The forms are comprised of pages)

Title of the Programme you are invited to participate

Biobanking and the Cyprus Human Genome Project – CY-Biobank

Brief description of the programme (procedures and purpose).

You are invited to participate as a volunteer to the Biobank of University of Cyprus and contribute to research programmes that will be implemented and are associated with your health.

What is a Biobank? A Biobank is an organized collection of medical records and information that are accompanied by biological material in the form of DNA, serum, plasma, urine and other (e.g. biopsies, hair, nasopharyngeal swab etc.) with the aim to support basic or applied medical research. Biobanks as research infrastructures, promote the discovery of new knowledge to separately help each patient (personalized medicine), with the development of innovative treatments and improved processes of diagnosis and patient management.

The Biobank was approved by the National Bioethics Committee of Cyprus in 2011 (File No: EEBK / EP / 2011/04), through competitive funding from the Republic of Cyprus and the European Regional Development Fund, through the Research Infrastructure Foundation (Project: Strategic Infrastructure: NEW INFRASTRUCTURE / STRATEGIC / 0308/24).

According to its official approval, the University of Cyprus Biobank **specializes in kidney and other genetic diseases.**

In 2019, further funding was obtained through competition under the European Horizon 2020 program to expand this research infrastructure as a Center of Excellence in the field of Biobanking and Biomedical Research.

Main objectives of the project:

- a. Enhancement of the Biobank in order to support its research capacity by involving as many volunteer donors as possible, both healthy and not.
- b. The study of the Cypriot genome (DNA) in order to discover information that will lead to a deeper understanding of the Cypriot genetic heritage and to enhance studies for better diagnosis, prognosis and prevention of diseases.
- c. The study of specific hereditary diseases, or diseases involving complex genetic and environmental factors, in order to acquire knowledge that will help us discover better medication for the benefit of the general public.

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Participant:

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(Form EEBK03-1)

CONSENT FORMS

For the participation of minors in a research programme

(The forms are comprised of pages)

Title of the Programme you are invited to participate

Biobanking and the Cyprus Human Genome Project – CY-Biobank

How will the objectives of the program be achieved? Your altruistic involvement is needed, as well as that of thousands of Cypriot volunteer donors, to support research studies. To do this you need to give us access to your medical file and donate blood, and other biological material to be used in research. Your medical file may be the content of your GESY file, together with any other information you may provide to the Biobank. It is specified that access to your medical files will only be possible following your written consent, provided by signing this document.

Any research program implemented must first be approved by the National Bioethics Commission of Cyprus. Use of your personal information will be strictly confidential and secure, in accordance with Cyprus law 125(I)/2018) for implementation of the **European Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679**.

Sending Information and Samples Abroad: It is possible that, in the context of research programs, collaborations with researchers in other centers or universities, in Cyprus and abroad, may be undertaken in order to enhance and improve research results. Samples or coded items of your personal file may be sent to researchers abroad in the framework of such collaborations, always with SECURITY, ANONYMITY and confidentiality. By signing this consent form you agree that the Biobank can analyse any biological material provided and use the results of these analyses for the benefit of society and the general public.

As provided by law, processing controller is the Excellence Center - Biobank and Biomedical Research (CY-Biobank) and the University of Cyprus. The responsibility for data protection (Data Protection Officer – DPO) lies with the legal firm KOUSIOS KORFIOTIS PAPACHARALAMBOUS (<https://kkplaw.com/>).

Details of what will be requested and/or what will happen to programme participants

Registering and participating as a volunteer donor, either as a patient or as a healthy person, is deemed useful for the success of the Biobank goals and the wider project as described above, and does not pose any risk nor will it affect the treatment you are provided or you will be provided by your doctor, if you are a patient.

You will be asked to provide personal information about yourself and your medical history and access to your medical record. You may also be asked to provide recent blood and urine test results. You will then be asked to provide some biological material as described in a different question below.

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As part of your participation in the program, you will not suffer further discomfort or undergo a biopsy, if this is not appropriate or you do not wish to. Anything that needs to be done in the context of the investigation will always be discussed with your doctor and will be performed after you have been informed and signed this consent form. The results of the research are likely to have a direct or indirect medical benefit for you, your children, or other relatives. However, it should be made clear that due to the nature of the research, exporting useful results may take many months or years or something useful may never arise for you personally or your family members.

If you agree, and where applicable, you will complete a questionnaire for your personal and family history and undergo a series of specialized examinations and blood tests related to your physical condition and health, such as physical measurements (height, weight, waist circumference and hip, etc.), blood pressure measurement and arterial stiffness, grip force, spirometry, retinal image, etc. You will not incur any costs.

The above are only indicative and will be useful for your health, no matter which program you will participate in the future. If you are invited to join the Biobank under a specific research program upon your doctor's invitation, you may only undergo some of the above tests/analyses and additionally undergo some others for which your doctor will decide, **given that the program is approved by the National Bioethics Commission of Cyprus**. Please note that it is your right to accept only part of the tests or analyses required.

The results of haematological & biochemical tests and examinations will be shared with you during your visit to the Biobank by a healthcare professional.

Details of the funding of the research programme

The program is funded as follows:

European Union: EUR 15 million (for 7 years, until September 2026)

Republic of Cyprus: EUR 15 million

University of Cyprus: EUR 8 million

Funding from Cypriot sources is for 15 years, until September 2034.

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Details of any risks that may exist or any inconvenience that programme participants may incur

No discomfort beyond the blood and urine collection or other biological material is anticipated. Some people may have a small bruise at the puncture site, which will normally go away in a few days.

DNA analysis will be performed with the latest methods for determining the order of the genetic code “letters”, i.e. the nucleotides, which are the molecules making up the DNA. By using these methods, as described in this form, the programme allows for the determination of the sequence of the letters of the whole genome (genomic material) in at least 500 healthy family trios. Understanding the information that lies within the DNA is a difficult and complicated process. As technology advances, by studying the DNA experts are able to uncover useful information regarding your health and other behavioural characteristics, such as your mental health, increased risk for a cardiac condition or cancer etc, as well as genetic factors protecting from some chronic conditions, such as hypertension, diabetes and dementia. For some conditions it might be easier to come to conclusions, whereas for others great effort and discovery of new knowledge are required. Your voluntary participation will contribute towards achieving these noble goals of science and medicine. Your personal results might be ANONYMOUSLY included in local or international databases, along with the results from thousands of other volunteers across the world, for the enhancement of the world effort for combating diseases.

As with any database, an extremely small risk of a data breach cannot be completely ruled out. The University of Cyprus implements every available measure to eliminate this danger. The University of Cyprus IT Infrastructure Service, in collaboration with external advisors with expertise in data handling and protection, implements practices and mechanisms that protect against any theft or leak such as: storing data and servers in secure data centers that are under constant visual surveillance, software and virtual machine protection (Firewalls, Intrusion Detection/Prevention Systems), Use of Private Network Address (IP), High Availability Architecture, use of sophisticated passwords, use of antivirus software, and implementation of data center security policies. All of the above measures are the best practices for data security, **to ensure data will never be acquired by non-authorized individuals and institutions, without your consent.**

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Details of what information and/or what material will be collected under the programme, who will have access to it and for how long.

You will be asked for information about your demographics and your overall health, by requesting access to your medical record. From your medical record, data will be extracted about your symptoms, blood and urine tests, genetic or other tests, results and data from ultrasounds or other imaging methods, and generally anything that is considered evidence and gives information about your health. By providing your personal information and biological material, information regarding close relatives might ensue, which will **ALWAYS REMAIN CONFIDENTIAL**.

You will be asked to provide biological material as follows:

- a. Blood from which DNA and / or RNA, plasma, serum, cells will be isolated
- b. Mouthwash or saliva for isolation of DNA and / or RNA or another biological molecule
- c. Urine or hair or nasopharyngeal swab or other material
- d. Genetic/protein or other material from a biopsy that you may have undergone (or will undergo in the future) for medical reasons, with your consent.

Depending on the goals of the research programmes and funding in the upcoming years, your biological samples may be subjected to a series of analyses. This information will be accessible to those directly involved in the research, i.e. doctors, the project coordinator and researchers who sign a confidentiality form. The unlimited future distribution of material and data to other researchers in Cyprus or abroad will be anonymized so that the file and data cannot be linked to you.

In case of any complaint for any reason, please contact:

Marios Dimitriadis

Head of Research Support Service

University of Cyprus, PO. 20537, 1678 Nicosia

Tel: (+357) 22894287 | Fax: (+357) 22895506

E-mail: demetriades.a.marios@ucy.ac.cy

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Given the fact that you are an underage individual access is granted for 15 years, as per the duration of the present research programme. Upon completion of the 15-year time period your records will be anonymised so that you cannot be linked to them.

If new information that directly affects your health is discovered, would you like to be informed?

YES <input type="checkbox"/>	NO <input type="checkbox"/>	I CANNOT MAKE A DECISION NOW. PLEASE ASK AGAIN IF NEEDED <input type="checkbox"/>
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Details of what data will be generated for you within the programme, who will have access to them and for how long.

New knowledge will emerge about the aetiology of some of the diseases that you or other people suffer, new information that will help better diagnose or even treat illnesses, knowledge that may help invent new drugs for diseases such as heart diseases, kidney diseases, cancers etc.

As part of this programme, access to the anonymised data and research results will be possible as they will be very useful as reference data for future research. Access will be provided only to authorised personnel. Given the fact that you are an underage upon completion of the 15-year time period, access to your records will continue through a mechanism prohibiting recognition of the volunteer.

Expected benefit for participants

If you are healthy, data that may be useful for preventative purposes may emerge. As a result, you will be able to take some measures to protect your health. If you are a patient it is likely that the genetic or other justification for your illness will be found. This may help receive better treatment in the future. This may also extend to your close relatives, such as your

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children. While it may be possible in the future for researchers or the University of Cyprus to have financial benefits from the use of research results, you will not benefit financially, as you will not incur any financial burden.

Expected benefit for researchers and/or sponsors

There is no financial benefit to researchers or funders unless marketable copyrights arise. The main benefit for researchers is research publications in reputable journals that will give recognition and career advancement.

Details of termination or early postponement of the research programme.

No conditions for termination or early interruption of the program are anticipated.

Site and duration of storage of data and/or biological samples to be collected under the programme

Your demographic and clinical data will be digitally imported and stored in the REDCap program, which is an approved and secure web application for storing the data before importing it into the Biobank database. The University of Cyprus is licensed to use this application in a secure and controlled environment.

The University of Cyprus has a dedicated suite for the storage of records and samples, which is the Biobank. All biological samples collected will be stored encoded in Biobank in specially-locked -80°C freezers located in a separate locked room, or by another freezer mechanism.

The key is only accessible to the Coordinator and the person in charge of the Biobank. For the purposes of research and / or analysis of data derived from research programs, coded biological samples and anonymous results will be analyzed by partners in Cyprus or abroad. Given the fact that you are an underage upon completion of the 15-year time period, access to

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your records will continue through a mechanism prohibiting recognition of the volunteer.

Description of procedures of handling data and/or biological samples of participants who withdraw from the study prior to its completion.

In order not to interfere with the credibility of the research results that may be ongoing, and to minimize the loss of scientific benefit, if you decide to withdraw, you will be asked by the project manager if you agree for the Biobank to keep all of your data and biological samples that have been collected up to that point, in full anonymity and disconnected from your identifiable folder. If you do not agree, the Biobank will delete your personal data and results and destroy the biological samples

Full contact details and title of the person to whom participants can submit complaints or grievances regarding the programme they participate in.

Marios Dimitriadis
Head of Research Support Service
University of Cyprus, PO. 20537, 1678 Nicosia
Tel: (+357) 22894287 | Fax: (+357) 22895506
E-mail: demetriades.a.marios@ucy.ac.cy

Full contact details and title of the person whom participants can contact for more information or clarifications about the research programme.

Prof. Constantinos Deltas,
Director, Molecular Medicine Research Center
University of Cyprus
Panepistimiou 1, 2109, Nicosia
Tel: 22892815 / 22-892882 Email: Deltas@ucy.ac.cy

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(Form EEBK03-1)

CY-Biobank CoE and Incidental Findings

POLICY

The Biobank might become aware of incidental findings that could be actionable or not.

Disclosure will be considered when:

- The findings reveal an established risk of likely health importance to the participant and they have a likely therapeutic benefit
- The incidental findings must concern a disease that is susceptible to prevention, treatment or care actions (actionable)
- The incidental findings are of diagnostic or prognostic nature OR
- The incidental findings are related to important variants related to a life-threatening condition OR
- The incidental findings are heritable or related to a familial disease
- The findings arising from NGS technologies are verified and valid, i.e. have been confirmed independently by an accredited diagnostic lab if possible, or by a second verification method e.g. Sanger

For not actionable incidental findings, the Biobank will not proceed with validation unless they are part of exploratory projects performed by researchers employed at the CoE or collaborators.

For actionable incidental findings that meet the above criteria, the disclosure to the volunteer who chose to have a return of such findings, should be exercised only after the validation process has been completed and the variants have been scrutinized for their clinical use.

If possible, the results will be shared with the patient's doctor. The patient/doctor relationship will be preserved, and a face-to-face interview should be in the presence of a genetic counsellor.

In cases that the patient opted not to know, and the result could affect survival or quality of life of concerned members, the issue will be brought to the Academic Council and the CNBC for a final decision.

Biobank will make every effort to disseminate scientific knowledge after validating the results in accredited diagnostic laboratories. However, the presence of relevant accredited laboratories in Cyprus, personnel needs, and budget available for reaching a firm conclusion on the pathogenicity of each such variant will be considered.

Commentary:

In Cyprus, one of many obstacles in facilitating the evaluation of DNA variants found during diagnostic or research investigations, is the lack of any data at population level, *vis-a-vis* the frequency of such variants and/or their potential association with phenotype. To remedy this weakness, the CY-Biobank project has set as a priority the whole exome and/or genome sequencing of 1000 at first phase and another 1000 at second phase of Cypriots volunteers. The project is in progress.

DEFINITIONS

Incidental finding is a finding that is not related to the specific research project and disease entities that the volunteer agreed and consented to participate. An incidental finding may arise when researchers use DNA samples retrieved from the Biobank with the aim to answer questions of their own interest. Incidental findings may also arise when in their research pursuits, separate researchers or research groups come across potential actionable findings. An out of target search for actionable DNA variants is not be an obligatory objective for research through our Biobank, because it generates likely important ethical dilemmas concerning the verification of the variants and the mechanism to return upsetting results to the volunteer. Notwithstanding that these findings may be of ultimate usefulness to the donor, it is unpredictable how these findings may be received and understood by the donor.

In the framework of large genomics projects that include whole exome or whole genome sequencing of high numbers of volunteers, potential actionable findings may arise. These projects are usually performed in an anonymous format and the DNA variants are expected to be in the thousands. It is therefore challenging to perform the verification, evaluation, and disclosure of such findings to individual donors.

Volunteer may be a healthy person or a patient with a heritable or a complex chronic condition of any severity. In our Biobank, volunteers enrol upon signing a broad informed consent form, approved by the CNBC, and with the purpose to participate in research projects with no limitation or restriction, as long as the project is approved by the Cyprus National Bioethics Committee.

During enrolment, participants are informed about the uncommon likelihood of incidental actionable findings and can decide on their right and choice either to know or not to know. They will be informed about any implication that their choice to know about incidental actionable findings would have for insurance or employment, in which case the volunteer might prefer not to know even though it is a useful outcome on research grounds.

This workshop on incidental findings (IF) puts the focus especially on the ethical, legal and societal implications (ELSI). The programme comprises of presentations to provide an overview on incidental and secondary findings, involvement of vulnerable populations in biobanking with focus on minors, and break-out group discussions of two scenarios of IF featuring different stages of the process. The workshop will conclude with a presentation highlighting biobank governance and practical aspects regarding IF, and finally, a general discussion on IF policy.

Incidental Findings Scenario I

45 min (Break-out) 10 min (Plenum)

This template will guide your group to think about incidental findings as a process. The aim is to gather thoughts and ideas that will contribute to the CY-Biobank Incidental Findings Policy. This mural will be available until 1/1/2021 to allow further contributions by the workshop participants and CY-Biobank staff, who could not attend the workshop. You may find below further resources.

Instructions

- The session Incidental Findings Scenarios will take an hour. This includes:
- Break-out group discussion of 45 minutes,
- Reporting from break-out groups (Scenarios: I & II) in plenum for 10 minutes.
- The Mural will be available for further additions.
- Use the 45 minutes to discuss (1) steps of the process based on the case and (2) how to anticipate in a broader sense.
- The first activity is to synthesize insights that will contribute to the second activity.
- After 45 minutes, the break-out session will end and the two groups (Scenario I & II) will join.
- During the plenum (10 minutes), a member from each group will report the highlights of the discussion from own group.

General MURAL tips

- Select **Outline** from the top menu to move to each section of the board.
- To move around the board, **hold the spacebar, click and drag**.
- Zoom in and out from your mouse or trackpad or **Cmd/Ctrl** and **+** or **-** from your keyboard.
- Add sticky notes by **right-clicking** on the canvas or select from the **left-hand menu**.
- Edit sticky notes by **double-clicking** on text. To duplicate click and hold the **ALT** key.

0 Basic Information: The Incidental Finding and the Background

This section includes relevant information regarding the scenario, CMT and its genetics, as reference. It relies on the presentation of the scenarios by Kaya Akyüz.

Facilitator tip: Please proceed to the discussion and allow the discussion participants to make use of the information here, whenever questions arise regarding the scenario or CMT.

Case Report

Minor participant

Recruited for research project that includes **whole genome sequencing** (+ possibly aCGH)

Incidental finding (**genomic**): **Copy Number Variation** (CNV: Duplication of a 1.4 Mb region--17p12)

Known consequence: **CMT1A (demyelinating peripheral neuropathy)**

Possibly **sporadic**, no known case in the family

Participant has **no symptoms**

Expected progression:
 --usually early onset,
 --progressive sensory loss,
 --weakness in foot and lower leg muscles,
 --muscle atrophy in hands,
 --not fatal.

Predictive Testing: "For asymptomatic minors at risk for adult-onset conditions for which early treatment would have no beneficial effect on disease morbidity and mortality, predictive genetic testing is considered inappropriate, primarily because it negates the autonomy of the child with no compelling benefit." (*Gene Reviews*)

Oncology: "Over 30 medications have been identified as toxic or potentially toxic to persons with CMT... Vincristine and paclitaxel (chemotherapeutic agents) pose a definite high risk of nerve damage and should be avoided by all patients with CMT, including those who are asymptomatic." (*Actionability Knowledge Repository*)

Anesthesia: "Avoiding succinylcholine is recommended." (*ORPHANET*)

Further Resources

[Actionability Knowledge Repository: Recurrent CMT](#) [OMIM entry for CMT1A](#)

[ORPHANET entry for CMT](#) [NCBI Gene Reviews \(link for CMT\)](#)

[List of Neurotoxic Medication by CMT Association](#)

CY-Biobank Grant Agreement Sections on Incidental Findings

"We will provide details for handling unexpected or incidental findings and offer the choice for opting in or out. Per the official opinion prepared by the National Bioethics Committee, options will include for every participant to consent to be informed of incidental findings depending on several alternatives, including cases where there is treatment relating to the finding (actionable finding), or not. Preferably, the choice of the participant will be expressed at the time that they will sign the informed consent form for enrolling in the Biobank or when they enter the research program and provide the genetic material." (p. 76)

Expected and incidental findings return policy
 Researchers will be incited to disseminate scientific knowledge, especially if there is output of new actionable findings. During enrolment, participants will be informed about the likelihood of incidental findings and can decide on their right and choice not to know. They will be informed about any implication that their choice to know about incidental findings would have for insurance or employment. Where the participant agrees to have a return of such findings, these shall be scrutinized by the geneticists for their clinical use, before contacting the donor.

The following **criteria** will be used to decide the return policy:

- The incidental findings must aim a disease that is susceptible to prevention, treatment or care actions
- The incidental findings are of diagnostic nature OR
- The incidental findings are related to important variants related to a life-threatening condition OR
- The incidental findings are heritable or related to a familial disease.

Actionable incidental findings must be verified by the accredited diagnostic lab, and shared with the patient's doctor. The patient/doctor relationship will be preserved and a face-to-face interview should be in the presence of a genetic counselor. In cases that the patient opted not to know and the result could affect survival or quality of life of concerned members, the issue will be brought to the Academic Council and the CNBC for a final decision." (p. 45)

1 A Case to Test: CMT

Suggested time: 30 minutes

Consider the case above:
 What are **important elements of the process** of incidental findings, from informed consent to return of results and follow-up?

Facilitator tip: Lead the discussion for 30 minutes by thinking of elements relevant at different stages for a best practice return of incidental findings for this scenario.

2 How to Anticipate?

Suggested time: 15 mins

In the first activity, the aim was to think about the process from informing to feedback for a given incidental finding.

Facilitator tip: Encourage participants to synthesize ideas from the previous activity

For this activity, the aim is to think about **how to anticipate** the incidental findings and what can be done when **unanticipated findings** are encountered.

8 mins

Part 1 - How to anticipate?
 How can the biobank anticipate / select the incidental findings that are to be detected/sought for/communicated?

7 mins

Part 2 - What to do in case of unanticipated findings?
 Regardless of efforts to anticipate, incidental findings not yet anticipated by the biobank may emerge. How can the biobank be ready for unanticipated findings?

This workshop on incidental findings (IF) puts the focus especially on the ethical, legal and societal implications (ELSI). The programme comprises of presentations to provide an overview on incidental and secondary findings, involvement of vulnerable populations in biobanking with focus on minors, and break-out group discussions of two scenarios of IF featuring different stages of the process. The workshop will conclude with a presentation highlighting biobank governance and practical aspects regarding IF, and finally, a general discussion on IF policy.

Incidental Findings Scenario II

45 min (Break-out) 10 min (Plenum)

This template will guide your group to think about incidental findings as a process. The aim is to gather thoughts and ideas that will contribute to the CY-Biobank Incidental Findings Policy. This mural will be available until 1/1/2021 to allow further contributions by the workshop participants and CY-Biobank staff, who could not attend the workshop. You may find below further resources.

Instructions

- The session Incidental Findings Scenarios will take an hour. This includes:
- Break-out group discussion of 45 minutes,
- Reporting from break-out groups (Scenarios: I & II) in plenum for 10 minutes.
- The Mural will be available for further additions.
- Use the 45 minutes to discuss (1) steps of the process based on the case and (2) how to anticipate in a broader sense.
- The first activity is to synthesize insights that will contribute to the second activity.
- After 45 minutes, the break-out session will end and the two groups (Scenario I & II) will join.
- During the plenum (10 minutes), a member from each group will report the highlights of the discussion from own group.

General MURAL tips

- Select **Outline** from the top menu to move to each section of the board.
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0 Basic Information: The Incidental Finding and the Background

This section includes relevant information regarding the scenario, CMT and its genetics, as reference. It relies on the presentation of the scenarios by Kaya Akyüz.

Facilitator tip: Please proceed to the discussion and allow the discussion participants to make use of the information here, whenever questions arise regarding the scenario or CMT.

Case Report

Adult participant

Recruited for Cyprus Genome Project as part of a trio; **whole genome sequencing** conducted

Incidental finding (**genomic**): **Point Mutation (PMP22 C65->T, Ser22Phe, Autosomal Dominant)**

Known consequence: **CMT1A (demyelinating peripheral neuropathy), possibly HNPP**

Sporadic, mutation not identified in the rest of the trio

Participant has **no symptoms**

Expected progression:
 --variable onset and severity,
 --progressive distal muscle weakness and atrophy,
 --pes cavus deformity of the feet,
 --mild muscle atrophy in hands,
 --not fatal. See: Kleopa et al 2004

CMT: Actionability

Predictive Testing: "For asymptomatic minors at risk for adult-onset conditions for which early treatment would have no beneficial effect on disease morbidity and mortality, predictive genetic testing is considered inappropriate, primarily because it negates the autonomy of the child with no compelling benefit." (*Gene Reviews*)

Oncology: "Over 30 medications have been identified as toxic or potentially toxic to persons with CMT. [...] Vincristine and paclitaxel (chemotherapeutic agents) pose a definite high risk of nerve damage and should be avoided by all patients with CMT, including those who are asymptomatic." (*Actionability Knowledge Repository*)

Anesthesia: "Avoiding succinylcholine is recommended." (*ORPHANET*)

Further Resources

- Accessibility Knowledge Repository: Recurrent CMT
- OMIM entry for CMT1A
- ORPHANET entry for CMT
- NCBI Gene Reviews (link for CMT)
- List of Neurotoxic Medication by CMT Association

CY-Biobank Grant Agreement Sections on Incidental Findings

"We will provide details for handling unexpected or incidental findings and offer the choice for opting in or out. Per the official opinion prepared by the National Bioethics Committee, options will include for every participant to consent to be informed of incidental findings depending on several alternatives, including cases where there is treatment relating to the finding (actionable finding), or not. Preferably, the choice of the participant will be expressed at the time that they will sign the informed consent form for enrolling in the Biobank or when they enter the research program and provide the genetic material." (p. 76)

Expected and incidental findings return policy
 Researchers will be incited to disseminate scientific knowledge, especially if there is output of new actionable findings. During enrolment, participants will be informed about the likelihood of incidental findings and can decide on their right and choice not to know. They will be informed about any implication that their choice to know about incidental findings would have for insurance or employment. Where the participant agrees to have a return of such findings, these shall be scrutinized by the geneticists for their clinical use, before contacting the donor.

The following **criteria** will be used to decide the return policy:

- The incidental findings must aim a disease that is susceptible to prevention, treatment or care actions
- The incidental findings are of diagnostic nature OR
- The incidental findings are related to important variants related to a life-threatening condition OR
- The incidental findings are heritable or related to a familial disease.

Actionable incidental findings must be verified by the accredited diagnostic lab, and shared with the patient's doctor. The patient/doctor relationship will be preserved and a face-to-face interview should be in the presence of a genetic counselor. In cases that the patient opted not to know and the result could affect survival or quality of life of concerned members, the issue will be brought to the Academic Council and the CNBC for a final decision." (p. 45)

1 A Case to Test: CMT

Suggested time: 30 minutes

Consider the case above: What are **important elements of the process** of incidental findings, from informed consent to return of results and follow-up?

Facilitator tip: Lead the discussion for 30 minutes by thinking of elements relevant at different stages for a best practice return of incidental findings for this scenario.

2 How to Anticipate?

Suggested time: 15 mins

In the first activity, the aim was to think about the process from informing to feedback for a given incidental finding.

Facilitator tip: Encourage participants to synthesize ideas from the previous activity

For this activity, the aim is to think about **how to anticipate** the incidental findings and what can be done when **unanticipated findings** are encountered.

8 mins

Part 1 - How to anticipate?
 How can the biobank anticipate / select the incidental findings that are to be detected/sought for/communicated?

7 mins

Part 2 - What to do in case of unanticipated findings?
 Regardless of efforts to anticipate, incidental findings not yet anticipated by the biobank may emerge. How can the biobank be ready for unanticipated findings?

ROLE DESCRIPTION

Role title:	Genetic Counsellor	
Name of role holder:	N/A	
Supervisor:	Director <i>CY-Biobank</i> Centre of Excellence	
Representation: a) Representative for b) Represented by	-	-
Main tasks:		
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Interpret and explain genetic information to patients and concerned relatives 2. Help patients and other concerned family members to adapt to the various implications of a genetic condition and make informed decisions 		
Duties and Responsibilities:		
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Provide clear explanations to Biobank volunteers/patients about biobanking, including benefits, risks and limitations of donating biospecimens 2. Evaluate genetic information to identify patients or families at risk for specific genetic disorders 3. Write detailed consultation reports for providing information on complex genetic concepts to healthy volunteers, or patients or referring physicians 4. Participate in multidisciplinary teams for assessing clinical actionability of variants 5. Participate in advisory groups regarding the development and operations of the biobank 6. Participate in the design of information tools aimed at educating current and future potential donors about the biobank 7. Highlight unfair practices and potential ethical concerns and facilitate discussions about the social and ethical dimensions of research conducted with the use of material of the biobank 		
Qualification:		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MSc in Genetic/Genomic Counselling • Good knowledge of genetics and human genetic conditions • Good knowledge and ability to apply counselling methods and techniques • Ability to effectively communicate genetic information and genetic test results in a manner easily understood by the client/patient • Very good command of spoken and written Greek and English. Additional languages will be considered an advantage • Professional experience in an academic, laboratory or Biobank environment will be considered an advantage 		
Soft skills:		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critical-thinking, decision-making skills, communication skills • Service oriented, sociable and capable of working as part of a team • High-load capacity and emotional stability when faced with human suffering, emergencies, and additional stresses 		
Signature/date Role holder:	Signature/date Superior:	Signature/date Director General:

ΚΕΝΤΡΟ ΑΡΙΣΤΕΙΑΣ - ΒΙΟΤΡΑΠΕΖΑ ΚΑΙ ΒΙΟΙΑΤΡΙΚΗ ΕΡΕΥΝΑ, biobank.cy**ΕΝΤΥΠΟ ΑΝΑΚΛΗΣΗΣ ΣΥΓΚΑΤΑΘΕΣΗΣ****[για συμμετοχή ως εθελοντής δότης βιολογικού υλικού]****Ανάκληση Συγκατάθεσης:**

Εγώ ο/η

επιθυμώ να ανακαλέσω τη συγκατάθεσή μου για συμμετοχή ως εθελοντής δότης δεδομένων και βιολογικού υλικού:

Στη Βιοτράπεζα του Κέντρου Αριστείας - Βιοτράπεζα και Βιοϊατρική έρευνα, biobank.cy (**Βιοτράπεζα**)

Η εν λόγω ανάκληση συνεπάγεται ανάκληση συγκατάθεσης επεξεργασίας των προσωπικών μου δεδομένων από τη Βιοτράπεζα δυνάμει του άρθρου 7 παρ. 3 του Ευρωπαϊκού Γενικού Κανονισμού Προστασίας Δεδομένων 2016/679.

Δηλώνω ότι, έχω ενημερωθεί ότι για να μην επηρεασθεί η αξιοπιστία των αποτελεσμάτων έρευνας που ίσως βρίσκεται σε εξέλιξη, και να ελαχιστοποιηθεί η απώλεια του επιστημονικού οφέλους, στη περίπτωση απόφασής μου να αποσυρθώ, έχω ενημερωθεί για τους τρόπους ανάκλησης της συγκατάθεσής μου και έχω επιλέξει τον επιθυμητό τρόπο ανάκλησης όπως φαίνεται πιο κάτω.

Κατανοώ ότι σε περίπτωση επιλογής «Χωρίς περαιτέρω χρήση», η **Βιοτράπεζα** θα καταστρέψει με ασφάλη μέσα τα δεδομένα ή, εναλλακτικά, τα δεδομένα θα ανωνυμοποιηθούν πλήρως και θα αποσυνδεθούν από τα δείγματα που συλλέχθηκαν (irretrievably unlink) αφού ο κωδικός που χρησιμοποιείται για επανασύνδεση των δειγμάτων και των προσωπικών δεδομένων θα διαγραφεί. Μόνο το υπογεγραμμένο έντυπο συγκατάθεσης και ένα αντίγραφο του παρόντος εντύπου ανάκλησης συγκατάθεσης που επιβεβαιώνει την απόσυρσή μου θα φυλάσσονται για σκοπούς αρχειοθέτησης/αποδεικτικού στοιχείου της επιλογής ανάκλησης και για σκοπούς αποτροπής περαιτέρω χρήσης πληροφοριών σχετικά με εμένα σε έρευνα.

Τέλος, κατανοώ ότι τα δεδομένα δεν μπορούν να αφαιρεθούν από ήδη ολοκληρωμένες μελέτες / επιστημονικές αναλύσεις **που έγιναν με χρήση των δεδομένων και του βιολογικού υλικού μου**, καθώς επίσης **κατανοώ** ότι υπάρχει πιθανότητα να μην είναι δυνατή η ανίχνευση όλων των κατανεμημένων δειγμάτων.

Επιλογές ανάκλησης συγκατάθεσης (επιλέξτε με ✓)

- **«Χωρίς περαιτέρω επικοινωνία»:** Το Κέντρο δεν θα επικοινωνεί πλέον με κανένα μέσο με τον εθελοντή αλλά δύναται να συνεχίσει να χρησιμοποιεί τα δείγματα και τα δεδομένα που έχουν ήδη συλλεχθεί και δύναται να συνεχίσει να έχει πρόσβαση στο ιατρικό του ιστορικό εάν αυτό είναι απαραίτητο.
- **«Χωρίς περαιτέρω πρόσβαση»:** Η Βιοτράπεζα δεν θα επικοινωνήσει με τον εθελοντή και δε θα έχει δυνατότητα πρόσβασης στο ιατρικό ιστορικό του αλλά μπορεί να συνεχίσει να χρησιμοποιεί δείγματα και δεδομένα που έχουν ήδη συλλεχθεί.
- **«Χωρίς περαιτέρω χρήση»:** Το Κέντρο θα καταστρέψει ή θα ανωνυμοποιήσει όλα τα δείγματα και δεδομένα από τον εθελοντή και δεν θα επικοινωνήσει με τον συμμετέχοντα ξανά. Ως εκ τούτου, τυχόν πληροφορίες και δείγματα που συλλέχθηκαν προηγουμένως δεν θα είναι πλέον διαθέσιμα σε ερευνητές.

Ημερομηνία:

Υπογραφή: